

Assessing Emergency and Critical Care in District Hospitals in Malawi

Codebook ▾

Data Dictionary Codebook

06/22/2020 11:29am

^ Collapse all instruments

#	Variable / Field Name	Field Label <i>Field Note</i>	Field Attributes (Field Type, Validation, Choices, Calculations, etc.)																											
Instrument: Administrator (administrator) ^ Collapse																														
1	adm_record_id	Record ID <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 1																											
2	adm_date	Interview date and time (Day-Month-Year; 24 hour clock) <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	text (datetime_dmy), Required Question number: 2																											
3	adm_country	Country <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	text Question number: 3																											
4	adm_facility	Name of facility <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	text, Required Question number: 4																											
5	adm_address	Address of facility <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	text Question number: 5																											
6	adm_facility_level	Level of facility <i>Do not read choices</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Health centre or clinic</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1st level hospital</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>2nd level hospital</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Tertiary hospital</td></tr> </table>	1	Health centre or clinic	2	1st level hospital	3	2nd level hospital	4	Tertiary hospital																			
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7	adm_facility_type	Type of facility <i>read choices, check all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>adm_facility_type__1</td><td>Private hospital</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>adm_facility_type__2</td><td>NGO hospital</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>adm_facility_type__3</td><td>Government hospital</td></tr> </table>	1	adm_facility_type__1	Private hospital	2	adm_facility_type__2	NGO hospital	3	adm_facility_type__3	Government hospital																		
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2	adm_facility_type__2	NGO hospital																												
3	adm_facility_type__3	Government hospital																												
8	adm_higher_level_distance	Distance to nearest higher level facility (km) <i>can give best estimate, enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 10																											
9	adm_higher_level_time	How long (in hours) does it take to get to the nearest higher-level facility? <i>time it takes driving in a vehicle directly there</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 11																											
10	adm_population	Population served by facility (e.g., 123000) <i>can give best estimate, enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 200000000)																											
11	has_ed	Is there an area (room, unit, department) specifically designated for emergency care?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> </table> Question number: 13	0	No	1	Yes																							
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
12	adm_ed_pts Show the field ONLY if: [has_ed] = '1'	What types of patients are seen in the emergency unit? <i>read all choices, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>adm_ed_pts__1</td><td>Medical adult patients</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>adm_ed_pts__2</td><td>Medical pediatric patients</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>adm_ed_pts__3</td><td>Surgical adult patients</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>adm_ed_pts__4</td><td>Surgical pediatric patients</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>adm_ed_pts__5</td><td>Trauma adult patients</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>adm_ed_pts__6</td><td>Trauma pediatric patients</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>adm_ed_pts__7</td><td>OB patients</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>adm_ed_pts__8</td><td>GYN patients</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>adm_ed_pts__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table> Question number: 14	1	adm_ed_pts__1	Medical adult patients	2	adm_ed_pts__2	Medical pediatric patients	3	adm_ed_pts__3	Surgical adult patients	4	adm_ed_pts__4	Surgical pediatric patients	5	adm_ed_pts__5	Trauma adult patients	6	adm_ed_pts__6	Trauma pediatric patients	7	adm_ed_pts__7	OB patients	8	adm_ed_pts__8	GYN patients	9	adm_ed_pts__9	Other
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9	adm_ed_pts__9	Other																												

13	adm_ed_pts_spec Show the field ONLY if: [adm_ed_pts(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
14	has_opd	Is there an outpatient department (OPD) at your hospital?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 15</p>	0	No	1	Yes																							
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
15	adm_eval_location Show the field ONLY if: [has_ed] = '0'	Where are critically ill patients initially evaluated once they arrive at your hospital? <i>do not read all choices, select all that apply</i>	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>adm_eval_location__1</td> <td>OPD</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>adm_eval_location__2</td> <td>Emergency unit</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>adm_eval_location__3</td> <td>Ward</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>adm_eval_location__4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	adm_eval_location__1	OPD	2	adm_eval_location__2	Emergency unit	3	adm_eval_location__3	Ward	4	adm_eval_location__4	Other															
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4	adm_eval_location__4	Other																												
16	adm_eval_location_spec Show the field ONLY if: [adm_eval_location(3)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
17	has_icuhdu	Is there a high dependency unit (HDU) and/or intensive care unit (ICU) with a dedicated space in the hospital? <i>ICU or HDU is defined as a designated area in the hospital for critically ill patients not part of a general medicine ward or other area.</i>	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes																							
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18	has_icu_with_vents	Does this hospital have a unit with capacity for continuous monitoring and mechanical ventilation?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 18</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
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19	adm_icuhdu_pts Show the field ONLY if: [has_icuhdu] = '1'	What types of patients are admitted to the HDU and/or ICU? <i>Do not read choices, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>adm_icuhdu_pts__1</td> <td>Medical adult patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>adm_icuhdu_pts__2</td> <td>Medical pediatric patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>adm_icuhdu_pts__3</td> <td>Surgical adult patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>adm_icuhdu_pts__4</td> <td>Surgical pediatric patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>adm_icuhdu_pts__5</td> <td>Trauma adult patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>adm_icuhdu_pts__6</td> <td>Trauma pediatric patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>adm_icuhdu_pts__7</td> <td>OB patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>adm_icuhdu_pts__8</td> <td>GYN patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>adm_icuhdu_pts__9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	adm_icuhdu_pts__1	Medical adult patients	2	adm_icuhdu_pts__2	Medical pediatric patients	3	adm_icuhdu_pts__3	Surgical adult patients	4	adm_icuhdu_pts__4	Surgical pediatric patients	5	adm_icuhdu_pts__5	Trauma adult patients	6	adm_icuhdu_pts__6	Trauma pediatric patients	7	adm_icuhdu_pts__7	OB patients	8	adm_icuhdu_pts__8	GYN patients	9	adm_icuhdu_pts__9	Other
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20	adm_icuhdu_pts_spec Show the field ONLY if: [adm_icuhdu_pts(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
21	adm_where_cc	Tell me all areas in the hospital where critically ill patients managed? <i>Read all options, select all that apply. ICU or HDU is defined as a designated area in the hospital for critically ill patients not part of a general medicine ward or other area.</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>adm_where_cc__1</td> <td>ICU or HDU</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>adm_where_cc__2</td> <td>Post-operative recovery area</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>adm_where_cc__3</td> <td>Emergency unit</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>adm_where_cc__4</td> <td>Cohorted area of regular ward</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>adm_where_cc__5</td> <td>Interspersed on regular ward</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>adm_where_cc__6</td> <td>Operating theater</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>adm_where_cc__7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 20</p>	1	adm_where_cc__1	ICU or HDU	2	adm_where_cc__2	Post-operative recovery area	3	adm_where_cc__3	Emergency unit	4	adm_where_cc__4	Cohorted area of regular ward	5	adm_where_cc__5	Interspersed on regular ward	6	adm_where_cc__6	Operating theater	7	adm_where_cc__7	Other						
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22	adm_where_cc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [adm_where_cc(7)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
23	adm_ed_visits Show the field ONLY if: [has_ed] = '1'	Emergency unit visits per year <i>can give best estimate, enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 21																											
24	adm_outpt_visits	Outpatient visits per year (excluding emergency unit visits) <i>can give best estimate, enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 22																											
25	adm_inpt_admits	Inpatient admissions per year <i>can give best estimate, enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 23																											
26	adm_ed_beds	Beds/gurneys dedicated for general emergency care (not including inpatient beds) <i>can give best estimate, enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 24																											
27	adm_inpt_beds	Inpatient hospital beds <i>can give best estimate, enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 25																											
28	adm_number_or	Functioning operating theatres (24/7) <i>The operating theatre must be functioning 24/7 to count. Enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 26																											
29	adm_surg_type	What types of surgeries can be performed at this facility? <i>Read options, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>adm_surg_type__1</td> <td>C-section</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>adm_surg_type__2</td> <td>Other OB/GYN surgery</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>adm_surg_type__3</td> <td>General adult surgery</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>adm_surg_type__4</td> <td>General pediatric surgery</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>adm_surg_type__5</td> <td>Orthopedic surgery</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>adm_surg_type__6</td> <td>Neurosurgery</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>adm_surg_type__7</td> <td>Other sub-specialty surgery</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>adm_surg_type__0</td> <td>None</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>adm_surg_type__1</td> <td>Unknown</td> </tr> </table> Question number: 27	1	adm_surg_type__1	C-section	2	adm_surg_type__2	Other OB/GYN surgery	3	adm_surg_type__3	General adult surgery	4	adm_surg_type__4	General pediatric surgery	5	adm_surg_type__5	Orthopedic surgery	6	adm_surg_type__6	Neurosurgery	7	adm_surg_type__7	Other sub-specialty surgery	0	adm_surg_type__0	None	-1	adm_surg_type__1	Unknown
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30	adm_surg_type_spec Show the field ONLY if: [adm_surg_type(7)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
31	adm_emer_surg	Emergency operations per year <i>Can give best estimate, enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 28																											
32	adm_ed_24h Show the field ONLY if: [has_ed] = '1'	Is the emergency unit open 24 hours a day?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
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33	<p>adm_ed_timeopen</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [adm_ed_24h] = '0'</p>	<p>When does the Emergency Unit open?</p> <p><i>round to nearest hour</i></p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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<p>34</p>	<p>adm_ed_timeclose</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [adm_ed_24h] = '0'</p>	<p>When does the Emergency Unit close?</p> <p><i>round to nearest hour</i></p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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36	adm_opd_timeopen Show the field ONLY if: [adm_opd_24h] = '0'	When does the OPD open? <i>round to nearest hour</i>	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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37	adm_opd_timeclose Show the field ONLY if: [adm_opd_24h] = '0'	When does the OPD close? <i>round to nearest hour</i>	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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38	adm_lab_24h	Is the laboratory open 24 hours a day? <i>Do not read choices</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>There is no laboratory at this facility</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know	-2	There is no laboratory at this facility																																								
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39	<p>adm_lab_timeopen</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [adm_lab_24h] = '0'</p>	<p>When does the laboratory open?</p> <p><i>round to nearest hour</i></p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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41	adm_pharm_24h	Is the pharmacy open 24 hours a day? <i>do not read choices</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>There is no pharmacy at this facility</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know	-2	There is no pharmacy at this facility																																								
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<p>43</p>	<p>adm_pharm_timeclose</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [adm_pharm_24h] = '0'</p>	<p>When does the pharmacy close?</p> <p><i>round to nearest hour</i></p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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<p>44</p>	<p>adm_rads_24h</p>	<p>Is radiology open 24 hours a day?</p> <p><i>do not read choices</i></p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>There is no radiology at this facility</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know	-2	There is no radiology at this facility																																								
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46	<p>adm_rads_timeclose</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [adm_rads_24h] = '0'</p>	<p>When does radiology close?</p> <p><i>round to nearest hour</i></p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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47	adm_or_timeopen Show the field ONLY if: [adm_number_or] = '0'	When does the operating theatre open? <i>round to nearest hour</i>	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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48	adm_or_timeclose Show the field ONLY if: [adm_number_or] = '0'	When does the operating theatre close? <i>round to nearest hour</i>	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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49	administrator_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>Incomplete</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Unverified</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Complete</td></tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete																																										
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Instrument: **Clinician OPD** (clinician_opd) [^ Collapse](#)

50	opd_record_id Record ID	Section Header: <i>OUTPATIENT DEPARTMENT (OPD)</i> Record ID	text (integer, Min: 0, Max: 1000000), Required										
51	opd_facility	Name of facility <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	text, Required										
52	opd_has_ed	Is there an ED in this hospital? <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes						
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53	opd_clin_lead	Is this participant a clinical lead of the OPD? <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes						
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54	opd_date	Interview date and time (Day-Month-Year; 24 hour clock)	text (datetime_dmy)										
55	opd_where_work	Section Header: <i>Outpatient Department (OPD)A. Background Questions</i> Where in the hospital do you primarily work? <i>if the respondent works in multiple areas, ask them to choose the area they work in the most often</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Outpatient Department (OPD)</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Emergency unit (ED)</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Inpatient ward</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>HDU/ICU</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table> Question number: 1	1	Outpatient Department (OPD)	2	Emergency unit (ED)	3	Inpatient ward	4	HDU/ICU	5	Other
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56	<p>opd_where_work_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_where_work] = '5' or [opd_where_work] = '3'</p>	Please specify	text																																																
57	opd_role	<p>What is your role?</p> <p><i>read all choices</i></p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Doctor</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Nurse</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Clinical Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Medical Assistant</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 2</p>	1	Doctor	2	Nurse	3	Clinical Officer	4	Medical Assistant	5	Other																																						
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58	<p>opd_role_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_role] = '5'</p>	Please specify	text																																																
59	<p>opd_days_at_opd</p>	<p>How many days per week do you work in the OPD?</p> <p><i>enter -1 if unknown</i></p>	<p>text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 7)</p> <p>Question number: 3</p>																																																
60	opd_hours_prsnt	<p>Section Header: <i>Outpatient Department (OPD)B. Hospital Structure/Staffing</i></p> <p>During which hours is the OPD covered by providers who are physically present in the OPD?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than 24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>The OPD is never covered by providers who are physically present in the OPD</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 4</p>	1	24 hours a day	2	Less than 24 hours a day	-1	Don't know	-2	The OPD is never covered by providers who are physically present in the OPD																																								
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61	<p>opd_hours_prsnt_start</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_hours_prsnt] = '2'</p>	Coverage starts at	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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<p>62</p>	<p>opd_hours_prsnt_stop</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_hours_prsnt] = '2'</p>	<p>Coverage ends at</p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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<p>63</p>	<p>opd_hours_in</p>	<p>During which hours is the OPD covered by providers who are on call, inside the facility?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than 24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>The OPD is never covered by providers who are on call, inside the facility</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 5</p>	1	24 hours a day	2	Less than 24 hours a day	-1	Don't know	-2	The OPD is never covered by providers who are on call, inside the facility																																								
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64	<p>opd_hours_in_start</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_hours_in] = '2'</p>	<p>Coverage starts at</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">dropdown</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	dropdown		12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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68	<p>opd_hours_out_stop</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_hours_out] = '2'</p>	<p>Coverage ends at</p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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69	<p>opd_rn_available</p>	<p>Are nurses available 24 hours a day, every day of the week in the OPD for critically ill patients in the OPD? <i>read all choices</i></p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes, in the OPD</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Yes, on call within the facility</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Yes, on call outside the facility</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 7</p>	0	No	1	Yes, in the OPD	2	Yes, on call within the facility	3	Yes, on call outside the facility	-1	Don't know																																						
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3	Yes, on call outside the facility																																																		
-1	Don't know																																																		
70	<p>opd_has_cc_bed</p>	<p>Do you have beds/space reserved in the OPD for critically ill patients? <i>critically ill patients are patients who come to the OPD who need further assessment and immediate stabilizing treatment. These should be different from regular exam spaces for standard outpatients</i></p>	<p>radio, Required</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 8</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																																										
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-1	Don't know																																																		
71	<p>opd_cc_beds</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_cc_bed] = '1'</p>	<p>How many beds in the OPD are reserved for critically ill patients? <i>enter -1 if unknown</i></p>	<p>text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 9</p>																																																
72	<p>opd_cc_nightbeds</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_cc_bed] = '1'</p>	<p>How many of these beds for critically ill patients can have patients overnight? <i>enter 0 if no patients can be in these beds overnight, enter -1 if unknown</i></p>	<p>text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 10</p>																																																
73	<p>opd_cc_rn_avgday</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_cc_bed] = '1' and [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>How many nurse(s) are assigned to these beds for critically ill patients on an average daytime shift? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to these beds, enter -1 if unknown</i></p>	<p>text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 14</p>																																																

74	<p>opd_cc_rn_today</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_cc_bed] = '1' and [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>How many nurse(s) are assigned to these beds for critically ill patients today?</p> <p><i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to these beds, enter -1 if unknown</i></p>	<p>text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000)</p> <p>Question number: 15</p>						
75	<p>opd_cc_rn_avgnight</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cc_nightbeds] >= 1 and [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>How many nurses are assigned to these beds for critically ill patients on an average overnight shift?</p> <p><i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to these beds, enter -1 if unknown</i></p>	<p>text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000)</p> <p>Question number: 16</p>						
76	<p>opd_cc_rn_lastnight</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cc_nightbeds] >= 1 and [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>How many nurses were assigned to these beds for critically ill patients last night?</p> <p><i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to these beds, enter -1 if unknown</i></p>	<p>text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000)</p> <p>Question number: 17</p>						
77	<p>opd_cc_census</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>How many critically ill patients are currently in your OPD?</p> <p><i>This includes all critically ill patients in any bed patients, not just those in designated beds. Enter -1 if unknown</i></p>	<p>text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000)</p> <p>Question number: 18</p>						
78	<p>opd_to_inpt</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Outpatient Department (OPD) C. Transfers and Patient Flow</i></p> <p>Does the OPD transfer patients directly to inpatient wards in this hospital?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 23</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
79	<p>opd_sick_accept</p>	<p>Are patients ever too sick (meaning unstable vital signs or requiring interventions or monitoring that are too frequent or prognosis is too poor) to be accepted into the OPD?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 24</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
80	<p>opd_sick_accept_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_sick_accept] = '1'</p>	<p>Please specify</p>	<p>text</p>						
81	<p>opd_sick_trans</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_to_inpt] = '1'</p>	<p>Are patients ever too sick (meaning unstable vital signs or requiring interventions or monitoring that are too frequent or prognosis is too poor) to be transferred from the OPD to the inpatient wards of this hospital and need to stay in the OPD as a result?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 25</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
82	<p>opd_sick_trans_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_sick_trans] = '1'</p>	<p>Please specify</p>	<p>text</p>						
83	<p>opd_transfer_out</p>	<p>Does the OPD transfer patients from the OPD directly to other hospitals or health facilities?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 27</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
84	<p>opd_transfer_number</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	<p>Approximately how many patients were transferred out from the OPD to other hospitals or health facilities in the last month?</p> <p><i>Ask respondent to give best guess, (for example: they can consider how many patients they personally have transferred and what % of the time they work in the OPD). Enter -1 if unable to give best guess</i></p>	<p>text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000)</p> <p>Question number: 28</p>						

85	<p>opd_trans_dka</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>For the following conditions, indicate how often patient with that condition is transferred out to another hospital. Please consider only patients who are actually transferred, not how often you feel a patient with this condition requires transfer.</i></p> <p>Diabetic ketoacidosis</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 29</p>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
86	<p>opd_trans_seizures</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Seizures	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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87	<p>opd_trans_poisoning</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Poisoning	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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88	<p>opd_trans_chf</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Severe heart failure	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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89	<p>opd_trans_arf</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Severe renal failure	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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90	<p>opd_trans_respiratory</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Respiratory distress or respiratory failure	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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91	<p>opd_trans_shock</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Low blood pressure or shock	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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92	<p>opd_trans_ams</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Coma (altered mental status or decreased level of consciousness)	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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93	<p>opd_trans_stroke</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Suspected stroke	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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94	<p>opd_trans_head_trauma</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Severe head trauma	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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95	<p>opd_trans_open_frac</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Open fracture	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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96	<p>opd_trans_closed_frac</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Closed long bone fracture (e.g. femur)	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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97	<p>opd_trans_other_trauma</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Other trauma	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know															
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98	<p>opd_trans_obstructed_labor</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Obstructed labor	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know															
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99	<p>opd_trans_pph</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	Post-partum hemorrhage	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know															
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100	<p>opd_ambulance</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	When patients are transferred from the OPD to another hospital/healthcare facility, how often is it by ambulance?	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 30</p>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know															
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5	Almost always																													
-1	Don't know																													
101	<p>opd_trans_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	<p>What, if any, barriers do you commonly encounter when transferring patients to another hospital/healthcare facility?</p> <p><i>Do not read choices, select all that apply</i></p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_trans_barrier__1</td><td>Patient finances</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_trans_barrier__2</td><td>Availability of transportation</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_trans_barrier__3</td><td>Patient too sick to transfer</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_trans_barrier__4</td><td>Bed space at accepting hospital</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_trans_barrier__5</td><td>Approval for transfer from accepting hospital</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_trans_barrier__6</td><td>Family objection</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_trans_barrier__7</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>opd_trans_barrier__0</td><td>No barriers</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>opd_trans_barrier__1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 31</p>	1	opd_trans_barrier__1	Patient finances	2	opd_trans_barrier__2	Availability of transportation	3	opd_trans_barrier__3	Patient too sick to transfer	4	opd_trans_barrier__4	Bed space at accepting hospital	5	opd_trans_barrier__5	Approval for transfer from accepting hospital	6	opd_trans_barrier__6	Family objection	7	opd_trans_barrier__7	Other	0	opd_trans_barrier__0	No barriers	-1	opd_trans_barrier__1	Don't know
1	opd_trans_barrier__1	Patient finances																												
2	opd_trans_barrier__2	Availability of transportation																												
3	opd_trans_barrier__3	Patient too sick to transfer																												
4	opd_trans_barrier__4	Bed space at accepting hospital																												
5	opd_trans_barrier__5	Approval for transfer from accepting hospital																												
6	opd_trans_barrier__6	Family objection																												
7	opd_trans_barrier__7	Other																												
0	opd_trans_barrier__0	No barriers																												
-1	opd_trans_barrier__1	Don't know																												
102	<p>opd_trans_barrier_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_trans_barrier(7)] = '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

<p>103</p>	<p>opd_trans_accompany</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	<p>When critically ill patients are transferred to other facilities by ambulance, what, if any, staff typically accompany the patient, other than driver? <i>do not read choices, check all that apply</i></p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>opd_trans_accompany__1</td> <td>Nurse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>opd_trans_accompany__2</td> <td>Clinical officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>opd_trans_accompany__3</td> <td>Medical assistant</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>opd_trans_accompany__4</td> <td>Doctors without specialist training</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>opd_trans_accompany__5</td> <td>Emergency medicine specialists</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>opd_trans_accompany__6</td> <td>Other specialist doctor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>opd_trans_accompany__7</td> <td>Emergency medical technician/paramedic</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>opd_trans_accompany__8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>opd_trans_accompany__0</td> <td>Staff do not typically accompany critically ill patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>opd_trans_accompany__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-2</td> <td>opd_trans_accompany__2</td> <td>Patients do not go by ambulance</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 32</p>	1	opd_trans_accompany__1	Nurse	2	opd_trans_accompany__2	Clinical officer	3	opd_trans_accompany__3	Medical assistant	4	opd_trans_accompany__4	Doctors without specialist training	5	opd_trans_accompany__5	Emergency medicine specialists	6	opd_trans_accompany__6	Other specialist doctor	7	opd_trans_accompany__7	Emergency medical technician/paramedic	8	opd_trans_accompany__8	Other	0	opd_trans_accompany__0	Staff do not typically accompany critically ill patients	-1	opd_trans_accompany__1	Don't know	-2	opd_trans_accompany__2	Patients do not go by ambulance
1	opd_trans_accompany__1	Nurse																																		
2	opd_trans_accompany__2	Clinical officer																																		
3	opd_trans_accompany__3	Medical assistant																																		
4	opd_trans_accompany__4	Doctors without specialist training																																		
5	opd_trans_accompany__5	Emergency medicine specialists																																		
6	opd_trans_accompany__6	Other specialist doctor																																		
7	opd_trans_accompany__7	Emergency medical technician/paramedic																																		
8	opd_trans_accompany__8	Other																																		
0	opd_trans_accompany__0	Staff do not typically accompany critically ill patients																																		
-1	opd_trans_accompany__1	Don't know																																		
-2	opd_trans_accompany__2	Patients do not go by ambulance																																		
<p>104</p>	<p>opd_trans_accompany_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_trans_accompany(8)] = '1'</p>	<p>Please specify</p>	<p>text</p>																																	
<p>105</p>	<p>opd_trans_treatment</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfer_out] = '1' and [opd_trans_accompany(-2)] <> '1'</p>	<p>When patients are transferred to other facilities by ambulance, what if any treatments can be done in the ambulance? <i>read choices, check all that apply</i></p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>opd_trans_treatment__1</td> <td>Vital sign monitoring</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>opd_trans_treatment__2</td> <td>Cardiac monitoring</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>opd_trans_treatment__3</td> <td>IV fluid administration</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>opd_trans_treatment__4</td> <td>IV medication administration</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>opd_trans_treatment__5</td> <td>Blood transfusion</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>opd_trans_treatment__6</td> <td>Oxygen delivery</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>opd_trans_treatment__7</td> <td>Manual bag ventilation (through endotracheal tube or bag-valve-mask)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>opd_trans_treatment__8</td> <td>Mechanical non-invasive ventilation (BIPAP or CPAP)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>opd_trans_treatment__9</td> <td>Mechanical invasive ventilation with endotracheal tube</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>opd_trans_treatment__0</td> <td>None</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>opd_trans_treatment__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 33</p>	1	opd_trans_treatment__1	Vital sign monitoring	2	opd_trans_treatment__2	Cardiac monitoring	3	opd_trans_treatment__3	IV fluid administration	4	opd_trans_treatment__4	IV medication administration	5	opd_trans_treatment__5	Blood transfusion	6	opd_trans_treatment__6	Oxygen delivery	7	opd_trans_treatment__7	Manual bag ventilation (through endotracheal tube or bag-valve-mask)	8	opd_trans_treatment__8	Mechanical non-invasive ventilation (BIPAP or CPAP)	9	opd_trans_treatment__9	Mechanical invasive ventilation with endotracheal tube	0	opd_trans_treatment__0	None	-1	opd_trans_treatment__1	Don't know
1	opd_trans_treatment__1	Vital sign monitoring																																		
2	opd_trans_treatment__2	Cardiac monitoring																																		
3	opd_trans_treatment__3	IV fluid administration																																		
4	opd_trans_treatment__4	IV medication administration																																		
5	opd_trans_treatment__5	Blood transfusion																																		
6	opd_trans_treatment__6	Oxygen delivery																																		
7	opd_trans_treatment__7	Manual bag ventilation (through endotracheal tube or bag-valve-mask)																																		
8	opd_trans_treatment__8	Mechanical non-invasive ventilation (BIPAP or CPAP)																																		
9	opd_trans_treatment__9	Mechanical invasive ventilation with endotracheal tube																																		
0	opd_trans_treatment__0	None																																		
-1	opd_trans_treatment__1	Don't know																																		
<p>106</p>	<p>opd_arrive_ambulance</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Outpatient Department (OPD)D. Clinical</i></p> <p>What proportion (%) of patients with emergency conditions are brought to the facility by ambulance with formally trained prehospital care providers? <i>enter -1 if unknown</i></p>	<p>text (number, Min: -2, Max: 100)</p> <p>Question number: 34</p>																																	

107	<p>opd_must_triage</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Are there regulations and/or protocols mandating that acutely ill or injured patients are clinically triaged prior to being required to register?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 35</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
108	<p>opd_must_pay</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Does the facility require payment prior to provision of initial emergency care?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 36</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
109	<p>opd_electronic_register</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Is there an electronic system for registration?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 37</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
110	<p>opd_has_triage</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Does this facility use a formal triage system (includes a structured triage tool used by trained personnel 24 hours per day, 7 days per week)?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 38</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
111	<p>opd_triage_system</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_triage] = '1' and [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Which system? <i>enter -1 if unknown</i></p>	<p>text</p> <p>Question number: 39</p>						
112	<p>opd_triage_attempted</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_triage] = '0' and [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Has triage ever been attempted?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 40</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
113	<p>opd_triage_timing</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_triage] = '1' and [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Are there time targets for each triage category (e.g. YELLOW-seen by provider within 2 hours)?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 41</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
114	<p>opd_triage_tracked</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_triage_timing] = '1' and [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Is compliance (to time targets) tracked regularly?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 42</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
115	<p>opd_triage_peds</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Are there specific triage protocols for children < 5 years of age?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 43</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								

116	<p>opd_triage_pregnant</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Are there specific triage protocols for pregnant women?	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 44</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
117	<p>opd_protocol_triage</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Are the following protocols available at this facility</i></p> <p>Protocol for systematic triage that ensure patients are seen in order of acuity</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 45</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
118	<p>opd_protocol_surveillance</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Syndromic surveillance guidelines with links to public health officials for case definition and reporting	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
119	<p>opd_protocol_crowding</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Clear protocol for communication with hospital administration during times of overcrowding	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
120	<p>opd_protocol_ext_event</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	OPD specific emergency response protocol, including protocol for mass casualty incidents?	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
121	<p>opd_protocol_abcde</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Are the following clinical management protocols available at this facility</i></p> <p>Protocol for initial approach to ABCs (airway, breathing, circulation, etc.) and basic neurologic function</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 46</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
122	<p>opd_protocol_trauma</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Trauma care checklist	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
123	<p>opd_protocol_med_resus</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Medical resuscitation checklist	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
124	<p>opd_protocol_neo_resus</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Protocol for neonatal resuscitation	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
125	<p>opd_protocol_volume</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Protocol for volume resuscitation of children and adults	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
126	<p>opd_protocol_malnourish</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Protocol for adjusting interventions for malnourished patients	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								

127	<p>opd_protocol_pt_pep</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Protocol for post-exposure prevention of STI/HIV, emergency contraception, counseling	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
128	<p>opd_protocol_labor</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Protocol for management of labor and delivery in low risk women	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
129	<p>opd_protocol_asthma</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Condition-specific management protocols for</i></p> <p>Asthma exacerbation</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 47</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
130	<p>opd_protocol_pneumonia</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Pneumonia	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
131	<p>opd_protocol_ob_bleed</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Maternal hemorrhage	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
132	<p>opd_protocol_sepsis</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Sepsis	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
133	<p>opd_protocol_dka</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Diabetic ketoacidosis	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
134	<p>opd_protocol_other</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Other	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
135	<p>opd_protocol_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_protocol_other] = '1'</p>	Please specify	text						
136	<p>opd_protocol_inter_trans</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Are the following disposition protocols available at this facility</i></p> <p>Acuity-based internal transfer protocols to OR or ICU</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 48</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
137	<p>opd_protocol_dispo</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Protocol for timely disposition from the OPD unit	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								

138	<p>opd_protocol_pt_comm</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Protocol for conveying information about discharge or disposition to the patient</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
139	<p>opd_protocol_handoff</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Hand-over protocols when transferring patients from one care provider to another</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
140	<p>opd_protocol_ext_trans</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Are the following outside transfer protocols available at this facility</i></p> <p>Condition-specific transfer or referral protocols (e.g. criteria for transfer of burn patients to burn center)</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 49</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
141	<p>opd_protocol_trans_comm</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Communication with receiving facility prior to transfer of patients with emergency conditions</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
142	<p>opd_protocol_infect_contr</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Are the following safety protocols available at this facility</i></p> <p>Infection prevention and control protocols</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 50</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
143	<p>opd_protocol_hcw_pep</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Protocol for post exposure prophylaxis for health care workers</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
144	<p>opd_protocol_security</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Security protocols to protect staff, patients, and infrastructure from violence</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
145	<p>opd_protocol_hazards</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Protocol for managing hazardous exposures (including designated decontamination area)</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
146	<p>opd_protocol_waste</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Containment and disposal of sharps and biomedical waste</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
147	<p>opd_protocol_inter_event</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Plan to ensure OPD staff and patient safety if an incident occurs within the OPD (including space, transport, communications)</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								

148	<p>opd_sw</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Outpatient Department (OPD) Ancillary Services Please rate the availability of each item 1 to 3 1 - Generally unavailable 2 - Some availability 3 - Adequate availability Note: If "don't know", enter -1 For rating < 3, mark all relevant barriers: Infrastructure Absent Equipment Broken Equipment Stock Out (Supplies) Training Personnel User Fees Opening Hours Other</i></p> <p>Social work services</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 52</p>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
1	Generally Unavailable																													
2	Some Availability																													
3	Adequate Availability																													
-1	Don't know																													
149	<p>opd_sw_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_sw] = '1' or [opd_sw] = '2'</p>	<p>Relevant barriers</p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_sw_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_sw_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_sw_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_sw_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_sw_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_sw_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_sw_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_sw_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_sw_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_sw_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_sw_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_sw_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_sw_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_sw_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_sw_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_sw_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_sw_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_sw_barrier__9	Other
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2	opd_sw_barrier__2	Absent equip																												
3	opd_sw_barrier__3	Broken equip																												
4	opd_sw_barrier__4	Stock out																												
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9	opd_sw_barrier__9	Other																												
150	<p>opd_sw_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_sw_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	<p>Please specify</p>	<p>text</p>																											
151	<p>opd_transport</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Patient transport services (within OPD)</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 53</p>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
1	Generally Unavailable																													
2	Some Availability																													
3	Adequate Availability																													
-1	Don't know																													
152	<p>opd_transport_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transport] = '1' or [opd_transport] = '2'</p>	<p>Relevant barriers</p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_transport_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_transport_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_transport_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_transport_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_transport_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_transport_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_transport_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_transport_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_transport_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_transport_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_transport_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_transport_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_transport_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_transport_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_transport_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_transport_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_transport_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_transport_barrier__9	Other
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2	opd_transport_barrier__2	Absent equip																												
3	opd_transport_barrier__3	Broken equip																												
4	opd_transport_barrier__4	Stock out																												
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8	opd_transport_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	opd_transport_barrier__9	Other																												
153	<p>opd_transport_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transport_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	<p>Please specify</p>	<p>text</p>																											
154	<p>opd_security</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Security</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 54</p>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2	Some Availability																													
3	Adequate Availability																													
-1	Don't know																													

155	<p>opd_security_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_security] = '1' or [opd_security] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_security_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_security_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_security_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_security_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_security_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_security_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_security_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_security_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_security_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_security_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_security_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_security_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_security_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_security_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_security_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_security_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_security_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_security_barrier__9	Other
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9	opd_security_barrier__9	Other																												
156	<p>opd_security_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_security_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
157	<p>opd_spirit</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Spiritual support	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 55</p>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
1	Generally Unavailable																													
2	Some Availability																													
3	Adequate Availability																													
-1	Don't know																													
158	<p>opd_spirit_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_spirit] = '1' or [opd_spirit] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_spirit_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_spirit_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_spirit_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_spirit_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_spirit_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_spirit_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_spirit_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_spirit_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_spirit_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_spirit_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_spirit_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_spirit_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_spirit_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_spirit_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_spirit_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_spirit_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_spirit_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_spirit_barrier__9	Other
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9	opd_spirit_barrier__9	Other																												
159	<p>opd_spirit_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_spirit_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
160	<p>opd_qi</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Outpatient Department (OPD) Quality Improvement</i></p> <p>Are there quality improvement projects in the OPD currently or at any time in the past year?[^]</p> <p><i>A quality improvement project is an effort to improve patient care based on an evaluation of the shortcomings of the care the ward provides and the changing knowledge base that informs best care</i></p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 60</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
161	<p>opd_registry</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Is there a systematic process for collecting patient data that links condition, management, and outcomes (e.g. trauma registry)?	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 61</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
162	<p>opd_m_and_m</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	Are there regular meetings convened to use clinical data for quality improvement (e.g. morbidity and mortality conferences, preventable death panels)?	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 62</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													

163	<p>opd_audits</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Is there tracking (e.g. clinical audit) to ensure that quality improvement actions (e.g. corrective action) are implemented after review meetings?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 63</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
164	<p>opd_clin_template</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Is there a clinical document template (e.g. standardized clinical chart)?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 64</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
165	<p>opd_ext_visitor</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Has there been a visit to this OPD by a supervisor from outside the facility within the last 6 months?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 65</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
166	<p>opd_ext_visitor_org</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ext_visitor] = '1'</p>	<p>What organization did the supervisor work for?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>NGO (e.g. PIH, CHAM)</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Ministry of Health</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 66</p>	1	NGO (e.g. PIH, CHAM)	2	Ministry of Health	3	Other	-1	Don't know
1	NGO (e.g. PIH, CHAM)										
2	Ministry of Health										
3	Other										
-1	Don't know										
167	<p>opd_ext_visitor_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ext_visitor_org] = '3'</p>	<p>Please specify</p>	<p>text</p>								
168	<p>opd_ext_visitor_doc</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ext_visitor] = '1'</p>	<p>Is there any documentation from the most recent external supervisory visit?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 67</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
169	<p>opd_ext_visitor_doc_detail</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ext_visitor_doc] = '1'</p>	<p>Does the document provide any feedback or comments on some aspect of emergency services?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 68</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
170	<p>opd_triagevital</p>	<p>Section Header: Outpatient Department (OPD) Signal Functions Please rate the availability of each item 1 to 3 1 - Generally unavailable 2 - Some availability 3 - Adequate availability Note: If "don't know", enter -1 For rating < 3, mark all relevant barriers: Infrastructure Absent Equipment Broken Equipment Stock Out (Supplies) Training Personnel User Fees Opening Hours Other</p> <p>Are vital signs measured in the triage area?</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know
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171	<p>opd_triagevital_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_triagevital] = '1' or [opd_triagevital] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_triagevital_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_triagevital_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_triagevital_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_triagevital_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_triagevital_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_triagevital_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_triagevital_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_triagevital_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_triagevital_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_triagevital_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_triagevital_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_triagevital_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_triagevital_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_triagevital_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_triagevital_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_triagevital_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_triagevital_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_triagevital_barrier__9	Other
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172	<p>opd_triagevital_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_triagevital_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
173	<p>opd_checkvital</p>	Are vital signs measured in the OPD?	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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174	<p>opd_checkvital_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_checkvital] = '1' or [opd_checkvital] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_checkvital_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_checkvital_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_checkvital_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_checkvital_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_checkvital_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_checkvital_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_checkvital_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_checkvital_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_checkvital_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_checkvital_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_checkvital_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_checkvital_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_checkvital_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_checkvital_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_checkvital_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_checkvital_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_checkvital_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_checkvital_barrier__9	Other
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175	<p>opd_checkvital_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_checkvital_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
176	<p>opd_manual</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Airway Interventions</i></p> <p>Use of manual maneuvers (e.g. jaw thrust, chin lift)</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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177	<p>opd_manual_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_manual] = '1' or [opd_manual] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_manual_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_manual_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_manual_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_manual_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_manual_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_manual_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_manual_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_manual_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_manual_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_manual_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_manual_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_manual_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_manual_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_manual_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_manual_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_manual_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_manual_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_manual_barrier__9	Other
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178	<p>opd_manual_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_manual_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

179	opd_suction	Use of suction	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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180	opd_suction_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_suction] = '1' or [opd_suction] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_suction_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_suction_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_suction_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_suction_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_suction_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_suction_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_suction_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_suction_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_suction_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_suction_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_suction_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_suction_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_suction_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_suction_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_suction_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_suction_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_suction_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_suction_barrier__9	Other
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181	opd_suction_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_suction_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
182	opd_oronas	Placement of oro- or naso-pharyngeal airway device	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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183	opd_oronas_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_oronas] = '1' or [opd_oronas] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_oronas_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_oronas_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_oronas_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_oronas_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_oronas_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_oronas_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_oronas_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_oronas_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_oronas_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_oronas_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_oronas_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_oronas_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_oronas_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_oronas_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_oronas_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_oronas_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_oronas_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_oronas_barrier__9	Other
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184	opd_oronas_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_oronas_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
185	opd_glottic	Placement of supraglottic device	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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186	<p>opd_glottic_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_glottic]= '1' or [opd_glottic] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_glottic_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_glottic_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_glottic_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_glottic_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_glottic_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_glottic_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_glottic_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_glottic_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_glottic_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_glottic_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_glottic_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_glottic_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_glottic_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_glottic_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_glottic_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_glottic_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_glottic_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_glottic_barrier__9	Other
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187	<p>opd_glottic_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_glottic_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
188	<p>opd_intubate</p>	Endotracheal intubation	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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189	<p>opd_intubate_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_intubate] = '1' or [opd_intubate] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_intubate_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_intubate_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_intubate_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_intubate_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_intubate_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_intubate_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_intubate_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_intubate_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_intubate_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_intubate_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_intubate_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_intubate_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_intubate_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_intubate_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_intubate_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_intubate_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_intubate_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_intubate_barrier__9	Other
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190	<p>opd_intubate_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_intubate_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
191	<p>opd_cric</p>	Creation of surgical airway	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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192	<p>opd_cric_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cric] = '1' or [opd_cric] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_cric_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_cric_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_cric_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_cric_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_cric_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_cric_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_cric_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_cric_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_cric_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_cric_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_cric_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_cric_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_cric_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_cric_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_cric_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_cric_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_cric_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_cric_barrier__9	Other
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194	opd_triagespo2	Section Header: <i>Breathing Interventions</i> Measurement of pulse oximetry at triage	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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195	opd_triagespo2_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_triagespo2] = '1' or [opd_triagespo2] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_triagespo2_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_triagespo2_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_triagespo2_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_triagespo2_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_triagespo2_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_triagespo2_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_triagespo2_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_triagespo2_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_triagespo2_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_triagespo2_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_triagespo2_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_triagespo2_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_triagespo2_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_triagespo2_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_triagespo2_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_triagespo2_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_triagespo2_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_triagespo2_barrier__9	Other
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196	opd_triagespo2_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_triagespo2_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
197	opd_checkspo2	Measurement of pulse oximetry in OPD	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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198	opd_checkspo2_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_checkspo2] = '1' or [opd_checkspo2] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_checkspo2_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_checkspo2_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_checkspo2_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_checkspo2_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_checkspo2_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_checkspo2_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_checkspo2_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_checkspo2_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_checkspo2_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_checkspo2_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_checkspo2_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_checkspo2_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_checkspo2_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_checkspo2_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_checkspo2_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_checkspo2_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_checkspo2_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_checkspo2_barrier__9	Other
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199	opd_checkspo2_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_checkspo2_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
200	opd_txasthma	Administration of critical therapies for reactive airway disease	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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201	<p>opd_txasthma_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_txasthma] = '1' or [opd_txasthma] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_txasthma_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_txasthma_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_txasthma_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_txasthma_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_txasthma_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_txasthma_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_txasthma_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_txasthma_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_txasthma_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_txasthma_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_txasthma_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_txasthma_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_txasthma_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_txasthma_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_txasthma_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_txasthma_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_txasthma_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_txasthma_barrier__9	Other
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202	<p>opd_txasthma_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_txasthma_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
203	<p>opd_giveo2</p>	Administration of oxygen	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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204	<p>opd_giveo2_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_giveo2] = '1' or [opd_giveo2] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_giveo2_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_giveo2_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_giveo2_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_giveo2_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_giveo2_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_giveo2_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_giveo2_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_giveo2_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_giveo2_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_giveo2_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_giveo2_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_giveo2_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_giveo2_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_giveo2_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_giveo2_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_giveo2_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_giveo2_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_giveo2_barrier__9	Other
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205	<p>opd_giveo2_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_giveo2_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
206	<p>opd_bagmask</p>	Bag-valve-mask ventilation	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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207	<p>opd_bagmask_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_bagmask] = '1' or [opd_bagmask] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_bagmask_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_bagmask_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_bagmask_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_bagmask_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_bagmask_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_bagmask_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_bagmask_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_bagmask_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_bagmask_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_bagmask_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_bagmask_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_bagmask_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_bagmask_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_bagmask_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_bagmask_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_bagmask_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_bagmask_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_bagmask_barrier__9	Other
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208	<p>opd_bagmask_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_bagmask_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

209	opd_ptx	Perform needle decompression of tension pneumothorax	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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210	opd_ptx_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ptx] = '1' or [opd_ptx] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_ptx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_ptx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_ptx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_ptx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_ptx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_ptx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_ptx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_ptx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_ptx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_ptx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_ptx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_ptx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_ptx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_ptx_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_ptx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_ptx_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_ptx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_ptx_barrier__9	Other
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211	opd_ptx_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ptx_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
212	opd_chesttube	Placement of chest tube	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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213	opd_chesttube_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_chesttube] = '1' or [opd_chesttube] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_chesttube_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_chesttube_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_chesttube_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_chesttube_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_chesttube_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_chesttube_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_chesttube_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_chesttube_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_chesttube_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_chesttube_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_chesttube_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_chesttube_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_chesttube_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_chesttube_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_chesttube_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_chesttube_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_chesttube_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_chesttube_barrier__9	Other
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214	opd_chesttube_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_chesttube_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
215	opd_nippv	Non-invasive mechanical ventilation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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216	<p>opd_nippv_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_nippv] = '1' or [opd_nippv] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_nippv_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_nippv_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_nippv_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_nippv_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_nippv_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_nippv_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_nippv_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_nippv_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_nippv_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_nippv_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_nippv_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_nippv_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_nippv_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_nippv_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_nippv_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_nippv_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_nippv_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_nippv_barrier__9	Other
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217	<p>opd_nippv_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_nippv_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
218	<p>opd_vent</p>	Invasive mechanical ventilation	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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219	<p>opd_vent_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_vent] = '1' or [opd_vent] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_vent_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_vent_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_vent_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_vent_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_vent_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_vent_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_vent_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_vent_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_vent_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_vent_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_vent_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_vent_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_vent_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_vent_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_vent_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_vent_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_vent_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_vent_barrier__9	Other
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9	opd_vent_barrier__9	Other																												
220	<p>opd_vent_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_vent_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
221	<p>opd_number_vented</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_vent] = '2' or [opd_vent] = '3'</p>	<p>How many patients can receive mechanical ventilation via a ventilator and endotracheal tube in the OPD at any one time? <i>enter 0 if none, -1 if unknown</i></p>	<p>text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000)</p> <p>Question number: 86</p>																											
222	<p>opd_vent_policy</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_vent] = '2' or [opd_vent] = '3'</p>	Is there a written policy for who can or cannot be intubated and/or placed on mechanical ventilation?	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 87</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
223	<p>opd_extubate_policy</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_vent] = '2' or [opd_vent] = '3'</p>	Is there a written policy for if and when intubation and/or mechanical ventilation can be withdrawn?	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 88</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													

224	opd_ors	Section Header: <i>Volume Resuscitation Interventions</i> Administer oral rehydration	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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225	opd_ors_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ors] = '1' or [opd_ors] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_ors_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_ors_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_ors_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_ors_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_ors_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_ors_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_ors_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_ors_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_ors_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_ors_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_ors_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_ors_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_ors_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_ors_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_ors_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_ors_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_ors_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_ors_barrier__9	Other
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226	opd_ors_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ors_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
227	opd_adj_ivf	Adjust fluid resuscitation for malnutrition or severe anemia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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228	opd_adj_ivf_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_adj_ivf] = '1' or [opd_adj_ivf] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_adj_ivf_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_adj_ivf_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_adj_ivf_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_adj_ivf_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_adj_ivf_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_adj_ivf_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_adj_ivf_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_adj_ivf_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_adj_ivf_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_adj_ivf_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_adj_ivf_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_adj_ivf_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_adj_ivf_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_adj_ivf_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_adj_ivf_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_adj_ivf_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_adj_ivf_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_adj_ivf_barrier__9	Other
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229	opd_adj_ivf_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_adj_ivf_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
230	opd_piv	Place peripheral IV access	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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231	<p>opd_piv_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_piv] = '1' or [opd_piv] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_piv_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_piv_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_piv_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_piv_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_piv_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_piv_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_piv_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_piv_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_piv_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_piv_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_piv_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_piv_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_piv_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_piv_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_piv_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_piv_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_piv_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_piv_barrier__9	Other
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232	<p>opd_piv_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_piv_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
233	<p>opd_io</p>	Establish intraosseous access	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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234	<p>opd_io_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_io] = '1' or [opd_io] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_io_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_io_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_io_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_io_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_io_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_io_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_io_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_io_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_io_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_io_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_io_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_io_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_io_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_io_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_io_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_io_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_io_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_io_barrier__9	Other
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235	<p>opd_io_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_io_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
236	<p>opd_cutdown</p>	Perform venous cutdown	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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237	<p>opd_cutdown_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cutdown] = '1' or [opd_c utdown] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_cutdown_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_cutdown_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_cutdown_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_cutdown_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_cutdown_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_cutdown_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_cutdown_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_cutdown_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_cutdown_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_cutdown_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_cutdown_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_cutdown_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_cutdown_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_cutdown_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_cutdown_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_cutdown_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_cutdown_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_cutdown_barrier__9	Other
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238	<p>opd_cutdown_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cutdown_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

239	opd_cvc	Establish central venous access	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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240	opd_cvc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cvc]='1' or [opd_cvc] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_cvc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_cvc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_cvc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_cvc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_cvc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_cvc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_cvc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_cvc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_cvc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_cvc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_cvc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_cvc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_cvc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_cvc_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_cvc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_cvc_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_cvc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_cvc_barrier__9	Other
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241	opd_cvc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cvc_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
242	opd_give_ivf	Administration of IV fluids	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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243	opd_give_ivf_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_give_ivf] = '1' or [opd_give_ivf] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_give_ivf_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_give_ivf_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_give_ivf_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_give_ivf_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_give_ivf_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_give_ivf_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_give_ivf_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_give_ivf_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_give_ivf_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_give_ivf_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_give_ivf_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_give_ivf_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_give_ivf_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_give_ivf_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_give_ivf_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_give_ivf_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_give_ivf_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_give_ivf_barrier__9	Other
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244	opd_give_ivf_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_give_ivf_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
245	opd_foley	Place urinary catheter	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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246	<p>opd_foley_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_foley] = '1' or [opd_foley] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_foley_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_foley_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_foley_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_foley_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_foley_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_foley_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_foley_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_foley_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_foley_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_foley_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_foley_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_foley_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_foley_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_foley_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_foley_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_foley_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_foley_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_foley_barrier__9	Other
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247	<p>opd_foley_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_foley_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
248	<p>opd_exctrl_bleed</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Control of Bleeding</i></p> <p>External control of haemorrhage</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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249	<p>opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_exctrl_bleed] = '1' or [opd_exctrl_bleed] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier__9	Other
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250	<p>opd_exctrl_bleed_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_exctrl_bleed_barrier(9)] = '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
251	<p>opd_pack</p>	Perform packing and/or suture control	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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252	<p>opd_pack_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_pack] = '1' or [opd_pack] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_pack_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_pack_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_pack_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_pack_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_pack_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_pack_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_pack_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_pack_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_pack_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_pack_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_pack_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_pack_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_pack_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_pack_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_pack_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_pack_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_pack_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_pack_barrier__9	Other
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253	<p>opd_pack_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_pack_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

254	opd_tourniquet	Apply arterial tourniquet	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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255	opd_tourniquet_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_tourniquet] = '1' or [opd_tourniquet] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_tourniquet_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_tourniquet_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_tourniquet_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_tourniquet_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_tourniquet_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_tourniquet_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_tourniquet_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_tourniquet_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_tourniquet_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_tourniquet_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_tourniquet_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_tourniquet_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_tourniquet_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_tourniquet_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_tourniquet_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_tourniquet_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_tourniquet_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_tourniquet_barrier__9	Other
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256	opd_tourniquet_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_tourniquet_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
257	opd_pelvicbind	Apply pelvic binding or sheeting	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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258	opd_pelvicbind_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_pelvicbind] = '1' or [opd_pelvicbind] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_pelvicbind_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_pelvicbind_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_pelvicbind_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_pelvicbind_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_pelvicbind_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_pelvicbind_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_pelvicbind_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_pelvicbind_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_pelvicbind_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_pelvicbind_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_pelvicbind_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_pelvicbind_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_pelvicbind_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_pelvicbind_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_pelvicbind_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_pelvicbind_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_pelvicbind_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_pelvicbind_barrier__9	Other
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259	opd_pelvicbind_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_pelvicbind_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
260	opd_transfuse	Ability to perform safe transfusion (including protocols for appropriate ratios for massive transfusion)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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261	<p>opd_transfuse_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfuse] = '1' or [opd_transfuse] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_transfuse_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_transfuse_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_transfuse_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_transfuse_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_transfuse_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_transfuse_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_transfuse_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_transfuse_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_transfuse_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_transfuse_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_transfuse_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_transfuse_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_transfuse_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_transfuse_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_transfuse_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_transfuse_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_transfuse_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_transfuse_barrier__9	Other
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262	<p>opd_transfuse_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_transfuse_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
263	<p>opd_pocus</p>	Perform and interpret point of care ultrasound	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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264	<p>opd_pocus_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_pocus] = '1' or [opd_pocus] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_pocus_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_pocus_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_pocus_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_pocus_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_pocus_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_pocus_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_pocus_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_pocus_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_pocus_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_pocus_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_pocus_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_pocus_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_pocus_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_pocus_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_pocus_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_pocus_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_pocus_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_pocus_barrier__9	Other
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265	<p>opd_pocus_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_pocus_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
266	<p>opd_ecg</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Cardiac Interventions</i></p> <p>Perform and interpret ECG</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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267	<p>opd_ecg_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ecg] = '1' or [opd_ecg] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_ecg_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_ecg_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_ecg_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_ecg_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_ecg_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_ecg_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_ecg_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_ecg_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_ecg_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_ecg_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_ecg_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_ecg_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_ecg_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_ecg_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_ecg_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_ecg_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_ecg_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_ecg_barrier__9	Other
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268	<p>opd_ecg_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ecg_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

269	opd_asa	Administer aspirin for ischemia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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270	opd_asa_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_asa] = '1' or [opd_asa] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_asa_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_asa_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_asa_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_asa_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_asa_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_asa_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_asa_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_asa_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_asa_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_asa_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_asa_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_asa_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_asa_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_asa_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_asa_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_asa_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_asa_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_asa_barrier__9	Other
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271	opd_asa_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_asa_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
272	opd_defib	Perform external defibrillation and/or cardioversion	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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273	opd_defib_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_defib] = '1' or [opd_defib] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_defib_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_defib_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_defib_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_defib_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_defib_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_defib_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_defib_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_defib_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_defib_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_defib_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_defib_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_defib_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_defib_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_defib_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_defib_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_defib_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_defib_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_defib_barrier__9	Other
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274	opd_defib_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_defib_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
275	opd_epi	Administration of adrenaline	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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276	<p>opd_epi_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_epi] = '1' or [opd_epi] = '2'</p>	<p>Relevant barriers</p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_epi_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_epi_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_epi_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_epi_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_epi_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_epi_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_epi_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_epi_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_epi_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_epi_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_epi_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_epi_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_epi_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_epi_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_epi_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_epi_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_epi_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_epi_barrier__9	Other
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277	<p>opd_epi_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_epi_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	<p>Please specify</p>	<p>text</p>																											
278	<p>opd_inotrope</p>	<p>Administer inotropes</p> <p><i>Examples of inotropes: digoxin, milrinone, dobutamine</i></p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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279	<p>opd_inotrope_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_inotrope] = '1' or [opd_inotrope] = '2'</p>	<p>Relevant barriers</p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_inotrope_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_inotrope_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_inotrope_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_inotrope_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_inotrope_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_inotrope_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_inotrope_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_inotrope_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_inotrope_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_inotrope_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_inotrope_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_inotrope_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_inotrope_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_inotrope_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_inotrope_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_inotrope_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_inotrope_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_inotrope_barrier__9	Other
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280	<p>opd_inotrope_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_inotrope_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	<p>Please specify</p>	<p>text</p>																											
281	<p>opd_rhythm</p>	<p>Administer anti-arrythmics</p> <p><i>Anti-arrythmics include amiodarone, lidocaine, flecainide, procainamide</i></p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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282	<p>opd_rhythm_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_rhythm] = '1' or [opd_rhythm] = '2'</p>	<p>Relevant barriers</p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_rhythm_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_rhythm_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_rhythm_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_rhythm_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_rhythm_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_rhythm_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_rhythm_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_rhythm_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_rhythm_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_rhythm_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_rhythm_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_rhythm_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_rhythm_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_rhythm_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_rhythm_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_rhythm_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_rhythm_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_rhythm_barrier__9	Other
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283	<p>opd_rhythm_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_rhythm_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	<p>Please specify</p>	<p>text</p>																											

284	opd_lytics	Administration of thrombolytics <i>Thrombolytics include alteplase, urokinase, streptokinase, tenecteplase. They DO NOT include enoxaparin, heparin, warfarin</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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285	opd_lytics_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_lytics] = '1' or [opd_lytics] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_lytics_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_lytics_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_lytics_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_lytics_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_lytics_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_lytics_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_lytics_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_lytics_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_lytics_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_lytics_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_lytics_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_lytics_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_lytics_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_lytics_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_lytics_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_lytics_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_lytics_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_lytics_barrier__9	Other
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286	opd_lytics_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_lytics_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
287	opd_tamponade	Perform pericardiocentesis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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288	opd_tamponade_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_tamponade] = '1' or [opd_tamponade] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_tamponade_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_tamponade_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_tamponade_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_tamponade_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_tamponade_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_tamponade_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_tamponade_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_tamponade_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_tamponade_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_tamponade_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_tamponade_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_tamponade_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_tamponade_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_tamponade_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_tamponade_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_tamponade_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_tamponade_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_tamponade_barrier__9	Other
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289	opd_tamponade_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_tamponade_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
290	opd_prcttams	Section Header: <i>Unconscious Patient</i> Protect unconscious patient from secondary injury	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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291	<p>opd_prctams_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_prctams] = '1' or [opd_prctams] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_prctams_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_prctams_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_prctams_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_prctams_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_prctams_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_prctams_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_prctams_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_prctams_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_prctams_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_prctams_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_prctams_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_prctams_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_prctams_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_prctams_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_prctams_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_prctams_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_prctams_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_prctams_barrier__9	Other
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293	<p>opd_hypoglyc</p>	Check and/or administer glucose	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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294	<p>opd_hypoglyc_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_hypoglyc] = '1' or [opd_hypoglyc] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_hypoglyc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_hypoglyc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_hypoglyc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_hypoglyc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_hypoglyc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_hypoglyc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_hypoglyc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_hypoglyc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_hypoglyc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_hypoglyc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_hypoglyc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_hypoglyc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_hypoglyc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_hypoglyc_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_hypoglyc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_hypoglyc_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_hypoglyc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_hypoglyc_barrier__9	Other
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295	<p>opd_hypoglyc_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_hypoglyc_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
296	<p>opd_insulin</p>	Administer insulin for hyperglycemia	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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297	<p>opd_insulin_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_insulin]= '1' or [opd_insulin] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_insulin_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_insulin_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_insulin_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_insulin_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_insulin_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_insulin_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_insulin_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_insulin_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_insulin_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_insulin_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_insulin_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_insulin_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_insulin_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_insulin_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_insulin_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_insulin_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_insulin_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_insulin_barrier__9	Other
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298	<p>opd_insulin_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_insulin_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

299	opd_lp	Perform lumbar puncture	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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300	opd_lp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_lp] = '1' or [opd_lp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_lp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_lp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_lp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_lp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_lp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_lp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_lp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_lp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_lp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_lp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_lp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_lp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_lp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_lp_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_lp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_lp_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_lp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_lp_barrier__9	Other
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301	opd_lp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_lp_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
302	opd_benzo	Section Header: <i>Seizure</i> Administer benzodiazepine	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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303	opd_benzo_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_benzo] = '1' or [opd_benzo] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_benzo_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_benzo_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_benzo_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_benzo_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_benzo_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_benzo_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_benzo_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_benzo_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_benzo_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_benzo_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_benzo_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_benzo_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_benzo_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_benzo_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_benzo_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_benzo_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_benzo_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_benzo_barrier__9	Other
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304	opd_benzo_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_benzo_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
305	opd_eclamp	Administer IV magnesium for pregnant patient	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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306	<p>opd_ecclamp_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ecclamp] = '1' or [opd_e cclamp] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_ecclamp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_ecclamp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_ecclamp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_ecclamp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_ecclamp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_ecclamp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_ecclamp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_ecclamp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_ecclamp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_ecclamp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_ecclamp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_ecclamp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_ecclamp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_ecclamp_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_ecclamp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_ecclamp_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_ecclamp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_ecclamp_barrier__9	Other
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307	<p>opd_ecclamp_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ecclamp_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
308	<p>opd_antidote</p>	Administer locally appropriate antidote	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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309	<p>opd_antidote_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_antidote] = '1' or [opd_a ntidote] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_antidote_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_antidote_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_antidote_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_antidote_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_antidote_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_antidote_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_antidote_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_antidote_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_antidote_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_antidote_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_antidote_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_antidote_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_antidote_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_antidote_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_antidote_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_antidote_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_antidote_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_antidote_barrier__9	Other
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310	<p>opd_antidote_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_antidote_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
311	<p>opd_mse</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Other Neurologic Interventions</i></p> <p>Perform mental status exam</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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312	<p>opd_mse_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_mse] = '1' or [opd_mse] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_mse_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_mse_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_mse_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_mse_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_mse_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_mse_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_mse_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_mse_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_mse_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_mse_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_mse_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_mse_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_mse_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_mse_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_mse_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_mse_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_mse_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_mse_barrier__9	Other
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313	<p>opd_mse_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_mse_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

314	opd_thermia	Management of extreme temperatures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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315	opd_thermia_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_thermia] = '1' or [opd_thermia] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_thermia_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_thermia_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_thermia_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_thermia_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_thermia_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_thermia_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_thermia_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_thermia_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_thermia_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_thermia_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_thermia_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_thermia_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_thermia_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_thermia_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_thermia_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_thermia_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_thermia_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_thermia_barrier__9	Other
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316	opd_thermia_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_thermia_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
317	opd_agitation	Administer appropriate therapeutics for agitation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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318	opd_agitation_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_agitation] = '1' or [opd_agitation] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_agitation_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_agitation_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_agitation_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_agitation_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_agitation_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_agitation_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_agitation_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_agitation_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_agitation_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_agitation_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_agitation_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_agitation_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_agitation_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_agitation_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_agitation_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_agitation_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_agitation_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_agitation_barrier__9	Other
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319	opd_agitation_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_agitation_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
320	opd_restraint	Ability to provide physical restraints	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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321	<p>opd_restraint_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_restraint] = '1' or [opd_restraint] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_restraint_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_restraint_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_restraint_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_restraint_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_restraint_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_restraint_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_restraint_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_restraint_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_restraint_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_restraint_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_restraint_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_restraint_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_restraint_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_restraint_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_restraint_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_restraint_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_restraint_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_restraint_barrier__9	Other
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322	<p>opd_restraint_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_restraint_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
323	<p>opd_ivcs</p>	Perform procedural sedation	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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324	<p>opd_ivcs_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ivcs] = '1' or [opd_ivcs] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_ivcs_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_ivcs_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_ivcs_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_ivcs_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_ivcs_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_ivcs_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_ivcs_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_ivcs_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_ivcs_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_ivcs_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_ivcs_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_ivcs_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_ivcs_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_ivcs_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_ivcs_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_ivcs_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_ivcs_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_ivcs_barrier__9	Other
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325	<p>opd_ivcs_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ivcs_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
326	<p>opd_giveabx</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Sepsis Interventions</i></p> <p>Administration of IV or IM antibiotics</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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327	<p>opd_giveabx_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_giveabx] = '1' or [opd_giveabx] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_giveabx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_giveabx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_giveabx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_giveabx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_giveabx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_giveabx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_giveabx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_giveabx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_giveabx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_giveabx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_giveabx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_giveabx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_giveabx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_giveabx_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_giveabx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_giveabx_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_giveabx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_giveabx_barrier__9	Other
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328	<p>opd_giveabx_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_giveabx_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

329	opd_pressor	Administration of IV vasopressors <i>Vasopressors include: dopamine, epinephrine, norepinephrine, vasopressin, phenylephrine</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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330	opd_pressor_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_pressor] = '1' or [opd_pressor] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_pressor_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_pressor_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_pressor_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_pressor_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_pressor_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_pressor_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_pressor_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_pressor_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_pressor_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_pressor_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_pressor_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_pressor_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_pressor_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_pressor_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_pressor_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_pressor_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_pressor_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_pressor_barrier__9	Other
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331	opd_pressor_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_pressor_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
332	opd_para	Perform diagnostic paracentesis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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333	opd_para_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_para] = '1' or [opd_para] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_para_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_para_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_para_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_para_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_para_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_para_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_para_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_para_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_para_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_para_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_para_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_para_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_para_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_para_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_para_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_para_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_para_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_para_barrier__9	Other
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334	opd_para_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_para_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
335	opd_sourcctrl	Bedside minor surgical techniques for source control (e.g. abscess, empyema)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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336	<p>opd_sourcctrl_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_sourcctrl] = '1' or [opd_sourcctrl] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_sourcctrl_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_sourcctrl_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_sourcctrl_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_sourcctrl_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_sourcctrl_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_sourcctrl_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_sourcctrl_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_sourcctrl_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_sourcctrl_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_sourcctrl_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_sourcctrl_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_sourcctrl_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_sourcctrl_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_sourcctrl_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_sourcctrl_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_sourcctrl_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_sourcctrl_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_sourcctrl_barrier__9	Other
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337	<p>opd_sourcctrl_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_sourcctrl_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
338	<p>opd_woundcare</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Trauma Interventions</i></p> <p>Perform initial appropriate wound care</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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339	<p>opd_woundcare_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_woundcare] = '1' or [opd_woundcare] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_woundcare_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_woundcare_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_woundcare_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_woundcare_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_woundcare_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_woundcare_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_woundcare_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_woundcare_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_woundcare_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_woundcare_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_woundcare_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_woundcare_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_woundcare_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_woundcare_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_woundcare_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_woundcare_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_woundcare_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_woundcare_barrier__9	Other
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340	<p>opd_woundcare_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_woundcare_barrier(9)] = '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
341	<p>opd_tetanus</p>	Administer tetanus vaccination or IVIG as appropriate	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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342	<p>opd_tetanus_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_tetanus] = '1' or [opd_tetanus] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_tetanus_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_tetanus_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_tetanus_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_tetanus_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_tetanus_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_tetanus_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_tetanus_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_tetanus_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_tetanus_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_tetanus_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_tetanus_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_tetanus_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_tetanus_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_tetanus_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_tetanus_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_tetanus_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_tetanus_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_tetanus_barrier__9	Other
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9	opd_tetanus_barrier__9	Other																												
343	<p>opd_tetanus_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_tetanus_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

344	opd_rabies	Administer rabies vaccine or IVIG as appropriate	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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345	opd_rabies_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_rabies] = '1' or [opd_rabies] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_rabies_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_rabies_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_rabies_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_rabies_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_rabies_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_rabies_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_rabies_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_rabies_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_rabies_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_rabies_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_rabies_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_rabies_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_rabies_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_rabies_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_rabies_barrier__6	Prsnl.	7	opd_rabies_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_rabies_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_rabies_barrier__9	Other
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346	opd_rabies_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_rabies_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
347	opd_cspine	Immobilize the cervical spine	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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348	opd_cspine_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cspine] = '1' or [opd_cspine] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_cspine_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_cspine_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_cspine_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_cspine_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_cspine_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_cspine_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_cspine_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_cspine_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_cspine_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_cspine_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_cspine_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_cspine_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_cspine_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_cspine_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_cspine_barrier__6	Prsnl.	7	opd_cspine_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_cspine_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_cspine_barrier__9	Other
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349	opd_cspine_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cspine_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
350	opd_immob_frac	Immobilize fractures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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351	<p>opd_immob_frac_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_immob_frac] = '1' or [opd_immob_frac] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_immob_frac_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_immob_frac_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_immob_frac_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_immob_frac_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_immob_frac_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_immob_frac_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_immob_frac_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_immob_frac_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_immob_frac_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_immob_frac_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_immob_frac_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_immob_frac_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_immob_frac_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_immob_frac_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_immob_frac_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_immob_frac_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_immob_frac_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_immob_frac_barrier__9	Other
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352	<p>opd_immob_frac_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_immob_frac_barrier(9)] = '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
353	<p>opd_reduce_frac</p>	Perform closed reduction of fracture or dislocation	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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354	<p>opd_reduce_frac_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_reduce_frac] = '1' or [opd_reduce_frac] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_reduce_frac_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_reduce_frac_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_reduce_frac_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_reduce_frac_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_reduce_frac_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_reduce_frac_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_reduce_frac_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_reduce_frac_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_reduce_frac_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_reduce_frac_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_reduce_frac_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_reduce_frac_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_reduce_frac_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_reduce_frac_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_reduce_frac_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_reduce_frac_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_reduce_frac_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_reduce_frac_barrier__9	Other
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355	<p>opd_reduce_frac_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_reduce_frac_barrier(9)] = '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
356	<p>opd_abx4frac</p>	Administer antibiotics for open fracture	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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357	<p>opd_abx4frac_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_abx4frac] = '1' or [opd_abx4frac] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_abx4frac_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_abx4frac_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_abx4frac_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_abx4frac_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_abx4frac_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_abx4frac_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_abx4frac_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_abx4frac_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_abx4frac_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_abx4frac_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_abx4frac_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_abx4frac_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_abx4frac_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_abx4frac_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_abx4frac_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_abx4frac_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_abx4frac_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_abx4frac_barrier__9	Other
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358	<p>opd_abx4frac_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_abx4frac_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
359	opd_compartsynd	Perform fasciotomy or escharotomy for compartment syndrome	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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360	<p>opd_compartsynd_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_compartsynd]= '1' or [opd_compartsynd] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_compartsynd_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_compartsynd_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_compartsynd_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_compartsynd_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_compartsynd_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_compartsynd_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_compartsynd_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_compartsynd_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_compartsynd_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_compartsynd_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_compartsynd_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_compartsynd_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_compartsynd_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_compartsynd_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_compartsynd_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_compartsynd_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_compartsynd_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_compartsynd_barrier__9	Other
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361	<p>opd_compartsynd_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_compartsynd_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
362	opd_threeway	Apply three-way dressing for sucking chest wound	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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363	<p>opd_threeway_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_threeway] = '1' or [opd_threeway] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_threeway_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_threeway_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_threeway_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_threeway_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_threeway_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_threeway_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_threeway_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_threeway_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_threeway_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_threeway_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_threeway_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_threeway_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_threeway_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_threeway_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_threeway_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_threeway_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_threeway_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_threeway_barrier__9	Other
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364	<p>opd_threeway_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_threeway_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
365	opd_opioids	Administer opiate analgesia	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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366	<p>opd_opioids_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_opioids] = '1' or [opd_opioids] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_opioids_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_opioids_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_opioids_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_opioids_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_opioids_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_opioids_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_opioids_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_opioids_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_opioids_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_opioids_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_opioids_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_opioids_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_opioids_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_opioids_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_opioids_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_opioids_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_opioids_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_opioids_barrier__9	Other
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9	opd_opioids_barrier__9	Other																												
367	<p>opd_opioids_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_opioids_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
368	<p>opd_avd</p>	<p>Perform assisted vaginal delivery</p> <p><i>Assisted vaginal delivery is a vaginal delivery performed with the help of a forceps or vacuum device</i></p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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369	<p>opd_avd_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_avd] = '1' or [opd_avd] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_avd_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_avd_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_avd_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_avd_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_avd_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_avd_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_avd_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_avd_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_avd_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_avd_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_avd_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_avd_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_avd_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_avd_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_avd_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_avd_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_avd_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_avd_barrier__9	Other
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370	<p>opd_avd_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_avd_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
371	<p>opd_oxytocin</p>	Administer uterotonic drug (e.g. oxytocin)	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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372	<p>opd_oxytocin_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_oxytocin] = '1' or [opd_oxytocin] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_oxytocin_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_oxytocin_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_oxytocin_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_oxytocin_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_oxytocin_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_oxytocin_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_oxytocin_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_oxytocin_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_oxytocin_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_oxytocin_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_oxytocin_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_oxytocin_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_oxytocin_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_oxytocin_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_oxytocin_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_oxytocin_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_oxytocin_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_oxytocin_barrier__9	Other
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373	<p>opd_oxytocin_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_oxytocin_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

374	opd_neonate	Perform neonatal resuscitation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Generally Unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Some Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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375	opd_neonate_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_neonate] = '1' or [opd_neonate] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>opd_neonate_barrier__1</td> <td>Infrastr.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>opd_neonate_barrier__2</td> <td>Absent equip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>opd_neonate_barrier__3</td> <td>Broken equip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>opd_neonate_barrier__4</td> <td>Stock out</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>opd_neonate_barrier__5</td> <td>Training</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>opd_neonate_barrier__6</td> <td>Prsnnl.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>opd_neonate_barrier__7</td> <td>User fees</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>opd_neonate_barrier__8</td> <td>Opening hours</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>opd_neonate_barrier__9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	opd_neonate_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_neonate_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_neonate_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_neonate_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_neonate_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_neonate_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_neonate_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_neonate_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_neonate_barrier__9	Other
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376	opd_neonate_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_neonate_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
377	opd_cc_diff	Section Header: <i>Outpatient Department (OPD)F. Critical Care</i> Compared to other patients in the OPD, what is different about the way you take care of critically ill patients? <i>Read options, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>opd_cc_diff__1</td> <td>Nurse to patient ratios</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>opd_cc_diff__2</td> <td>Type of nursing care</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>opd_cc_diff__3</td> <td>Training level of provders</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>opd_cc_diff__4</td> <td>Monitoring equipment</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>opd_cc_diff__5</td> <td>Frequency of vital signs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>opd_cc_diff__6</td> <td>Capabilities for advanced interventions</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>opd_cc_diff__7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>opd_cc_diff__0</td> <td>No difference</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>opd_cc_diff__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 160</p>	1	opd_cc_diff__1	Nurse to patient ratios	2	opd_cc_diff__2	Type of nursing care	3	opd_cc_diff__3	Training level of provders	4	opd_cc_diff__4	Monitoring equipment	5	opd_cc_diff__5	Frequency of vital signs	6	opd_cc_diff__6	Capabilities for advanced interventions	7	opd_cc_diff__7	Other	0	opd_cc_diff__0	No difference	-1	opd_cc_diff__1	Don't know
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0	opd_cc_diff__0	No difference																												
-1	opd_cc_diff__1	Don't know																												
378	opd_cc_diff_rn_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cc_diff(2)] = '1'	Please specify how type of nursing care is different for critically ill patients	text																											
379	opd_cc_diff_train_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cc_diff(3)] = '1'	Please specify how training level of providers is different for critically ill patients	text																											
380	opd_cc_diff_equip_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cc_diff(4)] = '1'	Please specify how monitoring equipment is different for critically ill patients	text																											
381	opd_cc_diff_adv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cc_diff(6)] = '1'	Please specify how capabilities for advanced interventions is different for critically ill patients	text																											
382	opd_cc_diff_other_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cc_diff(7)] = '1'	Please specify what other things are different about the way you take care of critically ill patients	text																											
383	opd_cc_admit_policy Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_cc_bed] = '1'	Is there a formal written policy outlining the criteria for placing a patient in the bed(s) reserved for critically ill patients in the OPD?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 163</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													

384	<p>opd_cc_admit_role</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_cc_bed] = '1'</p>	<p>Who makes the decision to place a patient there?</p> <p><i>do not read, select all that apply</i></p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>opd_cc_admit_role__1</td> <td>Doctor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>opd_cc_admit_role__2</td> <td>Nurse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>opd_cc_admit_role__3</td> <td>Clinical officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>opd_cc_admit_role__4</td> <td>Medical assistant</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>opd_cc_admit_role__5</td> <td>Administrator</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>opd_cc_admit_role__6</td> <td>Patient or patient family</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>opd_cc_admit_role__7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>opd_cc_admit_role__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 164</p>	1	opd_cc_admit_role__1	Doctor	2	opd_cc_admit_role__2	Nurse	3	opd_cc_admit_role__3	Clinical officer	4	opd_cc_admit_role__4	Medical assistant	5	opd_cc_admit_role__5	Administrator	6	opd_cc_admit_role__6	Patient or patient family	7	opd_cc_admit_role__7	Other	-1	opd_cc_admit_role__1	Don't know
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385	<p>opd_cc_admit_role_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cc_admit_role(7)] = '1'</p>	Please specify	text																								
386	<p>opd_vitals_how</p>	<p>How are vital signs checked on patients in the OPD?</p> <p><i>read choices, select all that apply</i></p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>opd_vitals_how__1</td> <td>Manual BP cuff</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>opd_vitals_how__2</td> <td>Automatic BP cuff</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>opd_vitals_how__3</td> <td>Intermittent pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>opd_vitals_how__4</td> <td>Continuous pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>opd_vitals_how__5</td> <td>Continuous cardiac monitor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>opd_vitals_how__6</td> <td>Invasive monitoring (e.g. arterial line)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>opd_vitals_how__7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>opd_vitals_how__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 165</p>	1	opd_vitals_how__1	Manual BP cuff	2	opd_vitals_how__2	Automatic BP cuff	3	opd_vitals_how__3	Intermittent pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)	4	opd_vitals_how__4	Continuous pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)	5	opd_vitals_how__5	Continuous cardiac monitor	6	opd_vitals_how__6	Invasive monitoring (e.g. arterial line)	7	opd_vitals_how__7	Other	-1	opd_vitals_how__1	Don't know
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387	<p>opd_vitals_how_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_vitals_how(7)] = '1'</p>	Please specify	text																								
388	<p>opd_vitals_recheck</p>	Are vital signs rechecked on stable patients in the OPD?	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 166</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																		
0	No																										
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389	<p>opd_vitals_recheck_freq</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_vitals_recheck] = '1'</p>	<p>How often (in hours)?</p> <p><i>enter -1 if unknown, -2 if not checked at regular intervals</i></p>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000)																								
390	<p>opd_ccvitals_recheck</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_cc_diff(5)] = '1'</p>	Are vital signs rechecked on critically ill patients in the OPD?	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 167</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																		
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391	<p>opd_ccvitals_recheck_freq</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ccvitals_recheck] = '1'</p>	<p>How often (in hours)?</p> <p><i>enter -1 if unknown, -2 if not checked at regular intervals</i></p>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000)																								

392	opd_cc_reassessed	Are critically ill patients in the OPD reassessed at least twice a day by a clinician who can change the treatment plan if needed?	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 168</p>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
393	opd_seen_dka	<p>Section Header: <i>Have you seen > 5 patients over the past 3 months in the OPD with each of the following?</i></p> <p>Diabetic ketoacidosis</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 169</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
394	opd_seen_seizures	Seizures	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
395	opd_seen_poisoning	Poisoning	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
396	opd_seen_chf	Severe heart failure	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
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1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
397	opd_seen_arf	Severe renal failure	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
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1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
398	opd_seen_respiratory	Respiratory distress or respiratory failure	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
399	opd_seen_shock	Low blood pressure or shock	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
400	opd_seen_ams	Coma (altered mental status or decreased level of consciousness)	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
401	opd_seen_stroke	Suspected stroke	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														

402	opd_seen_head_trauma	Severe head trauma	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
403	opd_seen_open_frac	Open fracture	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
404	opd_seen_closed_frac	Closed long bone fracture (e.g. femur)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
405	opd_seen_other_trauma	Other trauma	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
406	opd_seen_obstructed_labor	Obstructed labor	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
407	opd_seen_pph	Post-partum hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
408	opd_learn_dka	Section Header: <i>Have you received training in the past year on the following conditions:</i> Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 170
409	opd_learn_seizures	Seizures	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
410	opd_learn_poisoning	Poisoning	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
411	opd_learn_chf	Severe heart failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
412	opd_learn_arf	Severe renal failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know

413	opd_learn_respiratory	Respiratory distress or respiratory failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
414	opd_learn_shock	Low blood pressure or shock	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
415	opd_learn_ams	Coma (altered mental status or decreased level of consciousness)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
416	opd_learn_stroke	Suspected stroke	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
417	opd_learn_head_trauma	Severe head trauma	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
418	opd_learn_open_frac	Open fracture	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
419	opd_learn_closed_frac	Closed long bone fracture (e.g. femur)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
420	opd_learn_other_trauma	Other trauma	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
421	opd_learn_obstructed_labor	Obstructed labor	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
422	opd_learn_pph	Post-partum hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
423	opd_has_water	Section Header: <i>Outpatient Department (OPD) G. Infrastructure and Essential Equipment Rate availability of each item 1 to 31) Generally unavailable 2) Some availability 3) Adequate Availability If "don't know", enter -1 Provide comment if rating < 3</i> Clean, running water	radio 1 1) Generally unavailable 2 2) Some availability 3 3) Adequate Availability -1 -1) Don't know Custom alignment: LH Question number: 174

424	<p>opd_has_water_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_water] = '1' or [opd_has_water] = '2'</p>	Please comment	text								
425	opd_has_electric	Electricity source (e.g. wired, generator)	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1) Generally unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2) Some availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>3) Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>-1) Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 175</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
426	<p>opd_has_electric_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_electric] = '1' or [opd_has_electric] = '2'</p>	Please comment	text								
427	opd_has_comms	Designated telephone or radio for communicating with other facilities and/or prehospital providers	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1) Generally unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2) Some availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>3) Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>-1) Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 176</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
428	<p>opd_has_comms_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_comms] = '1' or [opd_has_comms] = '2'</p>	Please comment	text								
429	opd_paper_chart	Paper-based OPD chart	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1) Generally unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2) Some availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>3) Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>-1) Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 177</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
430	<p>opd_paper_chart_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_paper_chart] = '1' or [opd_paper_chart] = '2'</p>	Please comment	text								
431	opd_elec_chart	Electronic OPD chart	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1) Generally unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2) Some availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>3) Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>-1) Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 178</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
432	<p>opd_elec_chart_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_elec_chart] = '1' or [opd_elec_chart] = '2'</p>	Please comment	text								

433	opd_iso_room	Isolation room for infecious diseases (e.g. TB, haemorrhagic fever)	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 179	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
434	opd_iso_room_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_iso_room] = '1' or [opd_iso_room] = '2'	Please comment	text								
435	opd_accessible	Easy physical access to OPD for those requiring a wheelchair or stretcher	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 180	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
436	opd_accessible_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_accessible] = '1' or [opd_accessible] = '2'	Please comment	text								
437	opd_waiting	Designated waiting area	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 181	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
438	opd_waiting_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_waiting] = '1' or [opd_waiting] = '2'	Please comment	text								
439	opd_has_resus	Designated resuscitation area	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 182	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
440	opd_has_resus_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_resus] = '1' or [opd_has_resus] = '2'	Please comment	text								
441	opd_ecg_monitor	Electronic cardiac monitoring in OPD	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 183	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										

442	opd_ecg_monitor_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ecg_monitor] = '1' or [opd_ecg_monitor] = '2'	Please comment	text								
443	opd_codecart	Crash trolley or code cart with high-acuity equipment and supplies of various sizes in OPD	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 184	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
444	opd_codecart_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_codecart] = '1' or [opd_codecart] = '2'	Please comment	text								
445	opd_rapid_ambu	Rapid access to a transport ambulance and provider to administer care during transport for patients who need to be transferred to another facility	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 185	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
446	opd_rapid_ambu_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_rapid_ambu] = '1' or [opd_rapid_ambu] = '2'	Please comment	text								
447	opd_comm_mech	Is there a dedicated mechanism (radio, telephone) for communication with other facilities for transfer of patients?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 186	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
448	opd_comm_mech_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_comm_mech] = '1' or [opd_comm_mech] = '2'	Please comment	text								
449	opd_storage	Is there access to storage space within (or with immediate proximity to) the OPD, including secure storage for controlled substances?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 187	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
450	opd_storage_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_storage] = '1' or [opd_storage] = '2'	Please comment	text								

451	opd_workspace	Access to dedicated staff work area	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1) Generally unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2) Some availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>3) Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>-1) Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 188</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
452	opd_workspace_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_workspace] = '1' or [opd_workspace] = '2'	Please comment	text								
453	opd_toilet	Access to toilet facilities for patients and staff	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1) Generally unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2) Some availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>3) Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>-1) Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 189</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
454	opd_toilet_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_toilet] = '1' or [opd_toilet] = '2'	Please comment	text								
455	opd_handwash	Access to handwashing facilities in each patient care area	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1) Generally unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2) Some availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>3) Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>-1) Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 190</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
456	opd_handwash_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_handwash] = '1' or [opd_handwash] = '2'	Please comment	text								
457	opd_inventory	System for stocking, managing, and dispensing medications in the OPD	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1) Generally unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2) Some availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>3) Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>-1) Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 191</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
458	opd_inventory_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_inventory] = '1' or [opd_inventory] = '2'	Please comment	text								
459	opd_has_o2	Oxygen in the OPD	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1) Generally unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2) Some availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>3) Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>-1) Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 192</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										

460	<p>opd_has_o2_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_o2] = '1' or [opd_ha s_o2] = '2'</p>	Please comment	<p>text</p> <p>Question number: 193</p>								
461	<p>opd_o2_piped</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_o2] = '2' or [opd_ha s_o2] = '3'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Which of the following methods supply oxygen in the OPD?</i></p> <p>Central piped system</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
462	<p>opd_o2_cnctr</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_o2] = '2' or [opd_ha s_o2] = '3'</p>	Oxygen concentrator stored in the OPD	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
463	<p>opd_o2_tanks</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_o2] = '2' or [opd_ha s_o2] = '3'</p>	Tanks that are stored in the OPD	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
464	<p>opd_o2_central_tank</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_o2] = '2' or [opd_ha s_o2] = '3'</p>	Call for tank from central location if needed	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
465	<p>opd_o2_central_cnctr</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_has_o2] = '2' or [opd_ha s_o2] = '3'</p>	Call for oxygen from concentrator from central location if needed	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
466	<p>opd_protec_eye</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Which of the following personal protective equipment is available in the OPD?</i></p> <p>Eye protection</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 194</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
467	<p>opd_protec_n95</p>	N-95 mask	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
468	<p>opd_protec_gown</p>	Gowns	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
469	<p>opd_protec_glove</p>	Gloves	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
470	<p>opd_drwblood</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Outpatient Department (OPD) Diagnostic Services Please rate the availability of each item 1 to 3 1 - Generally unavailable 2 - Some availability 3 - Adequate availability Note: If "don't know", enter -1 For rating < 3, mark all relevant barriers: Infrastructure Absent Equipment Broken Equipment Stock Out (Supplies) Training Personnel User Fees Opening Hours Other</i></p> <p>Blood draw for laboratory testing in OPD (as opposed to central lab)</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know
1	Generally Unavailable										
2	Some Availability										
3	Adequate Availability										
-1	Don't know										

471	<p>opd_drwblood_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_drwblood] = '1' or [opd_drwblood] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_drwblood_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_drwblood_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_drwblood_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_drwblood_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_drwblood_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_drwblood_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_drwblood_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_drwblood_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_drwblood_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_drwblood_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_drwblood_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_drwblood_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_drwblood_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_drwblood_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_drwblood_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_drwblood_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_drwblood_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_drwblood_barrier__9	Other
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9	opd_drwblood_barrier__9	Other																												
472	<p>opd_drwblood_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_drwblood_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
473	<p>opd_hgb</p>	Hemoglobin	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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474	<p>opd_hgb_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_hgb] = '1' or [opd_hgb] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_hgb_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_hgb_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_hgb_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_hgb_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_hgb_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_hgb_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_hgb_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_hgb_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_hgb_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_hgb_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_hgb_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_hgb_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_hgb_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_hgb_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_hgb_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_hgb_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_hgb_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_hgb_barrier__9	Other
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475	<p>opd_hgb_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_hgb_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
476	<p>opd_fbc</p>	Full blood count	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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477	<p>opd_fbc_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_fbc] = '1' or [opd_fbc] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_fbc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_fbc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_fbc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_fbc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_fbc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_fbc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_fbc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_fbc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_fbc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_fbc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_fbc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_fbc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_fbc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_fbc_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_fbc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_fbc_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_fbc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_fbc_barrier__9	Other
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478	<p>opd_fbc_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_fbc_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

479	opd_ptinr	Coagulation profile (PT/PTT, INR)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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480	opd_ptinr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ptinr] = '1' or [opd_ptinr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_ptinr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_ptinr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_ptinr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_ptinr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_ptinr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_ptinr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_ptinr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_ptinr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_ptinr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_ptinr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_ptinr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_ptinr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_ptinr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_ptinr_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_ptinr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_ptinr_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_ptinr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_ptinr_barrier__9	Other
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481	opd_ptinr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ptinr_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
482	opd_electrolyte	Electrolytes	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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483	opd_electrolyte_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_electrolyte] = '1' or [opd_electrolyte] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_electrolyte_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_electrolyte_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_electrolyte_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_electrolyte_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_electrolyte_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_electrolyte_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_electrolyte_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_electrolyte_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_electrolyte_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_electrolyte_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_electrolyte_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_electrolyte_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_electrolyte_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_electrolyte_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_electrolyte_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_electrolyte_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_electrolyte_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_electrolyte_barrier__9	Other
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484	opd_electrolyte_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_electrolyte_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
485	opd_buncr	BUN and creatinine	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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486	<p>opd_buncr_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_buncr]= '1' or [opd_buncr] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_buncr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_buncr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_buncr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_buncr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_buncr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_buncr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_buncr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_buncr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_buncr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_buncr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_buncr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_buncr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_buncr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_buncr_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_buncr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_buncr_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_buncr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_buncr_barrier__9	Other
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487	<p>opd_buncr_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_buncr_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
488	<p>opd_lipase</p>	Lipase	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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489	<p>opd_lipase_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_lipase] = '1' or [opd_lipase] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_lipase_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_lipase_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_lipase_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_lipase_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_lipase_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_lipase_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_lipase_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_lipase_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_lipase_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_lipase_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_lipase_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_lipase_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_lipase_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_lipase_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_lipase_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_lipase_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_lipase_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_lipase_barrier__9	Other
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490	<p>opd_lipase_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_lipase_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
491	<p>opd_trop</p>	Cardiac marker (e.g. troponin)	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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492	<p>opd_trop_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_trop] = '1' or [opd_trop] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_trop_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_trop_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_trop_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_trop_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_trop_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_trop_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_trop_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_trop_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_trop_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_trop_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_trop_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_trop_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_trop_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_trop_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_trop_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_trop_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_trop_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_trop_barrier__9	Other
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493	<p>opd_trop_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_trop_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

494	opd_abg	Arterial blood gas	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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495	opd_abg_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_abg] = '1' or [opd_abg] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_abg_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_abg_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_abg_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_abg_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_abg_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_abg_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_abg_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_abg_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_abg_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_abg_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_abg_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_abg_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_abg_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_abg_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_abg_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_abg_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_abg_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_abg_barrier__9	Other
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496	opd_abg_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_abg_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
497	opd_typescrn	Cross matching for blood and blood products	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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498	opd_typescrn_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_typescrn] = '1' or [opd_t ypescrn] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_typescrn_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_typescrn_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_typescrn_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_typescrn_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_typescrn_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_typescrn_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_typescrn_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_typescrn_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_typescrn_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_typescrn_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_typescrn_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_typescrn_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_typescrn_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_typescrn_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_typescrn_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_typescrn_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_typescrn_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_typescrn_barrier__9	Other
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499	opd_typescrn_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_typescrn_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
500	opd_bcx	Blood cultures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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501	<p>opd_bcx_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_bcx] = '1' or [opd_bcx] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_bcx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_bcx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_bcx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_bcx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_bcx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_bcx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_bcx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_bcx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_bcx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_bcx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_bcx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_bcx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_bcx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_bcx_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_bcx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_bcx_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_bcx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_bcx_barrier__9	Other
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502	<p>opd_bcx_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_bcx_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
503	<p>opd_sterilesamp</p>	Capacity to obtain sterile blood samples for lab testing	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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504	<p>opd_sterilesamp_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_sterilesamp] = '1' or [opd_sterilesamp] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_sterilesamp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_sterilesamp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_sterilesamp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_sterilesamp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_sterilesamp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_sterilesamp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_sterilesamp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_sterilesamp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_sterilesamp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_sterilesamp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_sterilesamp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_sterilesamp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_sterilesamp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_sterilesamp_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_sterilesamp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_sterilesamp_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_sterilesamp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_sterilesamp_barrier__9	Other
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505	<p>opd_sterilesamp_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_sterilesamp_barrier(9)] = '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
506	<p>opd_reportlab</p>	System for reporting lab results in a timely fashion	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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507	<p>opd_reportlab_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_reportlab] = '1' or [opd_reportlab] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_reportlab_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_reportlab_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_reportlab_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_reportlab_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_reportlab_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_reportlab_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_reportlab_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_reportlab_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_reportlab_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_reportlab_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_reportlab_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_reportlab_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_reportlab_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_reportlab_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_reportlab_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_reportlab_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_reportlab_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_reportlab_barrier__9	Other
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508	<p>opd_reportlab_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_reportlab_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

509	opd_udip	Urine dipstick	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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510	opd_udip_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_udip] = '1' or [opd_udip] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_udip_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_udip_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_udip_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_udip_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_udip_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_udip_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_udip_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_udip_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_udip_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_udip_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_udip_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_udip_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_udip_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_udip_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_udip_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_udip_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_udip_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_udip_barrier__9	Other
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511	opd_udip_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_udip_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
512	opd_uhcg	Urine pregnancy	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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513	opd_uhcg_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_uhcg] = '1' or [opd_uhcg] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_uhcg_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_uhcg_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_uhcg_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_uhcg_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_uhcg_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_uhcg_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_uhcg_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_uhcg_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_uhcg_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_uhcg_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_uhcg_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_uhcg_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_uhcg_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_uhcg_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_uhcg_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_uhcg_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_uhcg_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_uhcg_barrier__9	Other
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514	opd_uhcg_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_uhcg_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
515	opd_glucose	Glucose	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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516	<p>opd_glucose_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_glucose] = '1' or [opd_glucose] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_glucose_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_glucose_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_glucose_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_glucose_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_glucose_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_glucose_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_glucose_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_glucose_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_glucose_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_glucose_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_glucose_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_glucose_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_glucose_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_glucose_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_glucose_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_glucose_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_glucose_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_glucose_barrier__9	Other
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517	<p>opd_glucose_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_glucose_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
518	opd_rdt	Malaria Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT)	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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519	<p>opd_rdt_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_rdt] = '1' or [opd_rdt] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_rdt_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_rdt_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_rdt_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_rdt_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_rdt_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_rdt_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_rdt_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_rdt_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_rdt_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_rdt_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_rdt_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_rdt_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_rdt_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_rdt_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_rdt_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_rdt_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_rdt_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_rdt_barrier__9	Other
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520	<p>opd_rdt_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_rdt_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
521	opd_malariasmr	Malaria smear/microscopy	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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522	<p>opd_malariasmr_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_malariasmr] = '1' or [opd_malariasmr] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_malariasmr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_malariasmr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_malariasmr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_malariasmr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_malariasmr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_malariasmr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_malariasmr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_malariasmr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_malariasmr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_malariasmr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_malariasmr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_malariasmr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_malariasmr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_malariasmr_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_malariasmr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_malariasmr_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_malariasmr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_malariasmr_barrier__9	Other
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523	<p>opd_malariasmr_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_malariasmr_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											

524	opd_rapidhiv	Rapid HIV testing	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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525	opd_rapidhiv_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_rapidhiv] = '1' or [opd_rapidhiv] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_rapidhiv_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_rapidhiv_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_rapidhiv_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_rapidhiv_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_rapidhiv_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_rapidhiv_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_rapidhiv_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_rapidhiv_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_rapidhiv_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_rapidhiv_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_rapidhiv_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_rapidhiv_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_rapidhiv_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_rapidhiv_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_rapidhiv_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_rapidhiv_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_rapidhiv_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_rapidhiv_barrier__9	Other
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526	opd_rapidhiv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_rapidhiv_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
527	opd_nonportxr	Stationary X-ray	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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528	opd_nonportxr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_nonportxr] = '1' or [opd_nonportxr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_nonportxr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_nonportxr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_nonportxr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_nonportxr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_nonportxr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_nonportxr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_nonportxr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_nonportxr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_nonportxr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_nonportxr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_nonportxr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_nonportxr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_nonportxr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_nonportxr_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_nonportxr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_nonportxr_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_nonportxr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_nonportxr_barrier__9	Other
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529	opd_nonportxr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_nonportxr_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
530	opd_portxr	Portable X-ray for use in OPD	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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532	<p>opd_portxr_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_portxr_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
533	<p>opd_us_hosp</p>	Ultrasound in the hospital	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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534	<p>opd_us_hosp_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_us_hosp] = '1' or [opd_us_hosp] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_us_hosp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_us_hosp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_us_hosp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_us_hosp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_us_hosp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_us_hosp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_us_hosp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_us_hosp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_us_hosp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_us_hosp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_us_hosp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_us_hosp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_us_hosp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_us_hosp_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_us_hosp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_us_hosp_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_us_hosp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_us_hosp_barrier__9	Other
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535	<p>opd_us_hosp_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_us_hosp_barrier(9)]= '1'</p>	Please specify	text																											
536	<p>opd_us_opd</p>	Ultrasound for use in OPD	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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537	<p>opd_us_opd_barrier</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [opd_us_opd] = '1' or [opd_us_opd] = '2'</p>	Relevant barriers	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>opd_us_opd_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>opd_us_opd_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>opd_us_opd_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>opd_us_opd_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>opd_us_opd_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>opd_us_opd_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>opd_us_opd_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>opd_us_opd_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>opd_us_opd_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	opd_us_opd_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_us_opd_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_us_opd_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_us_opd_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_us_opd_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_us_opd_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_us_opd_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_us_opd_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_us_opd_barrier__9	Other
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539	opd_ct	CT scan	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Generally Unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Some Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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540	opd_ct_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_ct] = '1' or [opd_ct] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>opd_ct_barrier__1</td> <td>Infrastr.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>opd_ct_barrier__2</td> <td>Absent equip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>opd_ct_barrier__3</td> <td>Broken equip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>opd_ct_barrier__4</td> <td>Stock out</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>opd_ct_barrier__5</td> <td>Training</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>opd_ct_barrier__6</td> <td>Prsnnl.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>opd_ct_barrier__7</td> <td>User fees</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>opd_ct_barrier__8</td> <td>Opening hours</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>opd_ct_barrier__9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	opd_ct_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_ct_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_ct_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_ct_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_ct_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_ct_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_ct_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_ct_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_ct_barrier__9	Other
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542	opd_systemrad	System for reporting radiology results in a timely fashion	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Generally Unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Some Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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543	opd_systemrad_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [opd_systemrad] = '1' or [opd_systemrad] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>opd_systemrad_barrier__1</td> <td>Infrastr.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>opd_systemrad_barrier__2</td> <td>Absent equip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>opd_systemrad_barrier__3</td> <td>Broken equip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>opd_systemrad_barrier__4</td> <td>Stock out</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>opd_systemrad_barrier__5</td> <td>Training</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>opd_systemrad_barrier__6</td> <td>Prsnnl.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>opd_systemrad_barrier__7</td> <td>User fees</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>opd_systemrad_barrier__8</td> <td>Opening hours</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>opd_systemrad_barrier__9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	opd_systemrad_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	opd_systemrad_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	opd_systemrad_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	opd_systemrad_barrier__4	Stock out	5	opd_systemrad_barrier__5	Training	6	opd_systemrad_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	opd_systemrad_barrier__7	User fees	8	opd_systemrad_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	opd_systemrad_barrier__9	Other
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544	opd_systemrad_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_systemrad_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
545	opd_rads_read	Who interprets radiology results? <i>read choices, choose all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>opd_rads_read__1</td> <td>Provider</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>opd_rads_read__2</td> <td>Radiologist</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>opd_rads_read__3</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>opd_rads_read__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 221</p>	1	opd_rads_read__1	Provider	2	opd_rads_read__2	Radiologist	3	opd_rads_read__3	Other	-1	opd_rads_read__1	Don't know															
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546	opd_rads_read_spec Show the field ONLY if: [opd_rads_read(3)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											

547	clinician_opd_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>Incomplete</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Unverified</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Complete</td></tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete				
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Instrument: Clinician Med (clinician_med)			^ Collapse										
548	med_record_id	Section Header: <i>MEDICAL WARD</i> Record ID	text (integer, Min: 0, Max: 1000000), Required										
549	med_facility	Name of facility <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	text, Required										
550	med_has_ed	Is there an ED in this hospital? <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes						
0	No												
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551	med_clin_lead	Is this participant a clinical lead of the medical ward? <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes						
0	No												
1	Yes												
552	med_date	Interview date and time (Day-Month-Year; 24 hour clock)	text (datetime_dmy)										
553	med_where_work	Section Header: <i>Medical WardA. Background Questions</i> Where in the hospital do you primarily work? <i>if the respondent works in multiple areas, ask them to choose the area they work in the most often</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Outpatient Department (OPD)</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Emergency unit (ED)</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Inpatient ward</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>HDU/ICU</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table> Question number: 1	1	Outpatient Department (OPD)	2	Emergency unit (ED)	3	Inpatient ward	4	HDU/ICU	5	Other
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5	Other												
554	med_where_work_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_where_work] = '5' or [med_where_work] = '3'	Please specify	text										
555	med_role	What is your role? <i>Read all choices</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Doctor</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Nurse</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Clinical Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Medical Assistant</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table> Question number: 2	1	Doctor	2	Nurse	3	Clinical Officer	4	Medical Assistant	5	Other
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3	Clinical Officer												
4	Medical Assistant												
5	Other												
556	med_role_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_role] = '5'	Please specify	text										
557	med_days_at_med	How many days per week do you work in the ward? <i>This question refers to the medical ward even if it is not where they primarily work, enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 7) Question number: 3										
558	med_hours_prsnt	Section Header: <i>Medical WardB. Hospital Structure/Staffing</i> During which hours is the ward covered by providers who are physically present in the ward?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than 24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>The ward is never covered by providers who are physically present in the ward</td></tr> </table> Question number: 4	1	24 hours a day	2	Less than 24 hours a day	-1	Don't know	-2	The ward is never covered by providers who are physically present in the ward		
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559	med_hours_prsnt_start Show the field ONLY if: [med_hours_prsnt] = '2'	Coverage starts at	dropdown <table border="1"><tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr><tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr><tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr><tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr><tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr><tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr><tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr><tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr><tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr><tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr><tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr><tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr><tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr><tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr><tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr><tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr><tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr><tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr><tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr><tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr><tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr><tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr><tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr><tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr></table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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561	med_hours_in	During which hours is the ward covered by providers who are on call, inside the facility?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than 24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>The ward is never covered by providers who are on call, inside the facility</td></tr> </table> Question number: 5	1	24 hours a day	2	Less than 24 hours a day	-1	Don't know	-2	The ward is never covered by providers who are on call, inside the facility																																								
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562	med_hours_in_start Show the field ONLY if: [med_hours_in] = '2'	Coverage starts at	<table border="1"><thead><tr><th colspan="2">dropdown</th></tr></thead><tbody><tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr><tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr><tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr><tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr><tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr><tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr><tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr><tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr><tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr><tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr><tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr><tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr><tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr><tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr><tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr><tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr><tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr><tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr><tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr><tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr><tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr><tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr><tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr><tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr></tbody></table>	dropdown		12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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563	<p>med_hours_in_stop</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [med_hours_in] = '2'</p>	<p>Coverage ends at</p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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564	<p>med_hours_out</p>	<p>During which hours is the ward covered by providers who are on call, outside the facility?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than 24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>The ward is never covered by providers who are on call, outside the facility</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 6</p>	1	24 hours a day	2	Less than 24 hours a day	-1	Don't know	-2	The ward is never covered by providers who are on call, outside the facility																																								
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566	med_hours_out_stop Show the field ONLY if: [med_hours_out] = '2'	Coverage ends at	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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10	10am																																																		
11	11am																																																		
567	med_rn_available	Are nurses available 24 hours a day, every day of the week in the ward for critically ill patients on your ward? <i>Read all choices</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes, in the ward</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Yes, on call within the facility</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Yes, on call outside the facility</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 7</p>	0	No	1	Yes, in the ward	2	Yes, on call within the facility	3	Yes, on call outside the facility	-1	Don't know																																						
0	No																																																		
1	Yes, in the ward																																																		
2	Yes, on call within the facility																																																		
3	Yes, on call outside the facility																																																		
-1	Don't know																																																		
568	med_beds	How many beds are on your ward? <i>enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000) Question number: 9																																																
569	med_rn_avgday Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	How many nurses work in your ward on an average daytime shift? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to ward, code -1 if unsure</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 14																																																
570	med_rn_today Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	How many nurses are working in your ward today? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to ward, code -1 if unsure</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 15																																																
571	med_rn_avgnight Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	How many nurses work in your ward on an average overnight shift? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to ward, code -1 if unsure</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 16																																																
572	med_rn_lastnight Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	How many nurses worked in your ward last night? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to ward, code -1 if unsure</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 17																																																
573	med_census Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	How many patients are currently in your ward? <i>enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 18																																																

574	med_obs_freq	What is the frequency of nurse observations for ward patients? <i>give answer in hours, enter -1 if unknown, enter -2 if no standard frequency</i>	text (number, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 19						
575	med_obs_ccfreq	What is the frequency of nurse observations for critically ill ward patients? <i>give answer in hours, enter -1 if unknown, enter -2 if no standard frequency</i>	text (number, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 20						
576	med_notify_change	If a nurse observes a clinical change, who does the nurse call? <i>enter -1 if don't know, enter 0 if nobody</i>	text Question number: 21						
577	med_rn_change	Can nurses initiate treatment without specific provider orders in response to an observed clinical change?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> Question number: 22	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
578	med_rn_change_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_rn_change] = '1'	Please specify	text						
579	med_from_opded	Section Header: <i>Medical WardC. Transfers and Patient Flow</i> Does your ward admit patients directly from the ED/OPD?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> Question number: 23	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
580	med_sick_accept Show the field ONLY if: [med_from_opded] = '1'	Are patients ever too sick (meaning unstable vital signs or requiring interventions or monitoring that are too frequent or prognosis is too poor) to be admitted to your ward and need to stay in the OPD/ED as a result?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> Question number: 25	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
581	med_sick_accept_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_sick_accept] = '1'	Please specify	text						
582	med_trans_ed Show the field ONLY if: [has_ed] = '1' or [med_has_ed] = '1'	Does your ward transfer patients to the ED of this hospital?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> Question number: 26	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
583	med_trans_ed_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_trans_ed] = '1'	Please specify	text						
584	med_transfer_out	Does your ward transfer patients from the ward directly to other hospitals or health facilities?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> Question number: 27	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
585	med_transfer_number Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Approximately how many patients were transferred out from your ward to other hospitals or health facilities in the last month? <i>Ask respondent to give best guess, for example, consider how many patients they personally have transferred and what % of the time they work. Enter -1 if unable to give best guess</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 28						

586	med_trans_dka Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Section Header: <i>For the following conditions, indicate how often patient with that condition is transferred out to another hospital. Please consider only patients who are actually transferred, not how often you feel a patient with this condition requires transfer.</i> Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 29	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
587	med_trans_seizures Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Seizures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
588	med_trans_poisoning Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Poisoning	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
589	med_trans_chf Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Severe heart failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
590	med_trans_arf Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Severe renal failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
591	med_trans_respiratory Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Respiratory distress or respiratory failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														

592	med_trans_shock Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Low blood pressure or shock	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
593	med_trans_ams Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Coma (altered mental status or decreased level of consciousness)	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
594	med_trans_stroke Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Suspected stroke	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
595	med_trans_head_trauma Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Severe head trauma	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
596	med_trans_open_frac Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Open fracture	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
597	med_trans_closed_frac Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Closed long bone fracture (e.g. femur)	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know

598	med_trans_other_trauma Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Other trauma	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
599	med_trans_obstructed_labor Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Obstructed labor	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
600	med_trans_pph Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	Post-partum hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
601	med_ambulance Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	When patients are transferred from the ward to another hospital/healthcare facility, how often is it by ambulance?	radio 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know Custom alignment: LH Question number: 30
602	med_trans_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'	What, if any, barriers do you commonly encounter when transferring patients to another hospital/healthcare facility? <i>Do not read choices, select all that apply</i>	checkbox 1 med_trans_barrier__1 Patient finances 2 med_trans_barrier__2 Availability of transportation 3 med_trans_barrier__3 Patient too sick to transfer 4 med_trans_barrier__4 Bed space at accepting hospital 5 med_trans_barrier__5 Approval for transfer from accepting hospital 6 med_trans_barrier__6 Family objection 7 med_trans_barrier__7 Other 0 med_trans_barrier__0 No barriers -1 med_trans_barrier__1 Don't know Question number: 31
603	med_trans_barrier_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_trans_barrier(7)] = '1'	Please specify	text

604	<p>med_trans_accompany</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1'</p>	<p>When critically ill patients are transferred to other facilities by ambulance, what, if any, staff typically accompany the patient, other than driver?</p> <p><i>do not read choices, check all that apply</i></p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1044 111 1549 737"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_trans_accompany__1</td><td>Nurse</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_trans_accompany__2</td><td>Clinical officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_trans_accompany__3</td><td>Medical assistant</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_trans_accompany__4</td><td>Doctors without specialist training</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_trans_accompany__5</td><td>Emergency medicine specialists</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_trans_accompany__6</td><td>Other specialist doctor</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_trans_accompany__7</td><td>Emergency medical technician/paramedic</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_trans_accompany__8</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>med_trans_accompany__0</td><td>Staff do not typically accompany critically ill patients</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>med_trans_accompany__1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>med_trans_accompany__2</td><td>Patients do not go by ambulance</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 32</p>	1	med_trans_accompany__1	Nurse	2	med_trans_accompany__2	Clinical officer	3	med_trans_accompany__3	Medical assistant	4	med_trans_accompany__4	Doctors without specialist training	5	med_trans_accompany__5	Emergency medicine specialists	6	med_trans_accompany__6	Other specialist doctor	7	med_trans_accompany__7	Emergency medical technician/paramedic	8	med_trans_accompany__8	Other	0	med_trans_accompany__0	Staff do not typically accompany critically ill patients	-1	med_trans_accompany__1	Don't know	-2	med_trans_accompany__2	Patients do not go by ambulance
1	med_trans_accompany__1	Nurse																																		
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-1	med_trans_accompany__1	Don't know																																		
-2	med_trans_accompany__2	Patients do not go by ambulance																																		
605	<p>med_trans_accompany_spec</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [med_trans_accompany(8)] = '1'</p>	<p>Please specify</p>	<p>text</p>																																	
606	<p>med_trans_treatment</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfer_out] = '1' and [med_trans_accompany(-2)] < > '1'</p>	<p>When patients are transferred to other facilities by ambulance, what if any treatments can be done in the ambulance?</p> <p><i>read choices, check all that apply</i></p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1044 963 1528 1694"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_trans_treatment__1</td><td>Vital sign monitoring</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_trans_treatment__2</td><td>Cardiac monitoring</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_trans_treatment__3</td><td>IV fluid administration</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_trans_treatment__4</td><td>IV medication administration</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_trans_treatment__5</td><td>Blood transfusion</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_trans_treatment__6</td><td>Oxygen delivery</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_trans_treatment__7</td><td>Manual bag ventilation (through endotracheal tube or bag-valve-mask)</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_trans_treatment__8</td><td>Mechanical non-invasive ventilation (BIPAP or CPAP)</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_trans_treatment__9</td><td>Mechanical invasive ventilation with endotracheal tube</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>med_trans_treatment__0</td><td>None</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>med_trans_treatment__1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 33</p>	1	med_trans_treatment__1	Vital sign monitoring	2	med_trans_treatment__2	Cardiac monitoring	3	med_trans_treatment__3	IV fluid administration	4	med_trans_treatment__4	IV medication administration	5	med_trans_treatment__5	Blood transfusion	6	med_trans_treatment__6	Oxygen delivery	7	med_trans_treatment__7	Manual bag ventilation (through endotracheal tube or bag-valve-mask)	8	med_trans_treatment__8	Mechanical non-invasive ventilation (BIPAP or CPAP)	9	med_trans_treatment__9	Mechanical invasive ventilation with endotracheal tube	0	med_trans_treatment__0	None	-1	med_trans_treatment__1	Don't know
1	med_trans_treatment__1	Vital sign monitoring																																		
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0	med_trans_treatment__0	None																																		
-1	med_trans_treatment__1	Don't know																																		
607	<p>med_protocol_abcd</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Medical Ward D. Clinical Are the following protocols available at this facility</i></p> <p>Protocol for initial approach to ABCs (airway, breathing, circulation, etc.) and basic neurologic function</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1044 1787 1195 1900"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																											
0	No																																			
1	Yes																																			
-1	Don't know																																			

608	med_protocol_med_resus Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Medical resuscitation checklist	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
609	med_protocol_volume Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for volume resuscitation of children and adults	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
610	med_protocol_malnourish Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for adjusting interventions for malnourished patients	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
611	med_protocol_pt_pep Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for post-exposure prevention of STI/HIV, emergency contraception, counseling	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
612	med_protocol_asthma Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Condition-specific management protocols for:</i> Asthma exacerbation	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 47
613	med_protocol_pneumonia Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Pneumonia	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
614	med_protocol_ob_bleed Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Maternal hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
615	med_protocol_sepsis Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Sepsis	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
616	med_protocol_dka Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
617	med_protocol_other Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Other	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
618	med_protocol_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_protocol_other] = '1'	Please specify	text

619	med_protocol_dispo Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Are the following disposition protocols available at this facility</i> Formal written policy outlining the criteria for discharging a patient from your ward?	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 48
620	med_protocol_handoff Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Hand-over protocols when transferring patients from one care provider to another	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
621	med_protocol_ext_trans Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Are the following outside transfer protocols available at this facility</i> Condition-specific transfer or referral protocols (e.g. criteria for transfer of burn patients to burn center)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 49
622	med_protocol_trans_comm Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Communication with receiving facility prior to transfer of patients with emergency conditions	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
623	med_protocol_infect_contr Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Are the following safety protocols available at this facility</i> Infection prevention and control protocols	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 50
624	med_protocol_hcw_pep Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for post exposure prophylaxis for health care workers	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
625	med_protocol_security Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Security protocols to protect staff, patients, and infrastructure from violence	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
626	med_protocol_hazards Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for managing hazardous exposures (including designated decontamination area)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
627	med_protocol_waste Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Containment and disposal of sharps and biomedical waste	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
628	med_protocol_inter_event Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Plan to ensure ward staff and patient safety if an incident occurs within the ward (including space, transport, communications)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know

629	med_protocol_goc Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Are protocols or guidelines on end of life care available at this facility?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 51</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
630	med_sw Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Medical Ward Ancillary Services Please rate the availability of each item 1 to 3 1 - Generally unavailable 2 - Some availability 3 - Adequate availability Note: If "don't know", enter -1 For rating < 3, mark all relevant barriers: Infrastructure Absent Equipment Broken Equipment Stock Out (Supplies) Training Personnel User Fees Opening Hours Other</i> Social work services	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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631	med_sw_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_sw] = '1' or [med_sw] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_sw_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_sw_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_sw_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_sw_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_sw_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_sw_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_sw_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_sw_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_sw_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_sw_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_sw_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_sw_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_sw_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_sw_barrier__5	Training	6	med_sw_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_sw_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_sw_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_sw_barrier__9	Other
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632	med_sw_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_sw_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
633	med_transport Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Patient transport services	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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634	med_transport_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_transport] = '1' or [med_transport] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_transport_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_transport_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_transport_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_transport_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_transport_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_transport_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_transport_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_transport_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_transport_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_transport_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_transport_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_transport_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_transport_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_transport_barrier__5	Training	6	med_transport_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_transport_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_transport_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_transport_barrier__9	Other
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635	med_transport_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_transport_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
636	med_security Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Security	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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637	med_security_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_security] = '1' or [med_security] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_security_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_security_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_security_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_security_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_security_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_security_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_security_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_security_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_security_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_security_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_security_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_security_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_security_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_security_barrier__5	Training	6	med_security_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_security_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_security_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_security_barrier__9	Other
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638	med_security_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_security_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
639	med_spirit Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Spiritual support	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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640	med_spirit_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_spirit] = '1' or [med_spirit] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_spirit_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_spirit_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_spirit_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_spirit_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_spirit_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_spirit_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_spirit_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_spirit_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_spirit_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_spirit_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_spirit_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_spirit_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_spirit_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_spirit_barrier__5	Training	6	med_spirit_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_spirit_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_spirit_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_spirit_barrier__9	Other
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641	med_spirit_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_spirit_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
642	med_nutritn Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Nutrition	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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643	med_nutritn_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_nutritn] = '1' or [med_nutritn] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_nutritn_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_nutritn_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_nutritn_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_nutritn_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_nutritn_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_nutritn_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_nutritn_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_nutritn_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_nutritn_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_nutritn_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_nutritn_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_nutritn_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_nutritn_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_nutritn_barrier__5	Training	6	med_nutritn_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_nutritn_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_nutritn_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_nutritn_barrier__9	Other
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644	med_nutritn_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_nutritn_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

645	med_resptherapy Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Respiratory therapy	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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646	med_resptherapy_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_resptherapy]='1' or [med_resptherapy] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_resptherapy_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_resptherapy_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_resptherapy_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_resptherapy_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_resptherapy_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_resptherapy_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_resptherapy_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_resptherapy_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_resptherapy_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_resptherapy_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_resptherapy_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_resptherapy_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_resptherapy_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_resptherapy_barrier__5	Training	6	med_resptherapy_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_resptherapy_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_resptherapy_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_resptherapy_barrier__9	Other
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647	med_resptherapy_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_resptherapy_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
648	med_engineer Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Clinical engineering	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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649	med_engineer_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_engineer] = '1' or [med_engineer] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_engineer_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_engineer_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_engineer_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_engineer_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_engineer_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_engineer_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_engineer_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_engineer_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_engineer_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_engineer_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_engineer_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_engineer_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_engineer_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_engineer_barrier__5	Training	6	med_engineer_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_engineer_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_engineer_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_engineer_barrier__9	Other
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650	med_engineer_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_engineer_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											
651	med_pt Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Physical therapy	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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652	med_pt_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_pt] = '1' or [med_pt] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_pt_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_pt_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_pt_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_pt_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_pt_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_pt_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_pt_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_pt_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_pt_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_pt_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_pt_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_pt_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_pt_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_pt_barrier__5	Training	6	med_pt_barrier__6	Prsnl.	7	med_pt_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_pt_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_pt_barrier__9	Other
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653	med_pt_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_pt_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
654	med_qi Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Medical Ward Quality Improvement</i> Are there quality improvement projects on your ward currently or at any time in the past year? <i>A quality improvement project is an effort to improve patient care based on an evaluation of the shortcomings of the care the ward provides and the changing knowledge base that informs best care</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 60</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
655	med_registry Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Is there a systematic process for collecting patient data that links condition, management, and outcomes (e.g. trauma registry)?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 61</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
656	med_m_and_m Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Are there regular meetings convened to use clinical data for quality improvement (e.g. morbidity and mortality conferences, preventable death panels)?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 62</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
657	med_audits Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Is there tracking (e.g. clinical audit) to ensure that quality improvement actions (e.g. corrective action) are implemented after review meetings?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 63</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
658	med_clin_template Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Is there a clinical document template (e.g. standardized clinical chart)?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 64</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
659	med_ext_visitor Show the field ONLY if: [med_clin_lead] = '1'	Has there been a visit to this ward by a supervisor from outside the facility within the last 6 months?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 65</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													

660	med_ext_visitor_org Show the field ONLY if: [med_ext_visitor] = '1'	What organization did the supervisor work for?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>NGO (e.g. PIH, CHAM)</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Ministry of Health</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 66</p>	1	NGO (e.g. PIH, CHAM)	2	Ministry of Health	3	Other	-1	Don't know																			
1	NGO (e.g. PIH, CHAM)																													
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661	med_ext_visitor_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ext_visitor_org] = '3'	Please specify	text																											
662	med_ext_visitor_doc Show the field ONLY if: [med_ext_visitor] = '1'	Is there any documentation from the most recent external supervisory visit?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 67</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
663	med_ext_visitor_doc_detail Show the field ONLY if: [med_ext_visitor_doc] = '1'	Does the document provide any feedback or comments on some aspect of emergency services?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 68</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
664	med_manual	Section Header: <i>Medical Ward Signal Functions Please rate the availability of each item 1 to 3 1 - Generally unavailable 2 - Some availability 3 - Adequate availability Note: If "don't know", enter -1 For rating < 3, mark all relevant barriers: Infrastructure Absent Equipment Broken Equipment Stock Out (Supplies) Training Personnel User Fees Opening Hours Other AIRWAY INTERVENTIONS</i> Use of manual maneuvers (e.g. jaw thrust, chin lift)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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3	Adequate Availability																													
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665	med_manual_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_manual] = '1' or [med_manual] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_manual_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_manual_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_manual_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_manual_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_manual_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_manual_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_manual_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_manual_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_manual_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_manual_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_manual_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_manual_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_manual_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_manual_barrier__5	Training	6	med_manual_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_manual_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_manual_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_manual_barrier__9	Other
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666	med_manual_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_manual_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
667	med_suction	Use of suction	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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668	med_suction_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_suction] = '1' or [med_suction] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_suction_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_suction_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_suction_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_suction_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_suction_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_suction_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_suction_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_suction_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_suction_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_suction_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_suction_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_suction_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_suction_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_suction_barrier__5	Training	6	med_suction_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_suction_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_suction_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_suction_barrier__9	Other
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9	med_suction_barrier__9	Other																												
669	med_suction_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_suction_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
670	med_oronas	Placement of oro- or naso-pharyngeal airway device	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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671	med_oronas_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_oronas] = '1' or [med_oronas] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_oronas_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_oronas_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_oronas_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_oronas_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_oronas_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_oronas_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_oronas_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_oronas_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_oronas_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_oronas_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_oronas_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_oronas_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_oronas_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_oronas_barrier__5	Training	6	med_oronas_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_oronas_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_oronas_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_oronas_barrier__9	Other
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672	med_oronas_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_oronas_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
673	med_glottic	Placement of supraglottic device	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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674	med_glottic_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_glottic]= '1' or [med_glottic] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_glottic_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_glottic_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_glottic_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_glottic_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_glottic_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_glottic_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_glottic_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_glottic_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_glottic_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_glottic_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_glottic_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_glottic_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_glottic_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_glottic_barrier__5	Training	6	med_glottic_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_glottic_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_glottic_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_glottic_barrier__9	Other
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675	med_glottic_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_glottic_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

676	med_intubate	Endotracheal intubation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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677	med_intubate_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_intubate] = '1' or [med_intubate] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_intubate_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_intubate_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_intubate_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_intubate_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_intubate_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_intubate_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_intubate_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_intubate_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_intubate_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_intubate_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_intubate_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_intubate_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_intubate_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_intubate_barrier__5	Training	6	med_intubate_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_intubate_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_intubate_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_intubate_barrier__9	Other
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678	med_intubate_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_intubate_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
679	med_cric	Creation of surgical airway	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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680	med_cric_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_cric] = '1' or [med_cric] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_cric_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_cric_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_cric_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_cric_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_cric_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_cric_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_cric_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_cric_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_cric_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_cric_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_cric_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_cric_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_cric_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_cric_barrier__5	Training	6	med_cric_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_cric_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_cric_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_cric_barrier__9	Other
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681	med_cric_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_cric_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
682	med_checkspo2	Section Header: <i>Breathing Interventions</i> Continuous pulse oximetry measurement	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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683	med_checkspo2_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_checkspo2] = '1' or [med_checkspo2] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_checkspo2_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_checkspo2_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_checkspo2_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_checkspo2_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_checkspo2_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_checkspo2_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_checkspo2_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_checkspo2_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_checkspo2_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_checkspo2_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_checkspo2_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_checkspo2_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_checkspo2_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_checkspo2_barrier__5	Training	6	med_checkspo2_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_checkspo2_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_checkspo2_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_checkspo2_barrier__9	Other
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684	med_checkspo2_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_checkspo2_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
685	med_txasthma	Administration of critical therapies for reactive airway disease	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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686	med_txasthma_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_txasthma] = '1' or [med_txasthma] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_txasthma_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_txasthma_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_txasthma_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_txasthma_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_txasthma_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_txasthma_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_txasthma_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_txasthma_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_txasthma_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_txasthma_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_txasthma_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_txasthma_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_txasthma_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_txasthma_barrier__5	Training	6	med_txasthma_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_txasthma_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_txasthma_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_txasthma_barrier__9	Other
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687	med_txasthma_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_txasthma_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											
688	med_giveo2	Administration of oxygen	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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689	med_giveo2_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_giveo2] = '1' or [med_giveo2] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_giveo2_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_giveo2_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_giveo2_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_giveo2_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_giveo2_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_giveo2_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_giveo2_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_giveo2_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_giveo2_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_giveo2_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_giveo2_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_giveo2_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_giveo2_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_giveo2_barrier__5	Training	6	med_giveo2_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_giveo2_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_giveo2_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_giveo2_barrier__9	Other
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690	med_giveo2_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_giveo2_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											

691	med_bagmask	Bag-valve-mask ventilation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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692	med_bagmask_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_bagmask] = '1' or [med_bagmask] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_bagmask_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_bagmask_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_bagmask_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_bagmask_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_bagmask_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_bagmask_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_bagmask_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_bagmask_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_bagmask_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_bagmask_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_bagmask_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_bagmask_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_bagmask_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_bagmask_barrier__5	Training	6	med_bagmask_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_bagmask_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_bagmask_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_bagmask_barrier__9	Other
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693	med_bagmask_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_bagmask_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
694	med_ptx	Perform needle decompression of tension pneumothorax	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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695	med_ptx_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_ptx] = '1' or [med_ptx] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_ptx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_ptx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_ptx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_ptx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_ptx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_ptx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_ptx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_ptx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_ptx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_ptx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_ptx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_ptx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_ptx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_ptx_barrier__5	Training	6	med_ptx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_ptx_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_ptx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_ptx_barrier__9	Other
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696	med_ptx_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ptx_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
697	med_chesttube	Placement of chest tube	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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698	med_chesttube_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_chesttube] = '1' or [med_chesttube] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_chesttube_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_chesttube_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_chesttube_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_chesttube_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_chesttube_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_chesttube_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_chesttube_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_chesttube_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_chesttube_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_chesttube_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_chesttube_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_chesttube_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_chesttube_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_chesttube_barrier__5	Training	6	med_chesttube_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_chesttube_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_chesttube_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_chesttube_barrier__9	Other
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699	med_chesttube_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_chesttube_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
700	med_nippv	Non-invasive mechanical ventilation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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701	med_nippv_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_nippv] = '1' or [med_nippv] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_nippv_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_nippv_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_nippv_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_nippv_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_nippv_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_nippv_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_nippv_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_nippv_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_nippv_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_nippv_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_nippv_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_nippv_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_nippv_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_nippv_barrier__5	Training	6	med_nippv_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_nippv_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_nippv_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_nippv_barrier__9	Other
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702	med_nippv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_nippv_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											
703	med_vent	Invasive mechanical ventilation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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704	med_vent_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '1' or [med_vent] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_vent_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_vent_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_vent_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_vent_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_vent_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_vent_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_vent_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_vent_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_vent_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_vent_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_vent_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_vent_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_vent_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_vent_barrier__5	Training	6	med_vent_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_vent_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_vent_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_vent_barrier__9	Other
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705	med_vent_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											

706	med_number_vented Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '2' or [med_vent] = '3'	How many patients can receive mechanical ventilation via a ventilator and endotracheal tube on your ward at any one time? <i>enter 0 if none, -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 86																											
707	med_vent_policy Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '2' or [med_vent] = '3'	Is there a written policy for who can or cannot be intubated and/or placed on mechanical ventilation?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 87	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
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708	med_extubate_policy Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '2' or [med_vent] = '3'	Is there a written policy for if and when intubation and/or mechanical ventilation can be withdrawn?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 88	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
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709	med_hob Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '2' or [med_vent] = '3'	Section Header: <i>Mechanical Ventilation</i> Maintain head of bed in semi-recumbent position (30-45 degrees) to reduce aspiration and ventilator associated pneumonia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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710	med_hob_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_hob] = '1' or [med_hob] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_hob_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_hob_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_hob_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_hob_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_hob_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_hob_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_hob_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_hob_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_hob_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_hob_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_hob_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_hob_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_hob_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_hob_barrier__5	Training	6	med_hob_barrier__6	Prsnl.	7	med_hob_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_hob_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_hob_barrier__9	Other
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711	med_hob_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_hob_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
712	med_ventsxn Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '2' or [med_vent] = '3'	Perform continuous or intermittent (at least every 4 hours) subglottic suctioning of secretions, via cuffed endotracheal tube	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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713	med_ventsxn_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_ventsxn] = '1' or [med_ventsxn] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_ventsxn_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_ventsxn_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_ventsxn_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_ventsxn_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_ventsxn_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_ventsxn_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_ventsxn_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_ventsxn_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_ventsxn_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_ventsxn_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_ventsxn_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_ventsxn_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_ventsxn_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_ventsxn_barrier__5	Training	6	med_ventsxn_barrier__6	Prsnl.	7	med_ventsxn_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_ventsxn_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_ventsxn_barrier__9	Other
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714	med_ventsn_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ventsn_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
715	med_sbt Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '2' or [med_vent] = '3'	Perform daily spontaneous breathing trials	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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716	med_sbt_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_sbt] = '1' or [med_sbt] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_sbt_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_sbt_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_sbt_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_sbt_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_sbt_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_sbt_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_sbt_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_sbt_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_sbt_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_sbt_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_sbt_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_sbt_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_sbt_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_sbt_barrier__5	Training	6	med_sbt_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_sbt_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_sbt_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_sbt_barrier__9	Other
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718	med_sat Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '2' or [med_vent] = '3'	Perform daily spontaneous awakening trials	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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719	med_sat_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_sat] = '1' or [med_sat] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_sat_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_sat_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_sat_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_sat_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_sat_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_sat_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_sat_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_sat_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_sat_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_sat_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_sat_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_sat_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_sat_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_sat_barrier__5	Training	6	med_sat_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_sat_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_sat_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_sat_barrier__9	Other
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720	med_sat_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_sat_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
721	med_ventpt Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '2' or [med_vent] = '3'	Perform early mobilization for mechanically ventilated patients	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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722	med_ventpt_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_ventpt] = '1' or [med_ventpt] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_ventpt_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_ventpt_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_ventpt_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_ventpt_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_ventpt_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_ventpt_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_ventpt_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_ventpt_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_ventpt_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_ventpt_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_ventpt_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_ventpt_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_ventpt_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_ventpt_barrier__5	Training	6	med_ventpt_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_ventpt_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_ventpt_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_ventpt_barrier__9	Other
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723	med_ventpt_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ventpt_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
724	med_cam Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '2' or [med_vent] = '3'	Assess delirium in mechanically ventilated patients at least twice a day	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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725	med_cam_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_cam]= '1' or [med_cam] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_cam_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_cam_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_cam_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_cam_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_cam_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_cam_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_cam_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_cam_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_cam_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_cam_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_cam_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_cam_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_cam_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_cam_barrier__5	Training	6	med_cam_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_cam_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_cam_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_cam_barrier__9	Other
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726	med_cam_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_cam_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
727	med_pots Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '2' or [med_vent] = '3'	Assess pain in mechanically ventilated patients at least twice a day	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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729	med_pots_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_pots_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

730	med_rass Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '2' or [med_vent] = '3'	Assess agitation/sedation in mechanically ventilated patients at least twice a day	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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731	med_rass_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_rass] = '1' or [med_rass] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_rass_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_rass_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_rass_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_rass_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_rass_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_rass_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_rass_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_rass_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_rass_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_rass_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_rass_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_rass_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_rass_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_rass_barrier__5	Training	6	med_rass_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_rass_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_rass_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_rass_barrier__9	Other
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733	med_paralyze Show the field ONLY if: [med_vent] = '2' or [med_vent] = '3'	Administer and maintain neuromuscular blockade	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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734	med_paralyze_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_paralyze] = '1' or [med_paralyze] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_paralyze_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_paralyze_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_paralyze_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_paralyze_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_paralyze_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_paralyze_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_paralyze_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_paralyze_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_paralyze_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_paralyze_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_paralyze_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_paralyze_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_paralyze_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_paralyze_barrier__5	Training	6	med_paralyze_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_paralyze_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_paralyze_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_paralyze_barrier__9	Other
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736	med_ors	Section Header: <i>Volume Resuscitation Interventions</i> Administer oral rehydration	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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737	med_ors_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_ors] = '1' or [med_ors] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_ors_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_ors_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_ors_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_ors_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_ors_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_ors_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_ors_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_ors_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_ors_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_ors_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_ors_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_ors_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_ors_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_ors_barrier__5	Training	6	med_ors_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_ors_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_ors_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_ors_barrier__9	Other
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738	med_ors_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ors_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
739	med_adj_ivf	Adjust fluid resuscitation for malnutrition or severe anemia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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740	med_adj_ivf_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_adj_ivf] = '1' or [med_adj_ivf] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_adj_ivf_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_adj_ivf_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_adj_ivf_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_adj_ivf_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_adj_ivf_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_adj_ivf_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_adj_ivf_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_adj_ivf_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_adj_ivf_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_adj_ivf_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_adj_ivf_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_adj_ivf_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_adj_ivf_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_adj_ivf_barrier__5	Training	6	med_adj_ivf_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_adj_ivf_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_adj_ivf_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_adj_ivf_barrier__9	Other
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741	med_adj_ivf_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_adj_ivf_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
742	med_piv	Place peripheral IV access	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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743	med_piv_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_piv] = '1' or [med_piv] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_piv_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_piv_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_piv_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_piv_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_piv_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_piv_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_piv_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_piv_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_piv_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_piv_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_piv_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_piv_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_piv_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_piv_barrier__5	Training	6	med_piv_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_piv_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_piv_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_piv_barrier__9	Other
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744	med_piv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_piv_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

745	med_io	Establish intraosseous access	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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746	med_io_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_io] = '1' or [med_io] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_io_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_io_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_io_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_io_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_io_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_io_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_io_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_io_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_io_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_io_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_io_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_io_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_io_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_io_barrier__5	Training	6	med_io_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_io_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_io_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_io_barrier__9	Other
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747	med_io_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_io_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
748	med_cutdown	Perform venous cutdown	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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749	med_cutdown_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_cutdown] = '1' or [med_cutdown] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_cutdown_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_cutdown_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_cutdown_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_cutdown_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_cutdown_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_cutdown_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_cutdown_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_cutdown_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_cutdown_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_cutdown_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_cutdown_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_cutdown_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_cutdown_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_cutdown_barrier__5	Training	6	med_cutdown_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_cutdown_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_cutdown_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_cutdown_barrier__9	Other
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750	med_cutdown_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_cutdown_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
751	med_cvc	Establish central venous access	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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752	med_cvc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_cvc]='1' or [med_cvc]='2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_cvc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_cvc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_cvc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_cvc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_cvc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_cvc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_cvc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_cvc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_cvc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_cvc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_cvc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_cvc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_cvc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_cvc_barrier__5	Training	6	med_cvc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_cvc_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_cvc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_cvc_barrier__9	Other
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753	med_cvc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_cvc_barrier(9)]=1'	Please specify	text																											
754	med_give_ivf	Administration of IV fluids	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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755	med_give_ivf_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_give_ivf]='1' or [med_give_ivf]='2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_give_ivf_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_give_ivf_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_give_ivf_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_give_ivf_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_give_ivf_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_give_ivf_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_give_ivf_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_give_ivf_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_give_ivf_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_give_ivf_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_give_ivf_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_give_ivf_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_give_ivf_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_give_ivf_barrier__5	Training	6	med_give_ivf_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_give_ivf_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_give_ivf_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_give_ivf_barrier__9	Other
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756	med_give_ivf_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_give_ivf_barrier(9)]=1'	Please specify	text																											
757	med_foley	Place urinary catheter	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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758	med_foley_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_foley]='1' or [med_foley]='2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_foley_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_foley_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_foley_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_foley_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_foley_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_foley_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_foley_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_foley_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_foley_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_foley_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_foley_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_foley_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_foley_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_foley_barrier__5	Training	6	med_foley_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_foley_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_foley_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_foley_barrier__9	Other
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759	med_foley_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_foley_barrier(9)]=1'	Please specify	text																											

760	med_exctrl_bleed	Section Header: <i>Control of Bleeding</i> External control of haemorrhage	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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761	med_exctrl_bleed_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_exctrl_bleed] = '1' or [med_exctrl_bleed] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__5	Training	6	med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_exctrl_bleed_barrier__9	Other
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762	med_exctrl_bleed_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_exctrl_bleed_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
763	med_pack	Perform packing and/or suture control	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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764	med_pack_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_pack] = '1' or [med_pack] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_pack_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_pack_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_pack_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_pack_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_pack_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_pack_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_pack_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_pack_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_pack_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_pack_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_pack_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_pack_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_pack_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_pack_barrier__5	Training	6	med_pack_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_pack_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_pack_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_pack_barrier__9	Other
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765	med_pack_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_pack_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											
766	med_tourniquet	Apply arterial tourniquet	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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767	med_tourniquet_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_tourniquet] = '1' or [med_tourniquet] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_tourniquet_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_tourniquet_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_tourniquet_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_tourniquet_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_tourniquet_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_tourniquet_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_tourniquet_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_tourniquet_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_tourniquet_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_tourniquet_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_tourniquet_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_tourniquet_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_tourniquet_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_tourniquet_barrier__5	Training	6	med_tourniquet_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_tourniquet_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_tourniquet_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_tourniquet_barrier__9	Other
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768	med_tourniquet_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_tourniquet_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
769	med_pelvicbind	Apply pelvic binding or sheeting	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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770	med_pelvicbind_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_pelvicbind] = '1' or [med_pelvicbind] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_pelvicbind_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_pelvicbind_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_pelvicbind_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_pelvicbind_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_pelvicbind_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_pelvicbind_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_pelvicbind_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_pelvicbind_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_pelvicbind_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_pelvicbind_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_pelvicbind_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_pelvicbind_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_pelvicbind_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_pelvicbind_barrier__5	Training	6	med_pelvicbind_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_pelvicbind_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_pelvicbind_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_pelvicbind_barrier__9	Other
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771	med_pelvicbind_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_pelvicbind_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
772	med_transfuse	Ability to perform safe transfusion (including protocols for appropriate ratios for massive transfusion)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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773	med_transfuse_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfuse] = '1' or [med_transfuse] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_transfuse_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_transfuse_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_transfuse_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_transfuse_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_transfuse_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_transfuse_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_transfuse_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_transfuse_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_transfuse_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_transfuse_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_transfuse_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_transfuse_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_transfuse_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_transfuse_barrier__5	Training	6	med_transfuse_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_transfuse_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_transfuse_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_transfuse_barrier__9	Other
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774	med_transfuse_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_transfuse_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
775	med_pocus	Perform and interpret point of care ultrasound	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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776	med_pocus_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_pocus] = '1' or [med_pocus] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_pocus_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_pocus_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_pocus_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_pocus_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_pocus_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_pocus_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_pocus_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_pocus_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_pocus_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_pocus_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_pocus_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_pocus_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_pocus_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_pocus_barrier__5	Training	6	med_pocus_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_pocus_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_pocus_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_pocus_barrier__9	Other
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777	med_pocus_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_pocus_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
778	med_ecg	Section Header: <i>Cardiac Interventions</i> Perform and interpret ECG	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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779	med_ecg_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_ecg] = '1' or [med_ecg] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_ecg_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_ecg_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_ecg_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_ecg_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_ecg_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_ecg_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_ecg_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_ecg_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_ecg_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_ecg_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_ecg_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_ecg_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_ecg_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_ecg_barrier__5	Training	6	med_ecg_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_ecg_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_ecg_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_ecg_barrier__9	Other
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780	med_ecg_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ecg_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
781	med_asa	Administer aspirin for ischemia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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782	med_asa_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_asa] = '1' or [med_asa] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_asa_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_asa_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_asa_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_asa_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_asa_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_asa_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_asa_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_asa_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_asa_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_asa_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_asa_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_asa_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_asa_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_asa_barrier__5	Training	6	med_asa_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_asa_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_asa_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_asa_barrier__9	Other
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783	med_asa_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_asa_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
784	med_defib	Perform external defibrillation and/or cardioversion	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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785	med_defib_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_defib] = '1' or [med_defib] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_defib_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_defib_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_defib_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_defib_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_defib_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_defib_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_defib_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_defib_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_defib_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_defib_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_defib_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_defib_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_defib_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_defib_barrier__5	Training	6	med_defib_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_defib_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_defib_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_defib_barrier__9	Other
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786	med_defib_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_defib_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
787	med_epi	Administration of adrenaline	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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788	med_epi_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_epi] = '1' or [med_epi] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_epi_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_epi_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_epi_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_epi_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_epi_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_epi_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_epi_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_epi_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_epi_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_epi_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_epi_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_epi_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_epi_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_epi_barrier__5	Training	6	med_epi_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_epi_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_epi_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_epi_barrier__9	Other
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789	med_epi_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_epi_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

790	med_inotrope	Administer inotropes <i>Examples of inotropes: digoxin, milrinone, dobutamine</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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791	med_inotrope_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_inotrope] = '1' or [med_inotrope] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_inotrope_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_inotrope_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_inotrope_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_inotrope_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_inotrope_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_inotrope_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_inotrope_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_inotrope_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_inotrope_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_inotrope_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_inotrope_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_inotrope_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_inotrope_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_inotrope_barrier__5	Training	6	med_inotrope_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_inotrope_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_inotrope_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_inotrope_barrier__9	Other
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792	med_inotrope_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_inotrope_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
793	med_rhythm	Administer anti-arrythmics <i>Anti-arrythmics include amiodarone, lidocaine, flecainide, procainamide</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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794	med_rhythm_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_rhythm] = '1' or [med_rhythm] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_rhythm_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_rhythm_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_rhythm_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_rhythm_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_rhythm_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_rhythm_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_rhythm_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_rhythm_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_rhythm_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_rhythm_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_rhythm_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_rhythm_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_rhythm_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_rhythm_barrier__5	Training	6	med_rhythm_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_rhythm_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_rhythm_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_rhythm_barrier__9	Other
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795	med_rhythm_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_rhythm_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
796	med_lytics	Administration of thrombolytics <i>Thrombolytics include alteplase, urokinase, streptokinase, tenecteplase. They DO NOT include enoxaparin, heparin, warfarin</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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797	med_lytics_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_lytics] = '1' or [med_lytics] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_lytics_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_lytics_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_lytics_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_lytics_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_lytics_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_lytics_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_lytics_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_lytics_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_lytics_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_lytics_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_lytics_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_lytics_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_lytics_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_lytics_barrier__5	Training	6	med_lytics_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_lytics_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_lytics_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_lytics_barrier__9	Other
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798	med_lytics_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_lytics_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
799	med_tamponade	Perform pericardiocentesis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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800	med_tamponade_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_tamponade] = '1' or [med_tamponade] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_tamponade_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_tamponade_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_tamponade_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_tamponade_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_tamponade_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_tamponade_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_tamponade_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_tamponade_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_tamponade_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_tamponade_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_tamponade_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_tamponade_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_tamponade_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_tamponade_barrier__5	Training	6	med_tamponade_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_tamponade_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_tamponade_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_tamponade_barrier__9	Other
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801	med_tamponade_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_tamponade_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
802	med_prcttams	Section Header: <i>Unconscious Patient</i> Protect unconscious patient from secondary injury	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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803	med_prcttams_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_prcttams] = '1' or [med_prcttams] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_prcttams_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_prcttams_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_prcttams_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_prcttams_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_prcttams_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_prcttams_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_prcttams_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_prcttams_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_prcttams_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_prcttams_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_prcttams_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_prcttams_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_prcttams_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_prcttams_barrier__5	Training	6	med_prcttams_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_prcttams_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_prcttams_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_prcttams_barrier__9	Other
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804	med_prcttams_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_prcttams_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

805	med_hypoglyc	Check and/or administer glucose	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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806	med_hypoglyc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_hypoglyc] = '1' or [med_hypoglyc] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_hypoglyc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_hypoglyc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_hypoglyc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_hypoglyc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_hypoglyc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_hypoglyc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_hypoglyc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_hypoglyc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_hypoglyc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_hypoglyc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_hypoglyc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_hypoglyc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_hypoglyc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_hypoglyc_barrier__5	Training	6	med_hypoglyc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_hypoglyc_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_hypoglyc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_hypoglyc_barrier__9	Other
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807	med_hypoglyc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_hypoglyc_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
808	med_insulin	Administer insulin for hyperglycemia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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809	med_insulin_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_insulin]= '1' or [med_insulin] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_insulin_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_insulin_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_insulin_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_insulin_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_insulin_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_insulin_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_insulin_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_insulin_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_insulin_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_insulin_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_insulin_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_insulin_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_insulin_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_insulin_barrier__5	Training	6	med_insulin_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_insulin_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_insulin_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_insulin_barrier__9	Other
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810	med_insulin_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_insulin_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
811	med_lp	Perform lumbar puncture	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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812	med_lp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_lp] = '1' or [med_lp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_lp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_lp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_lp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_lp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_lp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_lp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_lp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_lp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_lp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_lp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_lp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_lp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_lp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_lp_barrier__5	Training	6	med_lp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_lp_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_lp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_lp_barrier__9	Other
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813	med_lp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_lp_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
814	med_benzo	Section Header: <i>Seizure</i> Administer benzodiazepine	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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815	med_benzo_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_benzo] = '1' or [med_benzo] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_benzo_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_benzo_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_benzo_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_benzo_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_benzo_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_benzo_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_benzo_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_benzo_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_benzo_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_benzo_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_benzo_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_benzo_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_benzo_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_benzo_barrier__5	Training	6	med_benzo_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_benzo_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_benzo_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_benzo_barrier__9	Other
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816	med_benzo_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_benzo_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
817	med_ecclamp	Administer IV magnesium for pregnant patient	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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818	med_ecclamp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_ecclamp] = '1' or [med_ecclamp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_ecclamp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_ecclamp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_ecclamp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_ecclamp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_ecclamp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_ecclamp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_ecclamp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_ecclamp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_ecclamp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_ecclamp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_ecclamp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_ecclamp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_ecclamp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_ecclamp_barrier__5	Training	6	med_ecclamp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_ecclamp_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_ecclamp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_ecclamp_barrier__9	Other
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819	med_ecclamp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ecclamp_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

820	med_antidote	Administer locally appropriate antidote	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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821	med_antidote_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_antidote] = '1' or [med_antidote] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_antidote_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_antidote_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_antidote_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_antidote_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_antidote_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_antidote_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_antidote_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_antidote_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_antidote_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_antidote_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_antidote_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_antidote_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_antidote_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_antidote_barrier__5	Training	6	med_antidote_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_antidote_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_antidote_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_antidote_barrier__9	Other
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822	med_antidote_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_antidote_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
823	med_mse	Section Header: <i>Other Neurologic Interventions</i> Perform mental status exam	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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824	med_mse_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_mse] = '1' or [med_mse] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_mse_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_mse_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_mse_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_mse_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_mse_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_mse_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_mse_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_mse_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_mse_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_mse_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_mse_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_mse_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_mse_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_mse_barrier__5	Training	6	med_mse_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_mse_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_mse_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_mse_barrier__9	Other
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825	med_mse_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_mse_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
826	med_thermia	Management of extreme temperatures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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827	med_thermia_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_thermia] = '1' or [med_thermia] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_thermia_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_thermia_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_thermia_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_thermia_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_thermia_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_thermia_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_thermia_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_thermia_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_thermia_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_thermia_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_thermia_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_thermia_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_thermia_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_thermia_barrier__5	Training	6	med_thermia_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_thermia_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_thermia_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_thermia_barrier__9	Other
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828	med_thermia_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_thermia_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
829	med_agitation	Administer appropriate therapeutics for agitation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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830	med_agitation_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_agitation] = '1' or [med_agitation] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_agitation_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_agitation_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_agitation_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_agitation_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_agitation_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_agitation_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_agitation_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_agitation_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_agitation_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_agitation_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_agitation_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_agitation_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_agitation_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_agitation_barrier__5	Training	6	med_agitation_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_agitation_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_agitation_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_agitation_barrier__9	Other
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831	med_agitation_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_agitation_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
832	med_restraint	Ability to provide physical restraints	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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833	med_restraint_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_restraint] = '1' or [med_restraint] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_restraint_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_restraint_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_restraint_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_restraint_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_restraint_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_restraint_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_restraint_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_restraint_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_restraint_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_restraint_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_restraint_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_restraint_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_restraint_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_restraint_barrier__5	Training	6	med_restraint_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_restraint_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_restraint_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_restraint_barrier__9	Other
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834	med_restraint_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_restraint_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

835	med_ivcs	Perform procedural sedation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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836	med_ivcs_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_ivcs] = '1' or [med_ivcs] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_ivcs_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_ivcs_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_ivcs_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_ivcs_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_ivcs_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_ivcs_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_ivcs_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_ivcs_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_ivcs_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_ivcs_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_ivcs_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_ivcs_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_ivcs_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_ivcs_barrier__5	Training	6	med_ivcs_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_ivcs_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_ivcs_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_ivcs_barrier__9	Other
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837	med_ivcs_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ivcs_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
838	med_giveabx	Section Header: <i>Sepsis Interventions</i> Administration of IV or IM antibiotics	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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839	med_giveabx_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_giveabx] = '1' or [med_giveabx] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_giveabx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_giveabx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_giveabx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_giveabx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_giveabx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_giveabx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_giveabx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_giveabx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_giveabx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_giveabx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_giveabx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_giveabx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_giveabx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_giveabx_barrier__5	Training	6	med_giveabx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_giveabx_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_giveabx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_giveabx_barrier__9	Other
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840	med_giveabx_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_giveabx_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
841	med_pressor	Administration of IV vasopressors <i>Vasopressors include: dopamine, epinephrine, norepinephrine, vasopressin, phenylephrine</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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842	med_pressor_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_pressor] = '1' or [med_pressor] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_pressor_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_pressor_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_pressor_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_pressor_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_pressor_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_pressor_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_pressor_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_pressor_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_pressor_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_pressor_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_pressor_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_pressor_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_pressor_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_pressor_barrier__5	Training	6	med_pressor_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_pressor_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_pressor_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_pressor_barrier__9	Other
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843	med_pressor_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_pressor_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
844	med_para	Perform diagnostic paracentesis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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845	med_para_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_para] = '1' or [med_para] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_para_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_para_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_para_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_para_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_para_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_para_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_para_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_para_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_para_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_para_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_para_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_para_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_para_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_para_barrier__5	Training	6	med_para_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_para_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_para_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_para_barrier__9	Other
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846	med_para_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_para_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
847	med_sourcectrl	Bedside minor surgical techniques for source control (e.g. abscess, empyema)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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848	med_sourcectrl_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_sourcectrl] = '1' or [med_sourcectrl] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_sourcectrl_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_sourcectrl_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_sourcectrl_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_sourcectrl_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_sourcectrl_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_sourcectrl_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_sourcectrl_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_sourcectrl_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_sourcectrl_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_sourcectrl_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_sourcectrl_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_sourcectrl_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_sourcectrl_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_sourcectrl_barrier__5	Training	6	med_sourcectrl_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_sourcectrl_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_sourcectrl_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_sourcectrl_barrier__9	Other
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849	med_sourcectrl_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_sourcectrl_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

850	med_woundcare	Section Header: <i>Trauma Interventions</i> Perform initial appropriate wound care	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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851	med_woundcare_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_woundcare] = '1' or [med_woundcare] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_woundcare_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_woundcare_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_woundcare_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_woundcare_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_woundcare_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_woundcare_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_woundcare_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_woundcare_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_woundcare_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_woundcare_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_woundcare_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_woundcare_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_woundcare_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_woundcare_barrier__5	Training	6	med_woundcare_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_woundcare_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_woundcare_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_woundcare_barrier__9	Other
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852	med_woundcare_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_woundcare_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
853	med_goc	Section Header: <i>End of Life Care</i> Communicate with patient and/or families, including sharing poor prognoses	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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854	med_goc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_goc] = '1' or [med_goc] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_goc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_goc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_goc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_goc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_goc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_goc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_goc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_goc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_goc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_goc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_goc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_goc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_goc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_goc_barrier__5	Training	6	med_goc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_goc_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_goc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_goc_barrier__9	Other
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855	med_goc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_goc_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											
856	med_cmo	De-escalate care (e.g. stop treatments or remove life support) for patients with poor prognoses based on the expressed goals and wishes of the patient or their families	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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857	med_cmo_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_cmo] = '1' or [med_cmo] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_cmo_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_cmo_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_cmo_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_cmo_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_cmo_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_cmo_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_cmo_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_cmo_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_cmo_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_cmo_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_cmo_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_cmo_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_cmo_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_cmo_barrier__5	Training	6	med_cmo_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_cmo_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_cmo_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_cmo_barrier__9	Other
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858	med_cmo_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_cmo_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
859	med_dvtppx	Section Header: <i>Critical Care</i> Administer DVT prophylaxis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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860	med_dvtppx_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_dvtppx] = '1' or [med_dvtppx] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_dvtppx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_dvtppx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_dvtppx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_dvtppx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_dvtppx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_dvtppx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_dvtppx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_dvtppx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_dvtppx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_dvtppx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_dvtppx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_dvtppx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_dvtppx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_dvtppx_barrier__5	Training	6	med_dvtppx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_dvtppx_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_dvtppx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_dvtppx_barrier__9	Other
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861	med_dvtppx_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_dvtppx_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
862	med_ten	Provide enteral nutrition	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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863	med_ten_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_ten] = '1' or [med_ten] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_ten_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_ten_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_ten_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_ten_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_ten_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_ten_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_ten_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_ten_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_ten_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_ten_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_ten_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_ten_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_ten_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_ten_barrier__5	Training	6	med_ten_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_ten_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_ten_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_ten_barrier__9	Other
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864	med_ten_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ten_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

865	med_antibiogrm	Monitoring of nosocomial infections and antimicrobial resistance patterns	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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866	med_antibiogrm_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_antibiogrm] = '1' or [med_antibiogrm] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_antibiogrm_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_antibiogrm_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_antibiogrm_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_antibiogrm_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_antibiogrm_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_antibiogrm_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_antibiogrm_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_antibiogrm_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_antibiogrm_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_antibiogrm_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_antibiogrm_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_antibiogrm_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_antibiogrm_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_antibiogrm_barrier__5	Training	6	med_antibiogrm_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_antibiogrm_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_antibiogrm_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_antibiogrm_barrier__9	Other
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867	med_antibiogrm_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_antibiogrm_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
868	med_ivsedate	Administer IV sedatives (e.g. benzodiazepine, propofol)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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869	med_ivsedate_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_ivsedate]= '1' or [med_ivsedate] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_ivsedate_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_ivsedate_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_ivsedate_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_ivsedate_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_ivsedate_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_ivsedate_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_ivsedate_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_ivsedate_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_ivsedate_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_ivsedate_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_ivsedate_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_ivsedate_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_ivsedate_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_ivsedate_barrier__5	Training	6	med_ivsedate_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_ivsedate_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_ivsedate_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_ivsedate_barrier__9	Other
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870	med_ivsedate_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ivsedate_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
871	med_ivopioid	Administer IV opioids	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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872	med_ivopioid_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_ivopioid] = '1' or [med_ivopioid] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_ivopioid_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_ivopioid_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_ivopioid_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_ivopioid_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_ivopioid_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_ivopioid_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_ivopioid_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_ivopioid_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_ivopioid_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_ivopioid_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_ivopioid_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_ivopioid_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_ivopioid_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_ivopioid_barrier__5	Training	6	med_ivopioid_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_ivopioid_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_ivopioid_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_ivopioid_barrier__9	Other
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873	med_ivopioid_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ivopioid_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
874	med_q4bmp	Frequently (at least every 4 hours) check electrolytes and adjust management based on results	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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875	med_q4bmp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_q4bmp] = '1' or [med_q4bmp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_q4bmp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_q4bmp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_q4bmp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_q4bmp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_q4bmp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_q4bmp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_q4bmp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_q4bmp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_q4bmp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_q4bmp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_q4bmp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_q4bmp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_q4bmp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_q4bmp_barrier__5	Training	6	med_q4bmp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_q4bmp_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_q4bmp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_q4bmp_barrier__9	Other
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876	med_q4bmp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_q4bmp_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
877	med_q4position	Regularly (at least every 4 hours) reposition patients to prevent pressure ulcers	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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878	med_q4position_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_q4position] = '1' or [med_q4position] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_q4position_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_q4position_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_q4position_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_q4position_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_q4position_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_q4position_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_q4position_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_q4position_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_q4position_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_q4position_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_q4position_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_q4position_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_q4position_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_q4position_barrier__5	Training	6	med_q4position_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_q4position_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_q4position_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_q4position_barrier__9	Other
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9	med_q4position_barrier__9	Other																												
879	med_q4position_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_q4position_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											

880	med_gippx	Administer stress ulcer prophylaxis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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881	med_gippx_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_gippx] = '1' or [med_gippx] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_gippx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_gippx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_gippx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_gippx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_gippx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_gippx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_gippx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_gippx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_gippx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_gippx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_gippx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_gippx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_gippx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_gippx_barrier__5	Training	6	med_gippx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_gippx_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_gippx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_gippx_barrier__9	Other
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9	med_gippx_barrier__9	Other																												
882	med_gippx_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_gippx_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
883	med_cc_idsick	Section Header: <i>Medical Ward F. Critical Care</i> Is there a standardized method (e.g. protocol/checklist) for identifying critically ill patients on your ward?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 159</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
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-1	Don't know																													
884	med_cc_idsick_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_cc_idsick] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
885	med_cc_diff	Compared to other patients in the ward, what is different about the way you take care of critically ill patients? <i>Read options, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_cc_diff__1</td><td>Nurse to patient ratios</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_cc_diff__2</td><td>Type of nursing care</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_cc_diff__3</td><td>Training level of provders</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_cc_diff__4</td><td>Monitoring equipment</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_cc_diff__5</td><td>Frequency of vital signs</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_cc_diff__6</td><td>Capabilities for advanced interventions</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_cc_diff__7</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>med_cc_diff__0</td><td>No difference</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>med_cc_diff__1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 160</p>	1	med_cc_diff__1	Nurse to patient ratios	2	med_cc_diff__2	Type of nursing care	3	med_cc_diff__3	Training level of provders	4	med_cc_diff__4	Monitoring equipment	5	med_cc_diff__5	Frequency of vital signs	6	med_cc_diff__6	Capabilities for advanced interventions	7	med_cc_diff__7	Other	0	med_cc_diff__0	No difference	-1	med_cc_diff__1	Don't know
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7	med_cc_diff__7	Other																												
0	med_cc_diff__0	No difference																												
-1	med_cc_diff__1	Don't know																												
886	med_cc_diff_rn_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_cc_diff(2)] = '1'	Please specify how type of nursing care is different for critically ill patients	text																											
887	med_cc_diff_train_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_cc_diff(3)] = '1'	Please specify how training level of providers is different for critically ill patients	text																											
888	med_cc_diff equip_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_cc_diff(4)] = '1'	Please specify how monitoring equipment is different for critically ill patients	text																											
889	med_cc_diff_adv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_cc_diff(6)] = '1'	Please specify how capabilities for advanced interventions is different for critically ill patients	text																											

890	med_cc_diff_other_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_cc_diff(7)] = '1'	Please specify what other things are different about the way you take care of critically ill patients	text																								
891	med_cc_space	Is there an area in your ward preferentially used for critically ill patients?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 161</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																		
0	No																										
1	Yes																										
-1	Don't know																										
892	med_cc_beds	How many dedicated beds are there on your ward for critically ill patients?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 100000)																								
893	med_cc_census	How many critically ill patients are on the ward today? <i>This includes any patients deliberately placed in designated beds for critically ill patients as well as any other critically ill patients in other beds</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 100000) Question number: 162																								
894	med_cc_admit_policy Show the field ONLY if: [med_cc_space] = '1'	Is there a formal written policy outlining the criteria for placing a patient in this area on your ward	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 163</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																		
0	No																										
1	Yes																										
-1	Don't know																										
895	med_cc_admit_role Show the field ONLY if: [med_cc_space] = '1'	Who makes the decision to place a patient there? <i>do not read, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_cc_admit_role__1</td><td>Doctor</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_cc_admit_role__2</td><td>Nurse</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_cc_admit_role__3</td><td>Clinical officer</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_cc_admit_role__4</td><td>Medical assistant</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_cc_admit_role__5</td><td>Administrator</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_cc_admit_role__6</td><td>Patient or patient family</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_cc_admit_role__7</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>med_cc_admit_role__1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 164</p>	1	med_cc_admit_role__1	Doctor	2	med_cc_admit_role__2	Nurse	3	med_cc_admit_role__3	Clinical officer	4	med_cc_admit_role__4	Medical assistant	5	med_cc_admit_role__5	Administrator	6	med_cc_admit_role__6	Patient or patient family	7	med_cc_admit_role__7	Other	-1	med_cc_admit_role__1	Don't know
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896	med_cc_admit_role_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_cc_admit_role(7)] = '1'	Please specify	text																								
897	med_vitals_how	How are vital signs checked on patients on your ward? <i>read choices, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_vitals_how__1</td><td>Manual BP cuff</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_vitals_how__2</td><td>Automatic BP cuff</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_vitals_how__3</td><td>Intermittent pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_vitals_how__4</td><td>Continuous pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_vitals_how__5</td><td>Continuous cardiac monitor</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_vitals_how__6</td><td>Invasive monitoring (e.g. arterial line)</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_vitals_how__7</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>med_vitals_how__1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 165</p>	1	med_vitals_how__1	Manual BP cuff	2	med_vitals_how__2	Automatic BP cuff	3	med_vitals_how__3	Intermittent pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)	4	med_vitals_how__4	Continuous pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)	5	med_vitals_how__5	Continuous cardiac monitor	6	med_vitals_how__6	Invasive monitoring (e.g. arterial line)	7	med_vitals_how__7	Other	-1	med_vitals_how__1	Don't know
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898	med_vitals_how_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_vitals_how(7)] = '1'	Please specify	text																								
899	med_vitals_recheck_freq	How often (in hours) are vital signs checked on stable patients on the ward? <i>enter -1 for unsure and -2 if not checked at regular intervals</i>	text Question number: 166																								

900	med_ccvitals_recheck_freq Show the field ONLY if: [med_cc_diff(5)] = '1'	How often (in hours) are vital signs checked on critically ill patients on the ward? <i>enter -1 for unsure and -2 if not checked at regular intervals</i>	text Question number: 167												
901	med_cc_reassessed	Are critically ill patients on the ward reassessed at least twice a day by a clinician who can change the treatment plan if needed?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
902	med_seen_dka	Section Header: <i>Have you seen > 5 patients over the past 3 months in the medical ward with each of the following?</i> Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 169	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
903	med_seen_seizures	Seizures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
904	med_seen_poisoning	Poisoning	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
905	med_seen_chf	Severe heart failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
906	med_seen_arf	Severe renal failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
907	med_seen_respiratory	Respiratory distress or respiratory failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
908	med_seen_shock	Low blood pressure or shock	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
909	med_seen_ams	Coma (altered mental status or decreased level of consciousness)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
910	med_seen_stroke	Suspected stroke	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														

911	med_seen_head_trauma	Severe head trauma	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
912	med_seen_open_frac	Open fracture	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
913	med_seen_closed_frac	Closed long bone fracture (e.g. femur)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
914	med_seen_other_trauma	Other trauma	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
915	med_seen_obstructed_labor	Obstructed labor	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
916	med_seen_pph	Post-partum hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
917	med_learn_dka	Section Header: <i>Have you received training in the past year on the following conditions:</i> Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 170
918	med_learn_seizures	Seizures	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
919	med_learn_poisoning	Poisoning	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
920	med_learn_chf	Severe heart failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
921	med_learn_arf	Severe renal failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know

922	med_learn_respiratory	Respiratory distress or respiratory failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
923	med_learn_shock	Low blood pressure or shock	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
924	med_learn_ams	Coma (altered mental status or decreased level of consciousness)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
925	med_learn_stroke	Suspected stroke	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
926	med_learn_head_trauma	Severe head trauma	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
927	med_learn_open_frac	Open fracture	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
928	med_learn_closed_frac	Closed long bone fracture (e.g. femur)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
929	med_learn_other_trauma	Other trauma	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
930	med_learn_obstructed_labor	Obstructed labor	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
931	med_learn_pph	Post-partum hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
932	med_has_water	Section Header: <i>Medical WardG. Infrastructure and Essential Equipment Rate availability of each item 1 to 31) Generally unavailable 2) Some availability3) Adequate availability If "don't know", enter -1 Provide comment if rating < 3</i> Clean, running water	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 174	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										

933	med_has_water_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_has_water] = '1' or [med_has_water] = '2'	Please comment	text								
934	med_has_electric	Electricity source (e.g. wired, generator)	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 175	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
935	med_has_electric_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_has_electric] = '1' or [med_has_electric] = '2'	Please comment	text								
936	med_paper_chart	Paper-based chart	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 177	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
937	med_paper_chart_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_paper_chart] = '1' or [med_paper_chart] = '2'	Please comment	text								
938	med_elec_chart	Electronic chart	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 178	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
939	med_elec_chart_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_elec_chart] = '1' or [med_elec_chart] = '2'	Please comment	text								
940	med_iso_room	Isolation room for infectious diseases (e.g. TB, haemorrhagic fever)	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 179	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
941	med_iso_room_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_iso_room] = '1' or [med_iso_room] = '2'	Please comment	text								

942	med_ecg_monitor	Electronic cardiac monitoring in the ward	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 183</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
943	med_ecg_monitor_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ecg_monitor] = '1' or [med_ecg_monitor] = '2'	Please comment	text								
944	med_codecart	Crash trolley or code cart with high-acuity equipment and supplies of various sizes in ward	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 184</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
945	med_codecart_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_codecart] = '1' or [med_codecart] = '2'	Please comment	text								
946	med_storage	Is there access to storage space within (or with immediate proximity to) the ward, including secure storage for controlled substances?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 187</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
947	med_storage_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_storage] = '1' or [med_storage] = '2'	Please comment	text								
948	med_toilet	Access to toilet facilities for patients and staff	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 189</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
949	med_toilet_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_toilet] = '1' or [med_toilet] = '2'	Please comment	text								
950	med_handwash	Access to handwashing facilities in each patient care area	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 190</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										

951	med_handwash_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_handwash] = '1' or [med_handwash] = '2'	Please comment	text								
952	med_inventory Show the field ONLY if: [med_inventory] = '1' or [med_inventory] = '2'	System for stocking, managing, and dispensing medications in the ward	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 191</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
953	med_inventory_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_inventory] = '1' or [med_inventory] = '2'	Please comment	text								
954	med_has_o2 Show the field ONLY if: [med_has_o2] = '1' or [med_has_o2] = '2'	Oxygen in the ward	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 192</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
955	med_has_o2_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_has_o2] = '1' or [med_has_o2] = '2'	Please comment	text Question number: 193								
956	med_o2_piped Show the field ONLY if: [med_has_o2] = '2' or [med_has_o2] = '3'	Section Header: <i>Which of the following methods supply oxygen in the medical ward?</i> Central piped system	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
957	med_o2_cnctr Show the field ONLY if: [med_has_o2] = '2' or [med_has_o2] = '3'	Oxygen concentrator stored in the ward	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
958	med_o2_tanks Show the field ONLY if: [med_has_o2] = '2' or [med_has_o2] = '3'	Tanks that are stored in the ward	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
959	med_o2_central_tank Show the field ONLY if: [med_has_o2] = '2' or [med_has_o2] = '3'	Call for tank from central location if needed	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
960	med_o2_central_cnctr Show the field ONLY if: [med_has_o2] = '2' or [med_has_o2] = '3'	Call for oxygen from concentrator from central location if needed	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										

961	med_protec_eye	Section Header: <i>Which of the following personal protective equipment is available in the medical ward?</i> Eye protection	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 194</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
962	med_protec_n95	N-95 mask	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
963	med_protec_gown	Gowns	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
964	med_protec_glove	Gloves	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
965	med_drwblood	Section Header: <i>Medical Ward Diagnostic Services Please rate the availability of each item 1 to 3 1 - Generally unavailable 2 - Some availability 3 - Adequate availability Note: If "don't know", enter -1 For rating < 3, mark all relevant barriers: Infrastructure Absent Equipment Broken Equipment Stock Out (Supplies) Training Personnel User Fees Opening Hours Other</i> Blood draw for laboratory testing in ward (as opposed to central lab)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
1	Generally Unavailable																													
2	Some Availability																													
3	Adequate Availability																													
-1	Don't know																													
966	med_drwblood_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_drwblood] = '1' or [med_drwblood] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_drwblood_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_drwblood_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_drwblood_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_drwblood_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_drwblood_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_drwblood_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_drwblood_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_drwblood_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_drwblood_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_drwblood_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_drwblood_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_drwblood_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_drwblood_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_drwblood_barrier__5	Training	6	med_drwblood_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_drwblood_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_drwblood_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_drwblood_barrier__9	Other
1	med_drwblood_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
2	med_drwblood_barrier__2	Absent equip																												
3	med_drwblood_barrier__3	Broken equip																												
4	med_drwblood_barrier__4	Stock out																												
5	med_drwblood_barrier__5	Training																												
6	med_drwblood_barrier__6	Prsnnl.																												
7	med_drwblood_barrier__7	User fees																												
8	med_drwblood_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	med_drwblood_barrier__9	Other																												
967	med_drwblood_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_drwblood_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
968	med_hgb	Hemoglobin	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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969	med_hgb_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_hgb] = '1' or [med_hgb] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_hgb_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_hgb_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_hgb_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_hgb_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_hgb_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_hgb_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_hgb_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_hgb_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_hgb_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_hgb_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_hgb_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_hgb_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_hgb_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_hgb_barrier__5	Training	6	med_hgb_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_hgb_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_hgb_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_hgb_barrier__9	Other
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9	med_hgb_barrier__9	Other																												
970	med_hgb_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_hgb_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
971	med_fbc	Full blood count	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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972	med_fbc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_fbc] = '1' or [med_fbc] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_fbc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_fbc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_fbc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_fbc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_fbc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_fbc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_fbc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_fbc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_fbc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_fbc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_fbc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_fbc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_fbc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_fbc_barrier__5	Training	6	med_fbc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_fbc_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_fbc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_fbc_barrier__9	Other
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973	med_fbc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_fbc_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
974	med_ptinr	Coagulation profile (PT/PTT, INR)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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975	med_ptinr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_ptinr] = '1' or [med_ptinr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_ptinr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_ptinr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_ptinr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_ptinr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_ptinr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_ptinr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_ptinr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_ptinr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_ptinr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_ptinr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_ptinr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_ptinr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_ptinr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_ptinr_barrier__5	Training	6	med_ptinr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_ptinr_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_ptinr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_ptinr_barrier__9	Other
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976	med_ptinr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ptinr_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

977	med_electrolyte	Electrolytes	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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978	med_electrolyte_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_electrolyte] = '1' or [med_electrolyte] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_electrolyte_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_electrolyte_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_electrolyte_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_electrolyte_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_electrolyte_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_electrolyte_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_electrolyte_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_electrolyte_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_electrolyte_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_electrolyte_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_electrolyte_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_electrolyte_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_electrolyte_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_electrolyte_barrier__5	Training	6	med_electrolyte_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_electrolyte_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_electrolyte_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_electrolyte_barrier__9	Other
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979	med_electrolyte_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_electrolyte_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
980	med_buncr	BUN and creatinine	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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981	med_buncr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_buncr]= '1' or [med_buncr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_buncr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_buncr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_buncr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_buncr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_buncr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_buncr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_buncr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_buncr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_buncr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_buncr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_buncr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_buncr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_buncr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_buncr_barrier__5	Training	6	med_buncr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_buncr_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_buncr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_buncr_barrier__9	Other
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982	med_buncr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_buncr_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											
983	med_lipase	Lipase	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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984	med_lipase_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_lipase] = '1' or [med_lipase] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_lipase_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_lipase_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_lipase_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_lipase_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_lipase_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_lipase_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_lipase_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_lipase_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_lipase_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_lipase_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_lipase_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_lipase_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_lipase_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_lipase_barrier__5	Training	6	med_lipase_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_lipase_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_lipase_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_lipase_barrier__9	Other
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985	med_lipase_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_lipase_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
986	med_trop	Cardiac marker (e.g. troponin)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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987	med_trop_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_trop] = '1' or [med_trop] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_trop_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_trop_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_trop_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_trop_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_trop_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_trop_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_trop_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_trop_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_trop_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_trop_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_trop_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_trop_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_trop_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_trop_barrier__5	Training	6	med_trop_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_trop_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_trop_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_trop_barrier__9	Other
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988	med_trop_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_trop_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
989	med_abg	Arterial blood gas	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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990	med_abg_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_abg] = '1' or [med_abg] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_abg_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_abg_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_abg_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_abg_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_abg_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_abg_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_abg_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_abg_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_abg_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_abg_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_abg_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_abg_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_abg_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_abg_barrier__5	Training	6	med_abg_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_abg_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_abg_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_abg_barrier__9	Other
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991	med_abg_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_abg_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

992	med_typescrn	Cross matching for blood and blood products	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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993	med_typescrn_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_typescrn] = '1' or [med_typescrn] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_typescrn_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_typescrn_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_typescrn_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_typescrn_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_typescrn_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_typescrn_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_typescrn_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_typescrn_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_typescrn_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_typescrn_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_typescrn_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_typescrn_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_typescrn_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_typescrn_barrier__5	Training	6	med_typescrn_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_typescrn_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_typescrn_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_typescrn_barrier__9	Other
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8	med_typescrn_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	med_typescrn_barrier__9	Other																												
994	med_typescrn_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_typescrn_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
995	med_bcxsensi	Blood cultures and sensitivities	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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996	med_bcxsensi_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_bcxsensi] = '1' or [med_bcxsensi] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_bcxsensi_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_bcxsensi_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_bcxsensi_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_bcxsensi_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_bcxsensi_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_bcxsensi_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_bcxsensi_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_bcxsensi_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_bcxsensi_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_bcxsensi_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_bcxsensi_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_bcxsensi_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_bcxsensi_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_bcxsensi_barrier__5	Training	6	med_bcxsensi_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_bcxsensi_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_bcxsensi_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_bcxsensi_barrier__9	Other
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997	med_bcxsensi_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_bcxsensi_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
998	med_sterilesamp	Capacity to obtain sterile blood samples for lab testing	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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999	med_sterilesamp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_sterilesamp] = '1' or [med_sterilesamp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_sterilesamp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_sterilesamp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_sterilesamp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_sterilesamp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_sterilesamp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_sterilesamp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_sterilesamp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_sterilesamp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_sterilesamp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_sterilesamp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_sterilesamp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_sterilesamp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_sterilesamp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_sterilesamp_barrier__5	Training	6	med_sterilesamp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_sterilesamp_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_sterilesamp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_sterilesamp_barrier__9	Other
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1000	med_sterilesamp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_sterilesamp_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1001	med_reportlab	System for reporting lab results in a timely fashion	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1002	med_reportlab_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_reportlab] = '1' or [med_reportlab] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_reportlab_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_reportlab_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_reportlab_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_reportlab_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_reportlab_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_reportlab_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_reportlab_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_reportlab_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_reportlab_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_reportlab_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_reportlab_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_reportlab_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_reportlab_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_reportlab_barrier__5	Training	6	med_reportlab_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_reportlab_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_reportlab_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_reportlab_barrier__9	Other
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1003	med_reportlab_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_reportlab_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											
1004	med_udip	Urine dipstick	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1005	med_udip_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_udip] = '1' or [med_udip] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_udip_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_udip_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_udip_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_udip_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_udip_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_udip_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_udip_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_udip_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_udip_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_udip_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_udip_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_udip_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_udip_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_udip_barrier__5	Training	6	med_udip_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_udip_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_udip_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_udip_barrier__9	Other
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1006	med_udip_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_udip_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											

1007	med_uhcg	Urine pregnancy	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1008	med_uhcg_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_uhcg] = '1' or [med_uhcg] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_uhcg_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_uhcg_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_uhcg_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_uhcg_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_uhcg_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_uhcg_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_uhcg_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_uhcg_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_uhcg_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_uhcg_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_uhcg_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_uhcg_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_uhcg_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_uhcg_barrier__5	Training	6	med_uhcg_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_uhcg_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_uhcg_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_uhcg_barrier__9	Other
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1009	med_uhcg_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_uhcg_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1010	med_glucose	Glucose	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1011	med_glucose_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_glucose] = '1' or [med_glucose] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_glucose_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_glucose_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_glucose_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_glucose_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_glucose_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_glucose_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_glucose_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_glucose_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_glucose_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_glucose_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_glucose_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_glucose_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_glucose_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_glucose_barrier__5	Training	6	med_glucose_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_glucose_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_glucose_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_glucose_barrier__9	Other
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1012	med_glucose_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_glucose_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1013	med_rdt	Malaria Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1014	med_rdt_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_rdt] = '1' or [med_rdt] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_rdt_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_rdt_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_rdt_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_rdt_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_rdt_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_rdt_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_rdt_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_rdt_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_rdt_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_rdt_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_rdt_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_rdt_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_rdt_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_rdt_barrier__5	Training	6	med_rdt_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_rdt_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_rdt_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_rdt_barrier__9	Other
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1015	med_rdt_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_rdt_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1016	med_malariasmr	Malaria smear/microscopy	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1017	med_malariasmr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_malariasmr] = '1' or [med_malariasmr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_malariasmr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_malariasmr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_malariasmr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_malariasmr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_malariasmr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_malariasmr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_malariasmr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_malariasmr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_malariasmr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_malariasmr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_malariasmr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_malariasmr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_malariasmr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_malariasmr_barrier__5	Training	6	med_malariasmr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_malariasmr_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_malariasmr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_malariasmr_barrier__9	Other
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1018	med_malariasmr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_malariasmr_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1019	med_rapidhiv	Rapid HIV testing	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1020	med_rapidhiv_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_rapidhiv] = '1' or [med_rapidhiv] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_rapidhiv_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_rapidhiv_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_rapidhiv_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_rapidhiv_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_rapidhiv_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_rapidhiv_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_rapidhiv_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_rapidhiv_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_rapidhiv_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_rapidhiv_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_rapidhiv_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_rapidhiv_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_rapidhiv_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_rapidhiv_barrier__5	Training	6	med_rapidhiv_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_rapidhiv_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_rapidhiv_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_rapidhiv_barrier__9	Other
1	med_rapidhiv_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
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9	med_rapidhiv_barrier__9	Other																												
1021	med_rapidhiv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_rapidhiv_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1022	med_nonportxr	Stationary X-ray	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1023	med_nonportxr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_nonportxr] = '1' or [med_nonportxr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_nonportxr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_nonportxr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_nonportxr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_nonportxr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_nonportxr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_nonportxr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_nonportxr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_nonportxr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_nonportxr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_nonportxr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_nonportxr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_nonportxr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_nonportxr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_nonportxr_barrier__5	Training	6	med_nonportxr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_nonportxr_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_nonportxr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_nonportxr_barrier__9	Other
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1024	med_nonportxr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_nonportxr_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1025	med_portxr	Portable X-ray for use in the ward	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1026	med_portxr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_portxr] = '1' or [med_portxr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_portxr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_portxr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_portxr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_portxr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_portxr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_portxr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_portxr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_portxr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_portxr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_portxr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_portxr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_portxr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_portxr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_portxr_barrier__5	Training	6	med_portxr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_portxr_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_portxr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_portxr_barrier__9	Other
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1027	med_portxr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_portxr_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											
1028	med_us_hosp	Ultrasound in the hospital	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1029	med_us_hosp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_us_hosp] = '1' or [med_us_hosp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_us_hosp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_us_hosp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_us_hosp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_us_hosp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_us_hosp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_us_hosp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_us_hosp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_us_hosp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_us_hosp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_us_hosp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_us_hosp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_us_hosp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_us_hosp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_us_hosp_barrier__5	Training	6	med_us_hosp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_us_hosp_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_us_hosp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_us_hosp_barrier__9	Other
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1030	med_us_hosp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_us_hosp_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1031	med_us_med	Ultrasound for use in ward	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1032	med_us_med_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_us_med] = '1' or [med_us_med] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_us_med_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_us_med_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_us_med_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_us_med_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_us_med_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_us_med_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_us_med_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_us_med_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_us_med_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_us_med_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_us_med_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_us_med_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_us_med_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_us_med_barrier__5	Training	6	med_us_med_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_us_med_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_us_med_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_us_med_barrier__9	Other
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1033	med_us_med_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_us_med_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1034	med_ct	CT scan	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1035	med_ct_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_ct] = '1' or [med_ct] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>med_ct_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>med_ct_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>med_ct_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>med_ct_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>med_ct_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>med_ct_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>med_ct_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>med_ct_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>med_ct_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	med_ct_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_ct_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_ct_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_ct_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_ct_barrier__5	Training	6	med_ct_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_ct_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_ct_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_ct_barrier__9	Other
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1036	med_ct_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_ct_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1037	med_systemrad	System for reporting radiology results in a timely fashion	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Generally Unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Some Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1038	med_systemrad_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [med_systemrad] = '1' or [med_systemrad] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>med_systemrad_barrier__1</td> <td>Infrastr.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>med_systemrad_barrier__2</td> <td>Absent equip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>med_systemrad_barrier__3</td> <td>Broken equip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>med_systemrad_barrier__4</td> <td>Stock out</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>med_systemrad_barrier__5</td> <td>Training</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>med_systemrad_barrier__6</td> <td>Prsnnl.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>med_systemrad_barrier__7</td> <td>User fees</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>med_systemrad_barrier__8</td> <td>Opening hours</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>med_systemrad_barrier__9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	med_systemrad_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	med_systemrad_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	med_systemrad_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	med_systemrad_barrier__4	Stock out	5	med_systemrad_barrier__5	Training	6	med_systemrad_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	med_systemrad_barrier__7	User fees	8	med_systemrad_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	med_systemrad_barrier__9	Other
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9	med_systemrad_barrier__9	Other																												
1039	med_systemrad_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_systemrad_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1040	med_rads_read	Who interprets radiology results? <i>read choices, choose all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>med_rads_read__1</td> <td>Provider</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>med_rads_read__2</td> <td>Radiologist</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>med_rads_read__3</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>med_rads_read__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 221</p>	1	med_rads_read__1	Provider	2	med_rads_read__2	Radiologist	3	med_rads_read__3	Other	-1	med_rads_read__1	Don't know															
1	med_rads_read__1	Provider																												
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1041	med_rads_read_spec Show the field ONLY if: [med_rads_read(3)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1042	clinician_med_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete																					
0	Incomplete																													
1	Unverified																													
2	Complete																													
Instrument: Clinician ICU (clinician_icu)			^ Collapse																											
1043	icu_record_id	Section Header: <i>INTENSIVE CARE UNIT/HIGH DEPENDENCY UNIT</i> Record ID	text (integer, Min: 0, Max: 1000000)																											
1044	icu_facility	Name of facility <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	text, Required																											
1045	icu_has_ed	Is there an ED in this hospital? <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes																							
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
1046	icu_clin_lead	Is this participant a clinical lead of the unit? <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes																							
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
1047	icu_date	Interview date and time (Day-Month-Year; 24 hour clock)	text (datetime_dmy)																											

1048	icu_where_work	<p>Section Header: <i>Intensive Care/High Dependency UnitA. Background Questions</i></p> <p>Where in the hospital do you primarily work?</p> <p><i>if the respondent works in multiple areas, ask them to choose the area they work in the most often</i></p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Outpatient Department (OPD)</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Emergency unit (ED)</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Inpatient ward</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>HDU/ICU</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 1</p>	1	Outpatient Department (OPD)	2	Emergency unit (ED)	3	Inpatient ward	4	HDU/ICU	5	Other
1	Outpatient Department (OPD)												
2	Emergency unit (ED)												
3	Inpatient ward												
4	HDU/ICU												
5	Other												
1049	icu_where_work_spec	<p>Please specify</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [icu_where_work] = '5' or [icu_where_work] = '3'</p>	<p>text</p>										
1050	icu_role	<p>What is your role?</p> <p><i>Read all choices</i></p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Doctor</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Nurse</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Clinical Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Medical Assistant</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 2</p>	1	Doctor	2	Nurse	3	Clinical Officer	4	Medical Assistant	5	Other
1	Doctor												
2	Nurse												
3	Clinical Officer												
4	Medical Assistant												
5	Other												
1051	icu_role_spec	<p>Please specify</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [icu_role] = '5'</p>	<p>text</p>										
1052	icu_days_at_icu	<p>How many days per week do you work in the this unit?</p> <p><i>This question refers to the HDU/ICU, even if they primarily work somewhere else, enter -1 if unknown</i></p>	<p>text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 7)</p> <p>Question number: 3</p>										
1053	icu_hours_prsnt	<p>Section Header: <i>Intensive Care/High Dependency UnitB. Hospital Structure/Staffing</i></p> <p>During which hours is the unit covered by providers who are physically present in the unit?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than 24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>The unit is never covered by providers who are physically present in the unit</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 4</p>	1	24 hours a day	2	Less than 24 hours a day	-1	Don't know	-2	The unit is never covered by providers who are physically present in the unit		
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1054	icu_hours_prsnt_start Show the field ONLY if: [icu_hours_prsnt] = '2'	Coverage starts at	<table border="1"><thead><tr><th colspan="2">dropdown</th></tr></thead><tbody><tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr><tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr><tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr><tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr><tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr><tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr><tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr><tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr><tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr><tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr><tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr><tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr><tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr><tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr><tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr><tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr><tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr><tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr><tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr><tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr><tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr><tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr><tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr><tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr></tbody></table>	dropdown		12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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1055	icu_hours_prsnt_stop Show the field ONLY if: [icu_hours_prsnt] = '2'	Coverage ends at	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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1056	icu_hours_in	During which hours is the unit covered by providers who are on call, inside the facility?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than 24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>The unit is never covered by providers who are on call, inside the facility</td></tr> </table> Question number: 5	1	24 hours a day	2	Less than 24 hours a day	-1	Don't know	-2	The unit is never covered by providers who are on call, inside the facility																																								
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1057	icu_hours_in_start Show the field ONLY if: [icu_hours_in] = '2'	Coverage starts at	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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<p>1058</p>	<p>icu_hours_in_stop</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [icu_hours_in] = '2'</p>	<p>Coverage ends at</p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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<p>1059</p>	<p>icu_hours_out</p>	<p>During which hours is the unit covered by providers who are on call, outside the facility?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than 24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>The unit is never covered by providers who are on call, outside the facility</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 6</p>	1	24 hours a day	2	Less than 24 hours a day	-1	Don't know	-2	The unit is never covered by providers who are on call, outside the facility																																								
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1061	icu_hours_out_stop Show the field ONLY if: [icu_hours_out] = '2'	Coverage ends at	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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1062	icu_rn_available	Are nurses available 24 hours a day, every day of the week for patients in your unit? <i>read all choices</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes, in the unit</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Yes, on call within the facility</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Yes, on call outside the facility</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 7</p>	0	No	1	Yes, in the unit	2	Yes, on call within the facility	3	Yes, on call outside the facility	-1	Don't know																																						
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1063	icu_beds	How many beds are on your unit? <i>enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000) Question number: 9																																																
1064	icu_corps Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Do you have a core of fixed (non-rotating) providers permanently assigned to the unit?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 11</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																																										
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1065	icu_nonrot_rn Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>What is the number of each of the following non-rotating providers in your unit?</i> Nurses	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)																																																
1066	icu_nonrot_rn_cert Show the field ONLY if: [icu_nonrot_rn] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)																																																
1067	icu_nonrot_app Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Mid-level provider or advance practice nurses (e.g. clinical officers)	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)																																																

1068	icu_nonrot_app_cert Show the field ONLY if: [icu_nonrot_app] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1069	icu_nonrot_mo Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Doctors without specialist training	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1070	icu_nonrot_mo_cert Show the field ONLY if: [icu_nonrot_mo] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1071	icu_nonrot_ccmd Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Critical care specialists	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1072	icu_nonrot_ccmd_cert Show the field ONLY if: [icu_nonrot_ccmd] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1073	icu_nonrot_othermd Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Other specialist doctor	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1074	icu_nonrot_othermd_cert Show the field ONLY if: [icu_nonrot_othermd] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1075	icu_rot_rn Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>What is the number of each of the following rotating providers in your unit?</i> Nurses	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1076	icu_rot_rn_cert Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rot_rn] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1077	icu_rot_app Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Mid-level provider or advance practice nurses (e.g. clinical officers)	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1078	icu_rot_app_cert Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rot_app] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1079	icu_rot_mo Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Doctors without specialist training	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1080	icu_rot_mo_cert Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rot_mo] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1081	icu_rot_ccmd Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Critical care specialists	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1082	icu_rot_ccmd_cert Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rot_ccmd] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1083	icu_rot_othermd Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Other specialist doctor	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1084	icu_rot_othermd_cert Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rot_othermd] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1085	icu_rn_avgday Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	How many nurses work in your unit on an average daytime shift? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to unit, enter -1 if unsure</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 14

1086	icu_rn_today Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	How many nurses are working in your unit today? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to unit, enter -1 if unsure</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 15						
1087	icu_rn_avgnight Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	How many nurses work in your unit on an average overnight shift? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to unit, enter -1 if unsure</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 16						
1088	icu_rn_lastnight Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	How many nurses worked in your unit last night? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to unit, enter -1 if unsure</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 17						
1089	icu_census Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	How many patients are currently in your unit? <i>enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 18						
1090	icu_obs_freq	What is the frequency of nurse observations for patients on your unit? <i>give answer in hours, enter -1 if unknown, enter -2 if no standard frequency</i>	text (number, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 19						
1091	icu_notify_change	If a nurse observes a clinical change, who does the nurse call? <i>enter -1 if don't know, enter 0 if nobody</i>	text Question number: 21						
1092	icu_rn_change	Can nurses initiate treatment without specific provider orders in response to an observed clinical change?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 22	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1093	icu_rn_change_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rn_change] = '1'	Please specify	text						
1094	icu_from_opded	Section Header: <i>Intensive Care/High Dependency UnitC. Transfers and Patient Flow</i> Does your unit admit patients directly from the ED/OPD?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 23	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1095	icu_sick_accept Show the field ONLY if: [icu_from_opded] = '1'	Are patients ever too sick (meaning unstable vital signs or requiring interventions or monitoring that are too frequent or prognosis is too poor) to be admitted to your unit and need to stay in the OPD/ED as a result?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 25	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1096	icu_sick_accept_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_sick_accept] = '1'	Please specify	text						
1097	icu_trans_ed Show the field ONLY if: [has_ed] = '1' or [icu_has_ed] = '1'	Does your unit transfer patients to the ED of this hospital?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 26	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1098	icu_trans_ed_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_trans_ed] = '1'	Please specify	text						

1099	icu_transfer_out	Does your unit transfer patients from the unit directly to other hospitals or health facilities?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 27</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
1100	icu_transfer_number Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Approximately how many patients were transferred out from your unit to other hospitals or health facilities in the last month? <i>Ask respondent to give best guess, for example, consider how many patients they personally have transferred and what % of the time they work. Enter -1 if unable to give best guess</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 28												
1101	icu_trans_dka Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Section Header: <i>For the following conditions, indicate how often patient with that condition is transferred out to another hospital. Please consider only patients who are actually transferred, not how often you feel a patient with this condition requires transfer.</i> Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 29</p>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1102	icu_trans_seizures Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Seizures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1103	icu_trans_poisoning Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Poisoning	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1104	icu_trans_chf Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Severe heart failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1105	icu_trans_arf Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Severe renal failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														

1106	icu_trans_respiratory Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Respiratory distress or respiratory failure	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
1107	icu_trans_shock Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Low blood pressure or shock	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
1108	icu_trans_ams Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Coma (altered mental status or decreased level of consciousness)	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
1109	icu_trans_stroke Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Suspected stroke	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
1110	icu_trans_head_trauma Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Severe head trauma	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
1111	icu_trans_open_frac Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Open fracture	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know

1112	icu_trans_closed_frac Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Closed long bone fracture (e.g. femur)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
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4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1113	icu_trans_other_trauma Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Other trauma	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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4	Frequently														
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-1	Don't know														
1114	icu_trans_obstructed_labor Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Obstructed labor	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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1115	icu_trans_pph Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	Post-partum hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
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3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1116	icu_ambulance Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	When patients are transferred from the unit to another hospital/healthcare facility, how often is it by ambulance?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 30</p>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														

1117	icu_trans_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	What, if any, barriers do you commonly encounter when transferring patients to another hospital/healthcare facility? <i>Do not read choices, select all that apply</i>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="3">checkbox</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>icu_trans_barrier__1</td> <td>Patient finances</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>icu_trans_barrier__2</td> <td>Availability of transportation</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>icu_trans_barrier__3</td> <td>Patient too sick to transfer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>icu_trans_barrier__4</td> <td>Bed space at accepting hospital</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>icu_trans_barrier__5</td> <td>Approval for transfer from accepting hospital</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>icu_trans_barrier__6</td> <td>Family objection</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>icu_trans_barrier__7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>icu_trans_barrier__0</td> <td>No barriers</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>icu_trans_barrier__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Question number: 31</p>	checkbox			1	icu_trans_barrier__1	Patient finances	2	icu_trans_barrier__2	Availability of transportation	3	icu_trans_barrier__3	Patient too sick to transfer	4	icu_trans_barrier__4	Bed space at accepting hospital	5	icu_trans_barrier__5	Approval for transfer from accepting hospital	6	icu_trans_barrier__6	Family objection	7	icu_trans_barrier__7	Other	0	icu_trans_barrier__0	No barriers	-1	icu_trans_barrier__1	Don't know						
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7	icu_trans_barrier__7	Other																																					
0	icu_trans_barrier__0	No barriers																																					
-1	icu_trans_barrier__1	Don't know																																					
1118	icu_trans_barrier_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_trans_barrier(7)] = '1'	Please specify	text																																				
1119	icu_trans_accompany Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1'	When critically ill patients are transferred to other facilities by ambulance, what, if any, staff typically accompany the patient, other than driver? <i>do not read choices, check all that apply</i>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="3">checkbox</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>icu_trans_accompany__1</td> <td>Nurse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>icu_trans_accompany__2</td> <td>Clinical officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>icu_trans_accompany__3</td> <td>Medical assistant</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>icu_trans_accompany__4</td> <td>Doctors without specialist training</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>icu_trans_accompany__5</td> <td>Emergency medicine specialists</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>icu_trans_accompany__6</td> <td>Other specialist doctor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>icu_trans_accompany__7</td> <td>Emergency medical technician/paramedic</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>icu_trans_accompany__8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>icu_trans_accompany__0</td> <td>Staff do not typically accompany critically ill patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>icu_trans_accompany__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-2</td> <td>icu_trans_accompany__2</td> <td>Patients do not go by ambulance</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Question number: 32</p>	checkbox			1	icu_trans_accompany__1	Nurse	2	icu_trans_accompany__2	Clinical officer	3	icu_trans_accompany__3	Medical assistant	4	icu_trans_accompany__4	Doctors without specialist training	5	icu_trans_accompany__5	Emergency medicine specialists	6	icu_trans_accompany__6	Other specialist doctor	7	icu_trans_accompany__7	Emergency medical technician/paramedic	8	icu_trans_accompany__8	Other	0	icu_trans_accompany__0	Staff do not typically accompany critically ill patients	-1	icu_trans_accompany__1	Don't know	-2	icu_trans_accompany__2	Patients do not go by ambulance
checkbox																																							
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-2	icu_trans_accompany__2	Patients do not go by ambulance																																					
1120	icu_trans_accompany_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_trans_accompany(8)] = '1'	Please specify	text																																				

1121	<p>icu_trans_treatment</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfer_out] = '1' and [icu_trans_accompany(-2)] <> '1'</p>	<p>When patients are transferred to other facilities by ambulance, what if any treatments can be done in the ambulance? <i>read choices, check all that apply</i></p>	<p>checkbox</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1040 107 1518 785"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>icu_trans_treatment__1</td> <td>Vital sign monitoring</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>icu_trans_treatment__2</td> <td>Cardiac monitoring</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>icu_trans_treatment__3</td> <td>IV fluid administration</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>icu_trans_treatment__4</td> <td>IV medication administration</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>icu_trans_treatment__5</td> <td>Blood transfusion</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>icu_trans_treatment__6</td> <td>Oxygen delivery</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>icu_trans_treatment__7</td> <td>Manual bag ventilation (through endotracheal tube or bag-valve-mask)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>icu_trans_treatment__8</td> <td>Mechanical non-invasive ventilation (BIPAP or CPAP)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>icu_trans_treatment__9</td> <td>Mechanical invasive ventilation with endotracheal tube</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>icu_trans_treatment__0</td> <td>None</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>icu_trans_treatment__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 33</p>	1	icu_trans_treatment__1	Vital sign monitoring	2	icu_trans_treatment__2	Cardiac monitoring	3	icu_trans_treatment__3	IV fluid administration	4	icu_trans_treatment__4	IV medication administration	5	icu_trans_treatment__5	Blood transfusion	6	icu_trans_treatment__6	Oxygen delivery	7	icu_trans_treatment__7	Manual bag ventilation (through endotracheal tube or bag-valve-mask)	8	icu_trans_treatment__8	Mechanical non-invasive ventilation (BIPAP or CPAP)	9	icu_trans_treatment__9	Mechanical invasive ventilation with endotracheal tube	0	icu_trans_treatment__0	None	-1	icu_trans_treatment__1	Don't know
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1122	<p>icu_protocol_abcede</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Intensive Care/High Dependency UnitD. Clinical Are the following clinical management protocols available at this facility?</i></p> <p>Protocol for initial approach to ABCs (airway, breathing, circulation, etc.) and basic neurologic function</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1040 879 1195 999"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 46</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																											
0	No																																			
1	Yes																																			
-1	Don't know																																			
1123	<p>icu_protocol_icu_resus</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Medical resuscitation checklist</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1040 1100 1195 1220"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																											
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1124	<p>icu_protocol_volume</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Protocol for volume resuscitation of children and adults</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1040 1257 1195 1377"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																											
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1	Yes																																			
-1	Don't know																																			
1125	<p>icu_protocol_malnourish</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Protocol for adjusting interventions for malnourished patients</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1040 1415 1195 1535"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																											
0	No																																			
1	Yes																																			
-1	Don't know																																			
1126	<p>icu_protocol_pt_pep</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Protocol for post-exposure prevention of STI/HIV, emergency contraception, counseling</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1040 1572 1195 1692"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																											
0	No																																			
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1127	<p>icu_protocol_asthma</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Condition-specific management protocols for:</i></p> <p>Asthma exacerbation</p>	<p>radio (Matrix)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1040 1730 1195 1850"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 47</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																											
0	No																																			
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-1	Don't know																																			

1128	icu_protocol_pneumonia Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Pneumonia	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1129	icu_protocol_ob_bleed Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Maternal hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1130	icu_protocol_sepsis Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Sepsis	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1131	icu_protocol_dka Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1132	icu_protocol_other Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Other	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1133	icu_protocol_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_protocol_other] = '1'	Please specify	text
1134	icu_protocol_dispo Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Are the following disposition protocols available at this facility</i> Formal written policy outlining the criteria for discharging a patient from your unit?	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 48
1135	icu_protocol_handoff Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Hand-over protocols when transferring patients from one care provider to another	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1136	icu_protocol_ext_trans Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Are the following outside transfer protocols available at this facility</i> Condition-specific transfer or referral protocols (e.g. criteria for transfer of burn patients to burn center)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 49
1137	icu_protocol_trans_comm Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Communication with receiving facility prior to transfer of patients with emergency conditions	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1138	icu_protocol_infect_contr Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Are the following safety protocols available at this facility</i> Infection prevention and control protocols	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 50

1139	icu_protocol_hcw_pep Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for post exposure prophylaxis for health care workers	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1140	icu_protocol_security Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Security protocols to protect staff, patients, and infrastructure from violence	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1141	icu_protocol_hazards Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for managing hazardous exposures (including designated decontamination area)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1142	icu_protocol_waste Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Containment and disposal of sharps and biomedical waste	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1143	icu_protocol_inter_event Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Plan to ensure unit staff and patient safety if an incident occurs within the unit (including space, transport, communications)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1144	icu_protocol_goc Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Are protocols or guidelines on end of life care available at this facility?	radio 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 51
1145	icu_sw Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: Intensive Care Unit/High Dependency Unit Ancillary Services <i>Please rate the availability of each item 1 to 3 1 - Generally unavailable 2 - Some availability 3 - Adequate availability em>Note: If "don't know", enter -1 For rating < 3, mark all relevant barriers: Infrastructure Absent Equipment Broken Equipment Stock Out (Supplies) Training Personnel User Fees Opening Hours Other</i> Social work services	radio (Matrix) 1 Generally Unavailable 2 Some Availability 3 Adequate Availability -1 Don't know
1146	icu_sw_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_sw] = '1' or [icu_sw] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox 1 icu_sw_barrier__1 Infrastr. 2 icu_sw_barrier__2 Absent equip 3 icu_sw_barrier__3 Broken equip 4 icu_sw_barrier__4 Stock out 5 icu_sw_barrier__5 Training 6 icu_sw_barrier__6 Prsnnl. 7 icu_sw_barrier__7 User fees 8 icu_sw_barrier__8 Opening hours 9 icu_sw_barrier__9 Other
1147	icu_sw_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_sw_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text
1148	icu_transport Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Patient transport services	radio (Matrix) 1 Generally Unavailable 2 Some Availability 3 Adequate Availability -1 Don't know

1149	icu_transport_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transport] = '1' or [icu_transport] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_transport_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_transport_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_transport_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_transport_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_transport_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_transport_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_transport_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_transport_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_transport_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_transport_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_transport_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_transport_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_transport_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_transport_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_transport_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_transport_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_transport_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_transport_barrier__9	Other
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1150	icu_transport_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transport_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1151	icu_security Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Security	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1152	icu_security_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_security] = '1' or [icu_security] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_security_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_security_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_security_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_security_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_security_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_security_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_security_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_security_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_security_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_security_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_security_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_security_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_security_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_security_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_security_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_security_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_security_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_security_barrier__9	Other
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1153	icu_security_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_security_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1154	icu_spirit Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Spiritual support	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1155	icu_spirit_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_spirit] = '1' or [icu_spirit] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_spirit_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_spirit_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_spirit_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_spirit_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_spirit_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_spirit_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_spirit_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_spirit_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_spirit_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_spirit_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_spirit_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_spirit_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_spirit_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_spirit_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_spirit_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_spirit_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_spirit_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_spirit_barrier__9	Other
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1156	icu_spirit_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_spirit_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1157	icu_nutritn Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Nutrition	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1158	icu_nutritn_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_nutritn] = '1' or [icu_nutritn] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_nutritn_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_nutritn_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_nutritn_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_nutritn_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_nutritn_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_nutritn_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_nutritn_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_nutritn_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_nutritn_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_nutritn_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_nutritn_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_nutritn_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_nutritn_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_nutritn_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_nutritn_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_nutritn_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_nutritn_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_nutritn_barrier__9	Other
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1159	icu_nutritn_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_nutritn_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1160	icu_respthery Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Respiratory therapy	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1161	icu_respthery_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_respthery]= '1' or [icu_respthery] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_respthery_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_respthery_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_respthery_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_respthery_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_respthery_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_respthery_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_respthery_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_respthery_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_respthery_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_respthery_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_respthery_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_respthery_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_respthery_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_respthery_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_respthery_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_respthery_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_respthery_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_respthery_barrier__9	Other
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1162	icu_respthery_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_respthery_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1163	icu_engineer Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Clinical engineering	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1164	icu_engineer_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_engineer] = '1' or [icu_engineer] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_engineer_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_engineer_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_engineer_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_engineer_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_engineer_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_engineer_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_engineer_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_engineer_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_engineer_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_engineer_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_engineer_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_engineer_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_engineer_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_engineer_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_engineer_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_engineer_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_engineer_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_engineer_barrier__9	Other
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1165	icu_engineer_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_engineer_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1166	icu_pt Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Physical therapy	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1167	icu_pt_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_pt] = '1' or [icu_pt] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_pt_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_pt_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_pt_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_pt_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_pt_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_pt_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_pt_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_pt_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_pt_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_pt_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_pt_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_pt_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_pt_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_pt_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_pt_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_pt_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_pt_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_pt_barrier__9	Other
1	icu_pt_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
2	icu_pt_barrier__2	Absent equip																												
3	icu_pt_barrier__3	Broken equip																												
4	icu_pt_barrier__4	Stock out																												
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7	icu_pt_barrier__7	User fees																												
8	icu_pt_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	icu_pt_barrier__9	Other																												
1168	icu_pt_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_pt_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1169	icu_qi Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Intensive Care/High Dependency Unit Quality Improvement</i> Are there quality improvement projects on your unit currently or at any time in the past year? <i>A quality improvement project is an effort to improve patient care based on an evaluation of the shortcomings of the care the unit provides and the changing knowledge base that informs best care</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 60</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
1170	icu_registry Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Is there a systematic process for collecting patient data that links condition, management, and outcomes (e.g. trauma registry)?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 61</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
1171	icu_m_and_m Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Are there regular meetings convened to use clinical data for quality improvement (e.g. morbidity and mortality conferences, preventable death panels)?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 62</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													

1172	icu_audits Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Is there tracking (e.g. clinical audit) to ensure that quality improvement actions (e.g. corrective action) are implemented after review meetings?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 63</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1173	icu_clin_template Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Is there a clinical document template (e.g. standardized clinical chart)?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 64</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1174	icu_ext_visitor Show the field ONLY if: [icu_clin_lead] = '1'	Has there been a visit to this unit by a supervisor from outside the facility within the last 6 months?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 65</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1175	icu_ext_visitor_org Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ext_visitor] = '1'	What organization did the supervisor work for?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>NGO (e.g. PIH, CHAM)</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Ministry of Health</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 66</p>	1	NGO (e.g. PIH, CHAM)	2	Ministry of Health	3	Other	-1	Don't know
1	NGO (e.g. PIH, CHAM)										
2	Ministry of Health										
3	Other										
-1	Don't know										
1176	icu_ext_visitor_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ext_visitor_org] = '3'	Please specify	text								
1177	icu_ext_visitor_doc Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ext_visitor] = '1'	Is there any documentation from the most recent external supervisory visit?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 67</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1178	icu_ext_visitor_doc_detail Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ext_visitor_doc] = '1'	Does the document provide any feedback or comments on some aspect of emergency services?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 68</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1179	icu_manual	Section Header: Intensive Care Unit/High Dependency Unit E. Signal Functions Please rate the availability of each item 1 to 3 1 - Generally unavailable 2 - Some availability 3 - Adequate availability em>Note: If "don't know", enter -1 For rating < 3, mark all relevant barriers: Infrastructure Absent Equipment Broken Equipment Stock Out (Supplies) Training Personnel User Fees Opening Hours OtherAirway Interventions Use of manual maneuvers (e.g. jaw thrust, chin lift)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know
1	Generally Unavailable										
2	Some Availability										
3	Adequate Availability										
-1	Don't know										

1180	icu_manual_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_manual] = '1' or [icu_manual] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_manual_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_manual_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_manual_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_manual_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_manual_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_manual_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_manual_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_manual_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_manual_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_manual_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_manual_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_manual_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_manual_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_manual_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_manual_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_manual_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_manual_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_manual_barrier__9	Other
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8	icu_manual_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	icu_manual_barrier__9	Other																												
1181	icu_manual_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_manual_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1182	icu_suction	Use of suction	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1183	icu_suction_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_suction] = '1' or [icu_suction] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_suction_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_suction_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_suction_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_suction_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_suction_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_suction_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_suction_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_suction_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_suction_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_suction_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_suction_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_suction_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_suction_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_suction_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_suction_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_suction_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_suction_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_suction_barrier__9	Other
1	icu_suction_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
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8	icu_suction_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	icu_suction_barrier__9	Other																												
1184	icu_suction_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_suction_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1185	icu_oronaso	Placement of oro- or naso-pharyngeal airway device	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1186	icu_oronaso_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_oronaso] = '1' or [icu_oronaso] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_oronaso_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_oronaso_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_oronaso_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_oronaso_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_oronaso_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_oronaso_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_oronaso_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_oronaso_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_oronaso_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_oronaso_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_oronaso_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_oronaso_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_oronaso_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_oronaso_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_oronaso_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_oronaso_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_oronaso_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_oronaso_barrier__9	Other
1	icu_oronaso_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
2	icu_oronaso_barrier__2	Absent equip																												
3	icu_oronaso_barrier__3	Broken equip																												
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9	icu_oronaso_barrier__9	Other																												
1187	icu_oronaso_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_oronaso_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1188	icu_glottic	Placement of supraglottic device	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1189	icu_glottic_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_glottic]= '1' or [icu_glottic]= '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_glottic_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_glottic_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_glottic_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_glottic_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_glottic_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_glottic_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_glottic_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_glottic_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_glottic_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_glottic_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_glottic_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_glottic_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_glottic_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_glottic_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_glottic_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_glottic_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_glottic_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_glottic_barrier__9	Other
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1190	icu_glottic_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_glottic_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1191	icu_intubate	Endotracheal intubation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1192	icu_intubate_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_intubate] = '1' or [icu_intubate] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_intubate_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_intubate_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_intubate_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_intubate_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_intubate_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_intubate_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_intubate_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_intubate_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_intubate_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_intubate_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_intubate_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_intubate_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_intubate_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_intubate_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_intubate_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_intubate_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_intubate_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_intubate_barrier__9	Other
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1193	icu_intubate_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_intubate_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1194	icu_cric	Creation of surgical airway	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1195	icu_cric_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_cric] = '1' or [icu_cric] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_cric_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_cric_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_cric_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_cric_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_cric_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_cric_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_cric_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_cric_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_cric_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_cric_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_cric_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_cric_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_cric_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_cric_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_cric_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_cric_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_cric_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_cric_barrier__9	Other
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9	icu_cric_barrier__9	Other																												
1196	icu_cric_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_cric_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1197	icu_checkspo2	Section Header: <i>Breathing Interventions</i> Continuous pulse oximetry measurement	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1198	icu_checkspo2_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_checkspo2] = '1' or [icu_checkspo2] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_checkspo2_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_checkspo2_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_checkspo2_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_checkspo2_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_checkspo2_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_checkspo2_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_checkspo2_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_checkspo2_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_checkspo2_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_checkspo2_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_checkspo2_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_checkspo2_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_checkspo2_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_checkspo2_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_checkspo2_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_checkspo2_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_checkspo2_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_checkspo2_barrier__9	Other
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1199	icu_checkspo2_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_checkspo2_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1200	icu_txasthma	Administration of critical therapies for reactive airway disease	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1201	icu_txasthma_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_txasthma] = '1' or [icu_txasthma] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_txasthma_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_txasthma_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_txasthma_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_txasthma_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_txasthma_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_txasthma_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_txasthma_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_txasthma_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_txasthma_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_txasthma_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_txasthma_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_txasthma_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_txasthma_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_txasthma_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_txasthma_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_txasthma_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_txasthma_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_txasthma_barrier__9	Other
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1202	icu_txasthma_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_txasthma_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1203	icu_giveo2	Administration of oxygen	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1204	icu_giveo2_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_giveo2] = '1' or [icu_giveo2] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_giveo2_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_giveo2_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_giveo2_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_giveo2_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_giveo2_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_giveo2_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_giveo2_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_giveo2_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_giveo2_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_giveo2_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_giveo2_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_giveo2_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_giveo2_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_giveo2_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_giveo2_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_giveo2_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_giveo2_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_giveo2_barrier__9	Other
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1205	icu_giveo2_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_giveo2_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1206	icu_bagmask	Bag-valve-mask ventilation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1207	icu_bagmask_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_bagmask] = '1' or [icu_bagmask] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_bagmask_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_bagmask_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_bagmask_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_bagmask_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_bagmask_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_bagmask_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_bagmask_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_bagmask_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_bagmask_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_bagmask_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_bagmask_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_bagmask_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_bagmask_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_bagmask_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_bagmask_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_bagmask_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_bagmask_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_bagmask_barrier__9	Other
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1208	icu_bagmask_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_bagmask_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1209	icu_ptx	Perform needle decompression of tension pneumothorax	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1210	icu_ptx_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ptx] = '1' or [icu_ptx] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_ptx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_ptx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_ptx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_ptx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_ptx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_ptx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_ptx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_ptx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_ptx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_ptx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_ptx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_ptx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_ptx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_ptx_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_ptx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_ptx_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_ptx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_ptx_barrier__9	Other
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1211	icu_ptx_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ptx_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1212	icu_chesttube	Placement of chest tube	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1213	icu_chesttube_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_chesttube] = '1' or [icu_chesttube] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_chesttube_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_chesttube_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_chesttube_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_chesttube_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_chesttube_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_chesttube_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_chesttube_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_chesttube_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_chesttube_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_chesttube_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_chesttube_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_chesttube_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_chesttube_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_chesttube_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_chesttube_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_chesttube_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_chesttube_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_chesttube_barrier__9	Other
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1214	icu_chesttube_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_chesttube_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1215	icu_nippv	Non-invasive mechanical ventilation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1216	icu_nippv_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_nippv] = '1' or [icu_nippv] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_nippv_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_nippv_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_nippv_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_nippv_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_nippv_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_nippv_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_nippv_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_nippv_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_nippv_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_nippv_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_nippv_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_nippv_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_nippv_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_nippv_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_nippv_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_nippv_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_nippv_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_nippv_barrier__9	Other
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1217	icu_nippv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_nippv_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1218	icu_vent	Invasive mechanical ventilation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1219	icu_vent_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '1' or [icu_vent] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_vent_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_vent_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_vent_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_vent_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_vent_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_vent_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_vent_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_vent_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_vent_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_vent_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_vent_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_vent_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_vent_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_vent_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_vent_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_vent_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_vent_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_vent_barrier__9	Other
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1220	icu_vent_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1221	icu_number_vented Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '2' or [icu_vent] = '3'	How many patients can receive mechanical ventilation via a ventilator and endotracheal tube on your unit at any one time? <i>enter 0 if none, -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 86																											
1222	icu_vent_policy Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '2' or [icu_vent] = '3'	Is there a written policy for who can or cannot be intubated and/or placed on mechanical ventilation?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 87	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
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1	Yes																													
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1223	icu_extubate_policy Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '2' or [icu_vent] = '3'	Is there a written policy for if and when intubation and/or mechanical ventilation can be withdrawn?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 88	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
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1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
1224	icu_hob Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '2' or [icu_vent] = '3'	Section Header: <i>Mechanical Ventilation</i> Maintain head of bed in semi-recumbent position (30-45 degrees) to reduce aspiration and ventilator associated pneumonia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1225	icu_hob_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_hob] = '1' or [icu_hob] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_hob_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_hob_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_hob_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_hob_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_hob_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_hob_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_hob_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_hob_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_hob_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_hob_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_hob_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_hob_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_hob_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_hob_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_hob_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_hob_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_hob_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_hob_barrier__9	Other
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1226	icu_hob_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_hob_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1227	icu_ventsexn Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '2' or [icu_vent] = '3'	Perform continuous or intermittent (at least every 4 hours) subglottic suctioning of secretions, via cuffed endotracheal tube	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1228	icu_ventsexn_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ventsexn] = '1' or [icu_ventsexn] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_ventsexn_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_ventsexn_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_ventsexn_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_ventsexn_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_ventsexn_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_ventsexn_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_ventsexn_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_ventsexn_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_ventsexn_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_ventsexn_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_ventsexn_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_ventsexn_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_ventsexn_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_ventsexn_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_ventsexn_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_ventsexn_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_ventsexn_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_ventsexn_barrier__9	Other
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9	icu_ventsexn_barrier__9	Other																												
1229	icu_ventsexn_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ventsexn_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1230	icu_sbt Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '2' or [icu_vent] = '3'	Perform daily spontaneous breathing trials	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1231	icu_sbt_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_sbt] = '1' or [icu_sbt] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_sbt_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_sbt_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_sbt_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_sbt_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_sbt_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_sbt_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_sbt_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_sbt_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_sbt_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_sbt_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_sbt_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_sbt_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_sbt_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_sbt_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_sbt_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_sbt_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_sbt_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_sbt_barrier__9	Other
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1232	icu_sbt_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_sbt_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1233	icu_sat Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '2' or [icu_vent] = '3'	Perform daily spontaneous awakening trials	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1234	icu_sat_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_sat] = '1' or [icu_sat] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_sat_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_sat_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_sat_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_sat_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_sat_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_sat_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_sat_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_sat_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_sat_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_sat_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_sat_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_sat_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_sat_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_sat_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_sat_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_sat_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_sat_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_sat_barrier__9	Other
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9	icu_sat_barrier__9	Other																												
1235	icu_sat_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_sat_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1236	icu_ventpt Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '2' or [icu_vent] = '3'	Perform early mobilization for mechanically ventilated patients	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1237	icu_ventpt_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ventpt] = '1' or [icu_ventpt] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_ventpt_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_ventpt_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_ventpt_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_ventpt_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_ventpt_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_ventpt_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_ventpt_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_ventpt_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_ventpt_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_ventpt_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_ventpt_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_ventpt_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_ventpt_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_ventpt_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_ventpt_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_ventpt_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_ventpt_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_ventpt_barrier__9	Other
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1238	icu_ventpt_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ventpt_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1239	icu_cam Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '2' or [icu_vent] = '3'	Assess delirium in mechanically ventilated patients at least twice a day	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1240	icu_cam_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_cam] = '1' or [icu_cam] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_cam_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_cam_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_cam_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_cam_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_cam_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_cam_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_cam_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_cam_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_cam_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_cam_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_cam_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_cam_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_cam_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_cam_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_cam_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_cam_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_cam_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_cam_barrier__9	Other
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1241	icu_cam_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_cam_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1242	icu_pots Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '2' or [icu_vent] = '3'	Assess pain in mechanically ventilated patients at least twice a day	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1243	icu_pots_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_pots] = '1' or [icu_pots] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_pots_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_pots_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_pots_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_pots_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_pots_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_pots_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_pots_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_pots_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_pots_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_pots_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_pots_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_pots_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_pots_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_pots_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_pots_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_pots_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_pots_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_pots_barrier__9	Other
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1244	icu_pots_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_pots_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1245	icu_rass Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '2' or [icu_vent] = '3'	Assess agitation/sedation in mechanically ventilated patients at least twice a day	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1246	icu_rass_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rass] = '1' or [icu_rass] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_rass_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_rass_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_rass_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_rass_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_rass_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_rass_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_rass_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_rass_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_rass_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_rass_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_rass_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_rass_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_rass_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_rass_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_rass_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_rass_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_rass_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_rass_barrier__9	Other
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1247	icu_rass_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rass_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1248	icu_paralyze Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vent] = '2' or [icu_vent] = '3'	Administer and maintain neuromuscular blockade	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1249	icu_paralyze_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_paralyze] = '1' or [icu_paralyze] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_paralyze_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_paralyze_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_paralyze_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_paralyze_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_paralyze_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_paralyze_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_paralyze_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_paralyze_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_paralyze_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_paralyze_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_paralyze_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_paralyze_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_paralyze_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_paralyze_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_paralyze_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_paralyze_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_paralyze_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_paralyze_barrier__9	Other
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9	icu_paralyze_barrier__9	Other																												
1250	icu_paralyze_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rass_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1251	icu_ors	Section Header: <i>Volume Resuscitation Interventions</i> Administer oral rehydration	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1252	icu_ors_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ors] = '1' or [icu_ors] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_ors_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_ors_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_ors_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_ors_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_ors_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_ors_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_ors_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_ors_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_ors_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_ors_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_ors_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_ors_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_ors_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_ors_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_ors_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_ors_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_ors_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_ors_barrier__9	Other
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1253	icu_ors_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ors_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1254	icu_adj_ivf	Adjust fluid resuscitation for malnutrition or severe anemia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1255	icu_adj_ivf_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_adj_ivf] = '1' or [icu_adj_ivf] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_adj_ivf_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_adj_ivf_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_adj_ivf_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_adj_ivf_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_adj_ivf_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_adj_ivf_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_adj_ivf_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_adj_ivf_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_adj_ivf_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_adj_ivf_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_adj_ivf_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_adj_ivf_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_adj_ivf_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_adj_ivf_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_adj_ivf_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_adj_ivf_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_adj_ivf_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_adj_ivf_barrier__9	Other
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1256	icu_adj_ivf_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_adj_ivf_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1257	icu_piv	Place peripheral IV access	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1258	icu_piv_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_piv] = '1' or [icu_piv] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_piv_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_piv_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_piv_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_piv_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_piv_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_piv_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_piv_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_piv_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_piv_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_piv_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_piv_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_piv_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_piv_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_piv_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_piv_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_piv_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_piv_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_piv_barrier__9	Other
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1259	icu_piv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_piv_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1260	icu_io	Establish intraosseous access	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1261	icu_io_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_io] = '1' or [icu_io] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_io_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_io_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_io_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_io_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_io_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_io_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_io_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_io_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_io_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_io_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_io_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_io_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_io_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_io_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_io_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_io_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_io_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_io_barrier__9	Other
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1262	icu_io_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_io_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1263	icu_cutdown	Perform venous cutdown	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1264	icu_cutdown_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_cutdown] = '1' or [icu_cutdown] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_cutdown_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_cutdown_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_cutdown_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_cutdown_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_cutdown_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_cutdown_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_cutdown_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_cutdown_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_cutdown_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_cutdown_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_cutdown_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_cutdown_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_cutdown_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_cutdown_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_cutdown_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_cutdown_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_cutdown_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_cutdown_barrier__9	Other
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1265	icu_cutdown_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_cutdown_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1266	icu_cvc	Establish central venous access	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1267	icu_cvc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_cvc]= '1' or [icu_cvc] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_cvc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_cvc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_cvc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_cvc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_cvc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_cvc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_cvc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_cvc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_cvc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_cvc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_cvc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_cvc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_cvc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_cvc_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_cvc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_cvc_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_cvc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_cvc_barrier__9	Other
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1268	icu_cvc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_cvc_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1269	icu_give_ivf	Administration of IV fluids	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1270	icu_give_ivf_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_give_ivf] = '1' or [icu_give_ivf] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_give_ivf_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_give_ivf_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_give_ivf_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_give_ivf_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_give_ivf_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_give_ivf_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_give_ivf_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_give_ivf_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_give_ivf_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_give_ivf_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_give_ivf_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_give_ivf_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_give_ivf_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_give_ivf_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_give_ivf_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_give_ivf_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_give_ivf_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_give_ivf_barrier__9	Other
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1271	icu_give_ivf_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_give_ivf_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1272	icu_foley	Place urinary catheter	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1273	icu_foley_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_foley] = '1' or [icu_foley] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_foley_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_foley_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_foley_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_foley_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_foley_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_foley_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_foley_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_foley_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_foley_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_foley_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_foley_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_foley_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_foley_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_foley_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_foley_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_foley_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_foley_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_foley_barrier__9	Other
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8	icu_foley_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	icu_foley_barrier__9	Other																												
1274	icu_foley_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_foley_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1275	icu_exctrl_bleed	Section Header: <i>Control of Bleeding</i> External control of haemorrhage	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1276	icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_exctrl_bleed] = '1' or [icu_exctrl_bleed] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__9	Other
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8	icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
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1277	icu_exctrl_bleed_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_exctrl_bleed_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1278	icu_pack	Perform packing and/or suture control	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1279	icu_pack_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_pack] = '1' or [icu_pack] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_pack_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_pack_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_pack_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_pack_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_pack_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_pack_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_pack_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_pack_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_pack_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_pack_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_pack_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_pack_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_pack_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_pack_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_pack_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_pack_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_pack_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_pack_barrier__9	Other
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1280	icu_pack_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_pack_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1281	icu_tourniquet	Apply arterial tourniquet	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1282	icu_tourniquet_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_tourniquet] = '1' or [icu_tourniquet] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_tourniquet_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_tourniquet_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_tourniquet_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_tourniquet_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_tourniquet_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_tourniquet_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_tourniquet_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_tourniquet_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_tourniquet_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_tourniquet_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_tourniquet_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_tourniquet_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_tourniquet_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_tourniquet_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_tourniquet_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_tourniquet_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_tourniquet_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_tourniquet_barrier__9	Other
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1283	icu_tourniquet_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_tourniquet_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1284	icu_pelvicbind	Apply pelvic binding or sheeting	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1285	icu_pelvicbind_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_pelvicbind] = '1' or [icu_pelvicbind] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_pelvicbind_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_pelvicbind_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_pelvicbind_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_pelvicbind_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_pelvicbind_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_pelvicbind_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_pelvicbind_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_pelvicbind_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_pelvicbind_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_pelvicbind_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_pelvicbind_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_pelvicbind_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_pelvicbind_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_pelvicbind_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_pelvicbind_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_pelvicbind_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_pelvicbind_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_pelvicbind_barrier__9	Other
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1286	icu_pelvicbind_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_pelvicbind_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1287	icu_transfuse	Ability to perform safe transfusion (including protocols for appropriate ratios for massive transfusion)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1288	icu_transfuse_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfuse] = '1' or [icu_transfuse] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_transfuse_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_transfuse_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_transfuse_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_transfuse_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_transfuse_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_transfuse_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_transfuse_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_transfuse_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_transfuse_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_transfuse_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_transfuse_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_transfuse_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_transfuse_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_transfuse_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_transfuse_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_transfuse_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_transfuse_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_transfuse_barrier__9	Other
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1289	icu_transfuse_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_transfuse_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1290	icu_pocus	Perform and interpret point of care ultrasound	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1291	icu_pocus_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_pocus] = '1' or [icu_pocus] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_pocus_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_pocus_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_pocus_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_pocus_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_pocus_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_pocus_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_pocus_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_pocus_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_pocus_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_pocus_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_pocus_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_pocus_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_pocus_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_pocus_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_pocus_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_pocus_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_pocus_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_pocus_barrier__9	Other
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1292	icu_pocus_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_pocus_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1293	icu_ecg	Section Header: <i>Cardiac Interventions</i> Perform and interpret ECG	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1294	icu_ecg_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ecg] = '1' or [icu_ecg] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_ecg_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_ecg_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_ecg_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_ecg_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_ecg_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_ecg_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_ecg_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_ecg_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_ecg_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_ecg_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_ecg_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_ecg_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_ecg_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_ecg_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_ecg_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_ecg_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_ecg_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_ecg_barrier__9	Other
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1295	icu_ecg_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ecg_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1296	icu_asa	Administer aspirin for ischemia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1297	icu_asa_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_asa] = '1' or [icu_asa] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_asa_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_asa_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_asa_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_asa_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_asa_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_asa_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_asa_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_asa_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_asa_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_asa_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_asa_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_asa_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_asa_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_asa_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_asa_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_asa_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_asa_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_asa_barrier__9	Other
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1298	icu_asa_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_asa_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1299	icu_defib	Perform external defibrillation and/or cardioversion	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1300	icu_defib_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_defib] = '1' or [icu_defib] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_defib_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_defib_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_defib_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_defib_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_defib_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_defib_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_defib_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_defib_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_defib_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_defib_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_defib_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_defib_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_defib_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_defib_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_defib_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_defib_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_defib_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_defib_barrier__9	Other
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9	icu_defib_barrier__9	Other																												
1301	icu_defib_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_defib_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1302	icu_epi	Administration of adrenaline	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1303	icu_epi_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_epi] = '1' or [icu_epi] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_epi_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_epi_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_epi_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_epi_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_epi_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_epi_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_epi_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_epi_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_epi_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_epi_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_epi_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_epi_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_epi_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_epi_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_epi_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_epi_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_epi_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_epi_barrier__9	Other
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9	icu_epi_barrier__9	Other																												
1304	icu_epi_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_epi_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1305	icu_inotrope	Administer inotropes <i>Examples of inotropes: digoxin, milrinone, dobutamine</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1306	icu_inotrope_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_inotrope] = '1' or [icu_inotrope] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_inotrope_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_inotrope_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_inotrope_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_inotrope_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_inotrope_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_inotrope_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_inotrope_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_inotrope_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_inotrope_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_inotrope_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_inotrope_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_inotrope_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_inotrope_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_inotrope_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_inotrope_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_inotrope_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_inotrope_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_inotrope_barrier__9	Other
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8	icu_inotrope_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	icu_inotrope_barrier__9	Other																												
1307	icu_inotrope_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_inotrope_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1308	icu_rhythm	Administer anti-arrythmics <i>Anti-arrythmics include amiodarone, lidocaine, flecainide, procainamide</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1309	icu_rhythm_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rhythm] = '1' or [icu_rhythm] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_rhythm_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_rhythm_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_rhythm_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_rhythm_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_rhythm_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_rhythm_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_rhythm_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_rhythm_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_rhythm_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_rhythm_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_rhythm_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_rhythm_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_rhythm_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_rhythm_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_rhythm_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_rhythm_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_rhythm_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_rhythm_barrier__9	Other
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9	icu_rhythm_barrier__9	Other																												
1310	icu_rhythm_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rhythm_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1311	icu_lytics	Administration of thrombolytics <i>Thrombolytics include alteplase, urokinase, streptokinase, tenecteplase. They DO NOT include enoxaparin, heparin, warfarin</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1312	icu_lytics_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_lytics] = '1' or [icu_lytics] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_lytics_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_lytics_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_lytics_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_lytics_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_lytics_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_lytics_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_lytics_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_lytics_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_lytics_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_lytics_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_lytics_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_lytics_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_lytics_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_lytics_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_lytics_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_lytics_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_lytics_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_lytics_barrier__9	Other
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1313	icu_lytics_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_lytics_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1314	icu_tamponade	Perform pericardiocentesis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1315	icu_tamponade_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_tamponade] = '1' or [icu_tamponade] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_tamponade_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_tamponade_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_tamponade_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_tamponade_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_tamponade_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_tamponade_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_tamponade_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_tamponade_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_tamponade_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_tamponade_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_tamponade_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_tamponade_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_tamponade_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_tamponade_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_tamponade_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_tamponade_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_tamponade_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_tamponade_barrier__9	Other
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1316	icu_tamponade_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_tamponade_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1317	icu_prctctams	Section Header: <i>Unconscious Patient</i> Protect unconscious patient from secondary injury	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1318	icu_prctctams_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_prctctams] = '1' or [icu_prctctams] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_prctctams_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_prctctams_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_prctctams_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_prctctams_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_prctctams_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_prctctams_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_prctctams_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_prctctams_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_prctctams_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_prctctams_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_prctctams_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_prctctams_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_prctctams_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_prctctams_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_prctctams_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_prctctams_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_prctctams_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_prctctams_barrier__9	Other
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1319	icu_prctctams_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_prctctams_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1320	icu_hypoglyc	Check and/or administer glucose	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1321	icu_hypoglyc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_hypoglyc] = '1' or [icu_hypoglyc] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_hypoglyc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_hypoglyc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_hypoglyc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_hypoglyc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_hypoglyc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_hypoglyc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_hypoglyc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_hypoglyc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_hypoglyc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_hypoglyc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_hypoglyc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_hypoglyc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_hypoglyc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_hypoglyc_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_hypoglyc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_hypoglyc_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_hypoglyc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_hypoglyc_barrier__9	Other
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1322	icu_hypoglyc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_hypoglyc_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1323	icu_insulin	Administer insulin for hyperglycemia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1324	icu_insulin_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_insulin]='1' or [icu_insulin]='2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_insulin_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_insulin_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_insulin_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_insulin_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_insulin_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_insulin_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_insulin_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_insulin_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_insulin_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_insulin_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_insulin_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_insulin_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_insulin_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_insulin_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_insulin_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_insulin_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_insulin_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_insulin_barrier__9	Other
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1325	icu_insulin_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_insulin_barrier(9)]=1'	Please specify	text																											
1326	icu_lp	Perform lumbar puncture	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1327	icu_lp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_lp] = '1' or [icu_lp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_lp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_lp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_lp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_lp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_lp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_lp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_lp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_lp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_lp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_lp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_lp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_lp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_lp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_lp_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_lp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_lp_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_lp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_lp_barrier__9	Other
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1328	icu_lp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_lp_barrier(9)]=1'	Please specify	text																											
1329	icu_benzo	Section Header: <i>Seizure</i> Administer benzodiazepine	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1330	icu_benzo_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_benzo] = '1' or [icu_benzo] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_benzo_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_benzo_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_benzo_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_benzo_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_benzo_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_benzo_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_benzo_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_benzo_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_benzo_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_benzo_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_benzo_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_benzo_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_benzo_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_benzo_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_benzo_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_benzo_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_benzo_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_benzo_barrier__9	Other
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1331	icu_benzo_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_benzo_barrier(9)]=1'	Please specify	text																											

1332	icu_eclamp	Administer IV magnesium for pregnant patient	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1333	icu_eclamp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_eclamp] = '1' or [icu_eclamp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_eclamp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_eclamp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_eclamp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_eclamp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_eclamp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_eclamp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_eclamp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_eclamp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_eclamp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_eclamp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_eclamp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_eclamp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_eclamp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_eclamp_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_eclamp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_eclamp_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_eclamp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_eclamp_barrier__9	Other
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1334	icu_eclamp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_eclamp_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1335	icu_antidote	Administer locally appropriate antidote	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1336	icu_antidote_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_antidote] = '1' or [icu_antidote] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_antidote_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_antidote_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_antidote_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_antidote_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_antidote_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_antidote_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_antidote_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_antidote_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_antidote_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_antidote_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_antidote_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_antidote_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_antidote_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_antidote_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_antidote_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_antidote_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_antidote_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_antidote_barrier__9	Other
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1337	icu_antidote_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_antidote_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1338	icu_mse	Section Header: <i>Other Neurologic Interventions</i> Perform mental status exam	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1339	icu_mse_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_mse] = '1' or [icu_mse] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_mse_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_mse_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_mse_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_mse_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_mse_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_mse_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_mse_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_mse_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_mse_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_mse_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_mse_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_mse_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_mse_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_mse_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_mse_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_mse_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_mse_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_mse_barrier__9	Other
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1340	icu_mse_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_mse_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1341	icu_thermia	Management of extreme temperatures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1342	icu_thermia_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_thermia] = '1' or [icu_thermia] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_thermia_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_thermia_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_thermia_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_thermia_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_thermia_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_thermia_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_thermia_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_thermia_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_thermia_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_thermia_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_thermia_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_thermia_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_thermia_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_thermia_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_thermia_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_thermia_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_thermia_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_thermia_barrier__9	Other
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1343	icu_thermia_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_thermia_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1344	icu_agitation	Administer appropriate therapeutics for agitation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1345	icu_agitation_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_agitation] = '1' or [icu_agitation] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_agitation_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_agitation_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_agitation_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_agitation_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_agitation_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_agitation_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_agitation_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_agitation_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_agitation_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_agitation_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_agitation_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_agitation_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_agitation_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_agitation_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_agitation_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_agitation_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_agitation_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_agitation_barrier__9	Other
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1346	icu_agitation_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_agitation_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1347	icu_restraint	Ability to provide physical restraints	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1348	icu_restraint_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_restraint] = '1' or [icu_restraint] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_restraint_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_restraint_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_restraint_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_restraint_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_restraint_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_restraint_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_restraint_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_restraint_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_restraint_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_restraint_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_restraint_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_restraint_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_restraint_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_restraint_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_restraint_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_restraint_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_restraint_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_restraint_barrier__9	Other
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9	icu_restraint_barrier__9	Other																												
1349	icu_restraint_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_restraint_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1350	icu_ivcs	Perform procedural sedation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1351	icu_ivcs_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ivcs] = '1' or [icu_ivcs] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_ivcs_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_ivcs_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_ivcs_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_ivcs_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_ivcs_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_ivcs_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_ivcs_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_ivcs_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_ivcs_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_ivcs_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_ivcs_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_ivcs_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_ivcs_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_ivcs_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_ivcs_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_ivcs_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_ivcs_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_ivcs_barrier__9	Other
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1352	icu_ivcs_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ivcs_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1353	icu_giveabx	Section Header: <i>Sepsis Interventions</i> Administration of IV or IM antibiotics	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1354	icu_giveabx_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_giveabx] = '1' or [icu_giveabx] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_giveabx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_giveabx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_giveabx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_giveabx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_giveabx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_giveabx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_giveabx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_giveabx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_giveabx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_giveabx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_giveabx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_giveabx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_giveabx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_giveabx_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_giveabx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_giveabx_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_giveabx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_giveabx_barrier__9	Other
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1355	icu_giveabx_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_giveabx_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1356	icu_pressor	Administration of IV vasopressors <i>Vasopressors include: dopamine, epinephrine, norepinephrine, vasopressin, phenylephrine</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1357	icu_pressor_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_pressor] = '1' or [icu_pressor] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_pressor_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_pressor_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_pressor_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_pressor_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_pressor_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_pressor_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_pressor_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_pressor_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_pressor_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_pressor_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_pressor_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_pressor_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_pressor_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_pressor_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_pressor_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_pressor_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_pressor_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_pressor_barrier__9	Other
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1358	icu_pressor_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_pressor_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1359	icu_para	Perform diagnostic paracentesis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1360	icu_para_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_para] = '1' or [icu_para] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_para_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_para_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_para_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_para_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_para_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_para_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_para_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_para_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_para_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_para_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_para_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_para_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_para_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_para_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_para_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_para_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_para_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_para_barrier__9	Other
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1361	icu_para_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_para_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1362	icu_sourcectrl	Bedside minor surgical techniques for source control (e.g. abscess, empyema)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1363	icu_sourcectrl_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_sourcectrl] = '1' or [icu_sourcectrl] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_sourcectrl_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_sourcectrl_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_sourcectrl_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_sourcectrl_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_sourcectrl_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_sourcectrl_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_sourcectrl_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_sourcectrl_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_sourcectrl_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_sourcectrl_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_sourcectrl_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_sourcectrl_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_sourcectrl_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_sourcectrl_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_sourcectrl_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_sourcectrl_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_sourcectrl_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_sourcectrl_barrier__9	Other
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1364	icu_sourcectrl_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_sourcectrl_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1365	icu_woundcare	Section Header: <i>Trauma Interventions</i> Perform initial appropriate wound care	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1366	icu_woundcare_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_woundcare] = '1' or [icu_woundcare] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_woundcare_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_woundcare_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_woundcare_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_woundcare_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_woundcare_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_woundcare_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_woundcare_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_woundcare_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_woundcare_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_woundcare_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_woundcare_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_woundcare_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_woundcare_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_woundcare_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_woundcare_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_woundcare_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_woundcare_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_woundcare_barrier__9	Other
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1367	icu_woundcare_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_woundcare_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1368	icu_goc	Section Header: <i>End of Life Care</i> Communicate with patient and/or families, including sharing poor prognoses	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1369	icu_goc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_goc] = '1' or [icu_goc] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_goc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_goc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_goc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_goc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_goc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_goc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_goc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_goc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_goc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_goc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_goc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_goc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_goc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_goc_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_goc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_goc_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_goc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_goc_barrier__9	Other
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1370	icu_goc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_goc_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1371	icu_cmo	De-escalate care (e.g. stop treatments or remove life support) for patients with poor prognoses based on the expressed goals and wishes of the patient or their families	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1372	icu_cmo_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_cmo] = '1' or [icu_cmo] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_cmo_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_cmo_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_cmo_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_cmo_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_cmo_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_cmo_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_cmo_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_cmo_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_cmo_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_cmo_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_cmo_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_cmo_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_cmo_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_cmo_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_cmo_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_cmo_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_cmo_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_cmo_barrier__9	Other
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1373	icu_cmo_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_cmo_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1374	icu_dvtppx	Section Header: <i>Critical Care Interventions</i> Administer DVT prophylaxis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1375	icu_dvtppx_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_dvtppx] = '1' or [icu_dvtppx] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_dvtppx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_dvtppx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_dvtppx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_dvtppx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_dvtppx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_dvtppx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_dvtppx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_dvtppx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_dvtppx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_dvtppx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_dvtppx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_dvtppx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_dvtppx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_dvtppx_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_dvtppx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_dvtppx_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_dvtppx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_dvtppx_barrier__9	Other
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1376	icu_dvtppx_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_dvtppx_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1377	icu_ten	Provide enteral nutrition	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1378	icu_ten_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ten] = '1' or [icu_ten] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_ten_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_ten_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_ten_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_ten_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_ten_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_ten_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_ten_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_ten_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_ten_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_ten_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_ten_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_ten_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_ten_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_ten_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_ten_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_ten_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_ten_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_ten_barrier__9	Other
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1379	icu_ten_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ten_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1380	icu_antibiogrm	Monitoring of nosocomial infections and antimicrobial resistance patterns	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1381	icu_antibiogrm_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_antibiogrm] = '1' or [icu_antibiogrm] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_antibiogrm_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_antibiogrm_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_antibiogrm_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_antibiogrm_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_antibiogrm_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_antibiogrm_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_antibiogrm_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_antibiogrm_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_antibiogrm_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_antibiogrm_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_antibiogrm_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_antibiogrm_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_antibiogrm_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_antibiogrm_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_antibiogrm_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_antibiogrm_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_antibiogrm_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_antibiogrm_barrier__9	Other
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1382	icu_antibiogrm_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_antibiogrm_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1383	icu_ivsedate	Administer IV sedatives (e.g. benzodiazepine, propofol)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1384	icu_ivsedate_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ivsedate]='1' or [icu_ivse date] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_ivsedate_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_ivsedate_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_ivsedate_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_ivsedate_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_ivsedate_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_ivsedate_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_ivsedate_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_ivsedate_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_ivsedate_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_ivsedate_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_ivsedate_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_ivsedate_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_ivsedate_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_ivsedate_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_ivsedate_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_ivsedate_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_ivsedate_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_ivsedate_barrier__9	Other
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1385	icu_ivsedate_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ivsedate_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1386	icu_ivopioid	Administer IV opioids	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1387	icu_ivopioid_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ivopioid] = '1' or [icu_ivop ioid] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_ivopioid_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_ivopioid_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_ivopioid_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_ivopioid_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_ivopioid_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_ivopioid_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_ivopioid_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_ivopioid_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_ivopioid_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_ivopioid_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_ivopioid_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_ivopioid_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_ivopioid_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_ivopioid_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_ivopioid_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_ivopioid_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_ivopioid_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_ivopioid_barrier__9	Other
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1388	icu_ivopioid_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ivopioid_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1389	icu_q4bmp	Frequently (at least every 4 hours) check electrolytes and adjust management based on results	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1390	icu_q4bmp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_q4bmp] = '1' or [icu_q4b mp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_q4bmp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_q4bmp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_q4bmp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_q4bmp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_q4bmp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_q4bmp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_q4bmp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_q4bmp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_q4bmp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_q4bmp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_q4bmp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_q4bmp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_q4bmp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_q4bmp_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_q4bmp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_q4bmp_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_q4bmp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_q4bmp_barrier__9	Other
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1391	icu_q4bmp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_q4bmp_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1392	icu_q4position	Regularly (at least every 4 hours) reposition patients to prevent pressure ulcers	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1393	icu_q4position_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_q4position] = '1' or [icu_q4position] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_q4position_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_q4position_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_q4position_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_q4position_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_q4position_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_q4position_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_q4position_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_q4position_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_q4position_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_q4position_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_q4position_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_q4position_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_q4position_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_q4position_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_q4position_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_q4position_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_q4position_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_q4position_barrier__9	Other
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1394	icu_q4position_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_q4position_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1395	icu_gippx	Administer stress ulcer prophylaxis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1396	icu_gippx_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_gippx] = '1' or [icu_gippx] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_gippx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_gippx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_gippx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_gippx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_gippx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_gippx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_gippx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_gippx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_gippx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_gippx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_gippx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_gippx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_gippx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_gippx_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_gippx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_gippx_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_gippx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_gippx_barrier__9	Other
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1397	icu_gippx_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_gippx_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1398	icu_cc_admit_policy	Section Header: <i>Intensive Care/High Dependency Unit F. Critical Care</i> Is there a formal written policy outlining the criteria for admission to your unit?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 163</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
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1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													

1399	icu_cc_admit_role	Who decides if a patient can come to the unit? <i>do not read, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_cc_admit_role__1</td><td>Doctor</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_cc_admit_role__2</td><td>Nurse</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_cc_admit_role__3</td><td>Clinical officer</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_cc_admit_role__4</td><td>Medical assistant</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_cc_admit_role__5</td><td>Administrator</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_cc_admit_role__6</td><td>Patient or patient family</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_cc_admit_role__7</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>icu_cc_admit_role__1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 164</p>	1	icu_cc_admit_role__1	Doctor	2	icu_cc_admit_role__2	Nurse	3	icu_cc_admit_role__3	Clinical officer	4	icu_cc_admit_role__4	Medical assistant	5	icu_cc_admit_role__5	Administrator	6	icu_cc_admit_role__6	Patient or patient family	7	icu_cc_admit_role__7	Other	-1	icu_cc_admit_role__1	Don't know
1	icu_cc_admit_role__1	Doctor																									
2	icu_cc_admit_role__2	Nurse																									
3	icu_cc_admit_role__3	Clinical officer																									
4	icu_cc_admit_role__4	Medical assistant																									
5	icu_cc_admit_role__5	Administrator																									
6	icu_cc_admit_role__6	Patient or patient family																									
7	icu_cc_admit_role__7	Other																									
-1	icu_cc_admit_role__1	Don't know																									
1400	icu_cc_admit_role_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_cc_admit_role(7)] = '1'	Please specify	text																								
1401	icu_vitals_how	How are vital signs checked on patients on your unit? <i>read choices, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_vitals_how__1</td><td>Manual BP cuff</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_vitals_how__2</td><td>Automatic BP cuff</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_vitals_how__3</td><td>Intermittent pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_vitals_how__4</td><td>Continuous pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_vitals_how__5</td><td>Continuous cardiac monitor</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_vitals_how__6</td><td>Invasive monitoring (e.g. arterial line)</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_vitals_how__7</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>icu_vitals_how__1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 165</p>	1	icu_vitals_how__1	Manual BP cuff	2	icu_vitals_how__2	Automatic BP cuff	3	icu_vitals_how__3	Intermittent pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)	4	icu_vitals_how__4	Continuous pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)	5	icu_vitals_how__5	Continuous cardiac monitor	6	icu_vitals_how__6	Invasive monitoring (e.g. arterial line)	7	icu_vitals_how__7	Other	-1	icu_vitals_how__1	Don't know
1	icu_vitals_how__1	Manual BP cuff																									
2	icu_vitals_how__2	Automatic BP cuff																									
3	icu_vitals_how__3	Intermittent pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)																									
4	icu_vitals_how__4	Continuous pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)																									
5	icu_vitals_how__5	Continuous cardiac monitor																									
6	icu_vitals_how__6	Invasive monitoring (e.g. arterial line)																									
7	icu_vitals_how__7	Other																									
-1	icu_vitals_how__1	Don't know																									
1402	icu_vitals_how_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_vitals_how(7)] = '1'	Please specify	text																								
1403	icu_vitals_recheck_freq	How often (in hours) are vital signs checked on patients on the unit? <i>enter -1 for unsure and -2 if not checked at regular intervals</i>	text Question number: 167																								
1404	icu_cc_reassessed	Are patients on the unit reassessed at least twice a day by a clinician who can change the treatment plan if needed?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 168</p>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know												
1	Almost never																										
2	Infrequently																										
3	Sometimes																										
4	Frequently																										
5	Almost always																										
-1	Don't know																										
1405	icu_seen_dka	Section Header: <i>Have you seen > 5 patients over the past 3 months on your unit with each of the following?</i> Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 169</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																		
0	No																										
1	Yes																										
-1	Don't know																										

1406	icu_seen_seizures	Seizures	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1407	icu_seen_poisoning	Poisoning	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1408	icu_seen_chf	Severe heart failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1409	icu_seen_arf	Severe renal failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1410	icu_seen_respiratory	Respiratory distress or respiratory failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1411	icu_seen_shock	Low blood pressure or shock	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1412	icu_seen_ams	Coma (altered mental status or decreased level of consciousness)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1413	icu_seen_stroke	Suspected stroke	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1414	icu_seen_head_trauma	Severe head trauma	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1415	icu_seen_open_frac	Open fracture	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1416	icu_seen_closed_frac	Closed long bone fracture (e.g. femur)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1417	icu_seen_other_trauma	Other trauma	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know

1418	icu_seen_obstructed_labor	Obstructed labor	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1419	icu_seen_pph	Post-partum hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1420	icu_learn_dka	Section Header: <i>Have you received training in the past year on the following conditions:</i> Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 170
1421	icu_learn_seizures	Seizures	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1422	icu_learn_poisoning	Poisoning	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1423	icu_learn_chf	Severe heart failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1424	icu_learn_arf	Severe renal failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1425	icu_learn_respiratory	Respiratory distress or respiratory failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1426	icu_learn_shock	Low blood pressure or shock	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1427	icu_learn_ams	Coma (altered mental status or decreased level of consciousness)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1428	icu_learn_stroke	Suspected stroke	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know

1429	icu_learn_head_trauma	Severe head trauma	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1430	icu_learn_open_frac	Open fracture	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1431	icu_learn_closed_frac	Closed long bone fracture (e.g. femur)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1432	icu_learn_other_trauma	Other trauma	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1433	icu_learn_obstructed_labor	Obstructed labor	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1434	icu_learn_pph	Post-partum hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1435	icu_has_water	Section Header: <i>Intensive Care/High Dependency Unit</i> G. <i>Infrastructure and Essential Equipment</i> Rate availability of each item 1 to 31) Generally unavailable 2) Some availability3) Adequate availability If "don't know", enter -1 Provide comment if rating < 3 Clean, running water	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 174	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1436	icu_has_water_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_has_water] = '1' or [icu_has_water] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1437	icu_has_electric	Electricity source (e.g. wired, generator)	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 175	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1438	icu_has_electric_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_has_electric] = '1' or [icu_has_electric] = '2'	Please comment	text								

1439	icu_paper_chart	Paper-based chart	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 177</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1440	icu_paper_chart_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_paper_chart] = '1' or [icu_paper_chart] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1441	icu_elec_chart	Electronic chart	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 178</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1442	icu_elec_chart_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_elec_chart] = '1' or [icu_elec_chart] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1443	icu_iso_room	Isolation room for infecious diseases (e.g. TB, haemorrhagic fever)	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 179</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1444	icu_iso_room_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_iso_room] = '1' or [icu_iso_room] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1445	icu_ecg_monitor	Electronic cardiac monitoring in the unit	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 183</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1446	icu_ecg_monitor_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ecg_monitor] = '1' or [icu_ecg_monitor] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1447	icu_codecart	Crash trolley or code cart with high-acuity equipment and supplies of various sizes in the unit	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 184</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1448	icu_codecart_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_codecart] = '1' or [icu_codecart] = '2'	Please comment	text								

1449	icu_storage	Is there access to storage space within (or with immediate proximity to) the unit, including secure storage for controlled substances?	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 187</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1450	icu_storage_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_storage] = '1' or [icu_storage] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1451	icu_toilet	Access to toilet facilities for patients and staff	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 189</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1452	icu_toilet_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_toilet] = '1' or [icu_toilet] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1453	icu_handwash	Access to handwashing facilities in each patient care area	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 190</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1454	icu_handwash_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_handwash] = '1' or [icu_handwash] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1455	icu_inventory	System for stocking, managing, and dispensing medications in the unit	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 191</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1456	icu_inventory_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_inventory] = '1' or [icu_inventory] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1457	icu_has_o2	Oxygen in the unit	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 192</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1458	icu_has_o2_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_has_o2] = '1' or [icu_has_o2] = '2'	Please comment	text Question number: 193								

1459	icu_o2_piped Show the field ONLY if: [icu_has_o2] = '2' or [icu_has_o2] = '3'	Section Header: <i>Which of the following methods supply oxygen in your unit?</i> Central piped system	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1460	icu_o2_cnctrtr Show the field ONLY if: [icu_has_o2] = '2' or [icu_has_o2] = '3'	Oxygen concentrator stored in the unit	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1461	icu_o2_tanks Show the field ONLY if: [icu_has_o2] = '2' or [icu_has_o2] = '3'	Tanks that are stored in the unit	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1462	icu_o2_central_tank Show the field ONLY if: [icu_has_o2] = '2' or [icu_has_o2] = '3'	Call for tank from central location if needed	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1463	icu_o2_central_cnctrtr Show the field ONLY if: [icu_has_o2] = '2' or [icu_has_o2] = '3'	Call for oxygen from concentrator from central location if needed	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1464	icu_protec_eye	Section Header: <i>Which of the following personal protective equipment is available in your unit?</i> Eye protection	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 194
1465	icu_protec_n95	N-95 mask	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1466	icu_protec_gown	Gowns	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1467	icu_protec_glove	Gloves	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1468	icu_drwblood	Section Header: <i>Intensive Care Unit/High Dependency Unit Diagnostic Services</i> <i>Please rate the availability of each item 1 to 3 1 - Generally unavailable 2 - Some availability 3 - Adequate availability Note: If "don't know", enter -1 For rating < 3, mark all relevant barriers: Infrastructure Absent Equipment Broken Equipment Stock Out (Supplies) Training Personnel User Fees Opening Hours Other</i> Blood draw for laboratory testing in unit (as opposed to central lab)	radio (Matrix) 1 Generally Unavailable 2 Some Availability 3 Adequate Availability -1 Don't know

1469	icu_drwblood_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_drwblood] = '1' or [icu_drwblood] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_drwblood_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_drwblood_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_drwblood_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_drwblood_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_drwblood_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_drwblood_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_drwblood_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_drwblood_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_drwblood_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_drwblood_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_drwblood_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_drwblood_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_drwblood_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_drwblood_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_drwblood_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_drwblood_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_drwblood_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_drwblood_barrier__9	Other
1	icu_drwblood_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
2	icu_drwblood_barrier__2	Absent equip																												
3	icu_drwblood_barrier__3	Broken equip																												
4	icu_drwblood_barrier__4	Stock out																												
5	icu_drwblood_barrier__5	Training																												
6	icu_drwblood_barrier__6	Prsnnl.																												
7	icu_drwblood_barrier__7	User fees																												
8	icu_drwblood_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	icu_drwblood_barrier__9	Other																												
1470	icu_drwblood_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_drwblood_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1471	icu_hgb	Hemoglobin	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1472	icu_hgb_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_hgb] = '1' or [icu_hgb] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_hgb_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_hgb_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_hgb_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_hgb_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_hgb_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_hgb_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_hgb_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_hgb_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_hgb_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_hgb_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_hgb_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_hgb_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_hgb_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_hgb_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_hgb_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_hgb_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_hgb_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_hgb_barrier__9	Other
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9	icu_hgb_barrier__9	Other																												
1473	icu_hgb_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_hgb_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1474	icu_fbc	Full blood count	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1475	icu_fbc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_fbc] = '1' or [icu_fbc] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_fbc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_fbc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_fbc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_fbc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_fbc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_fbc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_fbc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_fbc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_fbc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_fbc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_fbc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_fbc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_fbc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_fbc_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_fbc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_fbc_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_fbc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_fbc_barrier__9	Other
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1476	icu_fbc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_fbc_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1477	icu_ptinr	Coagulation profile (PT/PTT, INR)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1478	icu_ptinr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ptinr] = '1' or [icu_ptinr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_ptinr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_ptinr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_ptinr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_ptinr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_ptinr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_ptinr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_ptinr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_ptinr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_ptinr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_ptinr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_ptinr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_ptinr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_ptinr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_ptinr_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_ptinr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_ptinr_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_ptinr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_ptinr_barrier__9	Other
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9	icu_ptinr_barrier__9	Other																												
1479	icu_ptinr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ptinr_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1480	icu_electrolyte	Electrolytes	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1481	icu_electrolyte_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_electrolyte] = '1' or [icu_electrolyte] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_electrolyte_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_electrolyte_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_electrolyte_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_electrolyte_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_electrolyte_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_electrolyte_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_electrolyte_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_electrolyte_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_electrolyte_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_electrolyte_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_electrolyte_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_electrolyte_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_electrolyte_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_electrolyte_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_electrolyte_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_electrolyte_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_electrolyte_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_electrolyte_barrier__9	Other
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1482	icu_electrolyte_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_electrolyte_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1483	icu_buncr	BUN and creatinine	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1484	icu_buncr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_buncr]='1' or [icu_buncr]='2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_buncr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_buncr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_buncr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_buncr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_buncr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_buncr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_buncr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_buncr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_buncr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_buncr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_buncr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_buncr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_buncr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_buncr_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_buncr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_buncr_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_buncr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_buncr_barrier__9	Other
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1485	icu_buncr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_buncr_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1486	icu_lipase	Lipase	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1487	icu_lipase_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_lipase] = '1' or [icu_lipase] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_lipase_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_lipase_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_lipase_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_lipase_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_lipase_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_lipase_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_lipase_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_lipase_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_lipase_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_lipase_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_lipase_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_lipase_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_lipase_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_lipase_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_lipase_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_lipase_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_lipase_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_lipase_barrier__9	Other
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1488	icu_lipase_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_lipase_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1489	icu_trop	Cardiac marker (e.g. troponin)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1490	icu_trop_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_trop] = '1' or [icu_trop] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_trop_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_trop_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_trop_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_trop_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_trop_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_trop_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_trop_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_trop_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_trop_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_trop_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_trop_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_trop_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_trop_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_trop_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_trop_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_trop_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_trop_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_trop_barrier__9	Other
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1491	icu_trop_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_trop_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1492	icu_abg	Arterial blood gas	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1493	icu_abg_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_abg] = '1' or [icu_abg] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_abg_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_abg_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_abg_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_abg_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_abg_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_abg_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_abg_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_abg_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_abg_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_abg_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_abg_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_abg_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_abg_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_abg_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_abg_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_abg_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_abg_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_abg_barrier__9	Other
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1494	icu_abg_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_abg_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1495	icu_typescrn	Cross matching for blood and blood products	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1496	icu_typescrn_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_typescrn] = '1' or [icu_typescrn] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_typescrn_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_typescrn_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_typescrn_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_typescrn_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_typescrn_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_typescrn_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_typescrn_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_typescrn_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_typescrn_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_typescrn_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_typescrn_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_typescrn_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_typescrn_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_typescrn_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_typescrn_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_typescrn_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_typescrn_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_typescrn_barrier__9	Other
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9	icu_typescrn_barrier__9	Other																												
1497	icu_typescrn_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_typescrn_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1498	icu_bcx sensi	Blood cultures and sensitivities	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1499	icu_bcx sensi_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_bcx sensi] = '1' or [icu_bcx sensi] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_bcx sensi_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_bcx sensi_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_bcx sensi_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_bcx sensi_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_bcx sensi_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_bcx sensi_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_bcx sensi_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_bcx sensi_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_bcx sensi_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_bcx sensi_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_bcx sensi_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_bcx sensi_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_bcx sensi_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_bcx sensi_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_bcx sensi_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_bcx sensi_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_bcx sensi_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_bcx sensi_barrier__9	Other
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1500	icu_bcx sensi_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_bcx sensi_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											
1501	icu_sterilesamp	Capacity to obtain sterile blood samples for lab testing	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1502	icu_sterilesamp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_sterilesamp] = '1' or [icu_ sterilesamp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_sterilesamp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_sterilesamp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_sterilesamp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_sterilesamp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_sterilesamp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_sterilesamp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_sterilesamp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_sterilesamp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_sterilesamp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_sterilesamp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_sterilesamp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_sterilesamp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_sterilesamp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_sterilesamp_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_sterilesamp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_sterilesamp_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_sterilesamp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_sterilesamp_barrier__9	Other
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1503	icu_sterilesamp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_sterilesamp_barrier(9)] ='1'	Please specify	text																											
1504	icu_reportlab	System for reporting lab results in a timely fashion	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1505	icu_reportlab_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_reportlab] = '1' or [icu_re portlab] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_reportlab_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_reportlab_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_reportlab_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_reportlab_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_reportlab_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_reportlab_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_reportlab_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_reportlab_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_reportlab_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_reportlab_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_reportlab_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_reportlab_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_reportlab_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_reportlab_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_reportlab_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_reportlab_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_reportlab_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_reportlab_barrier__9	Other
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1506	icu_reportlab_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_reportlab_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											

1507	icu_udip	Urine dipstick	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1508	icu_udip_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_udip] = '1' or [icu_udip] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_udip_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_udip_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_udip_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_udip_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_udip_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_udip_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_udip_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_udip_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_udip_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_udip_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_udip_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_udip_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_udip_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_udip_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_udip_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_udip_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_udip_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_udip_barrier__9	Other
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1509	icu_udip_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_udip_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1510	icu_uhcg	Urine pregnancy	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1511	icu_uhcg_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_uhcg] = '1' or [icu_uhcg] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_uhcg_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_uhcg_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_uhcg_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_uhcg_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_uhcg_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_uhcg_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_uhcg_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_uhcg_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_uhcg_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_uhcg_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_uhcg_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_uhcg_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_uhcg_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_uhcg_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_uhcg_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_uhcg_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_uhcg_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_uhcg_barrier__9	Other
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1512	icu_uhcg_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_uhcg_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1513	icu_glucose	Glucose	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1514	icu_glucose_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_glucose] = '1' or [icu_glucose] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_glucose_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_glucose_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_glucose_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_glucose_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_glucose_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_glucose_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_glucose_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_glucose_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_glucose_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_glucose_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_glucose_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_glucose_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_glucose_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_glucose_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_glucose_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_glucose_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_glucose_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_glucose_barrier__9	Other
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1515	icu_glucose_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_glucose_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1516	icu_rdt	Malaria Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1517	icu_rdt_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rdt] = '1' or [icu_rdt] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_rdt_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_rdt_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_rdt_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_rdt_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_rdt_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_rdt_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_rdt_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_rdt_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_rdt_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_rdt_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_rdt_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_rdt_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_rdt_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_rdt_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_rdt_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_rdt_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_rdt_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_rdt_barrier__9	Other
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1518	icu_rdt_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rdt_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1519	icu_malariasmr	Malaria smear/microscopy	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1520	icu_malariasmr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_malariasmr] = '1' or [icu_malariasmr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_malariasmr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_malariasmr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_malariasmr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_malariasmr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_malariasmr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_malariasmr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_malariasmr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_malariasmr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_malariasmr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_malariasmr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_malariasmr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_malariasmr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_malariasmr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_malariasmr_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_malariasmr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_malariasmr_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_malariasmr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_malariasmr_barrier__9	Other
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1521	icu_malariasmr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_malariasmr_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1522	icu_rapidhiv	Rapid HIV testing	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1523	icu_rapidhiv_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rapidhiv] = '1' or [icu_rapidhiv] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_rapidhiv_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_rapidhiv_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_rapidhiv_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_rapidhiv_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_rapidhiv_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_rapidhiv_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_rapidhiv_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_rapidhiv_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_rapidhiv_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_rapidhiv_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_rapidhiv_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_rapidhiv_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_rapidhiv_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_rapidhiv_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_rapidhiv_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_rapidhiv_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_rapidhiv_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_rapidhiv_barrier__9	Other
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1524	icu_rapidhiv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rapidhiv_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1525	icu_nonportxr	Stationary X-ray	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1526	icu_nonportxr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_nonportxr] = '1' or [icu_nonportxr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_nonportxr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_nonportxr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_nonportxr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_nonportxr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_nonportxr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_nonportxr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_nonportxr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_nonportxr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_nonportxr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_nonportxr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_nonportxr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_nonportxr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_nonportxr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_nonportxr_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_nonportxr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_nonportxr_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_nonportxr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_nonportxr_barrier__9	Other
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1527	icu_nonportxr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_nonportxr_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1528	icu_portxr	Portable X-ray for use in the unit	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1529	icu_portxr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_portxr] = '1' or [icu_portxr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_portxr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_portxr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_portxr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_portxr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_portxr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_portxr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_portxr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_portxr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_portxr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_portxr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_portxr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_portxr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_portxr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_portxr_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_portxr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_portxr_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_portxr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_portxr_barrier__9	Other
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1530	icu_portxr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_portxr_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1531	icu_us_hosp	Ultrasound in the hospital	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1532	icu_us_hosp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_us_hosp] = '1' or [icu_us_hosp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_us_hosp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_us_hosp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_us_hosp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_us_hosp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_us_hosp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_us_hosp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_us_hosp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_us_hosp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_us_hosp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_us_hosp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_us_hosp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_us_hosp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_us_hosp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_us_hosp_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_us_hosp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_us_hosp_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_us_hosp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_us_hosp_barrier__9	Other
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1533	icu_us_hosp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_us_hosp_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1534	icu_us_icu	Ultrasound for use in the unit	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1535	icu_us_icu_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_us_icu] = '1' or [icu_us_icu] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_us_icu_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_us_icu_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_us_icu_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_us_icu_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_us_icu_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_us_icu_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_us_icu_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_us_icu_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_us_icu_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_us_icu_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_us_icu_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_us_icu_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_us_icu_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_us_icu_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_us_icu_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_us_icu_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_us_icu_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_us_icu_barrier__9	Other
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1536	icu_us_icu_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_us_icu_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1537	icu_ct	CT scan	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1538	icu_ct_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ct] = '1' or [icu_ct] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_ct_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_ct_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_ct_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_ct_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_ct_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_ct_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_ct_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_ct_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_ct_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_ct_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_ct_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_ct_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_ct_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_ct_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_ct_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_ct_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_ct_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_ct_barrier__9	Other
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1539	icu_ct_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_ct_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1540	icu_systemrad	System for reporting radiology results in a timely fashion	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1541	icu_systemrad_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [icu_systemrad] = '1' or [icu_systemrad] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_systemrad_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_systemrad_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_systemrad_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>icu_systemrad_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>icu_systemrad_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>icu_systemrad_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>icu_systemrad_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>icu_systemrad_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>icu_systemrad_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	icu_systemrad_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	icu_systemrad_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	icu_systemrad_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	icu_systemrad_barrier__4	Stock out	5	icu_systemrad_barrier__5	Training	6	icu_systemrad_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	icu_systemrad_barrier__7	User fees	8	icu_systemrad_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	icu_systemrad_barrier__9	Other
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1542	icu_systemrad_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_systemrad_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1543	icu_rads_read	Who interprets radiology results? <i>read choices, choose all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>icu_rads_read__1</td><td>Provider</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>icu_rads_read__2</td><td>Radiologist</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>icu_rads_read__3</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>icu_rads_read__4</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 221</p>	1	icu_rads_read__1	Provider	2	icu_rads_read__2	Radiologist	3	icu_rads_read__3	Other	-1	icu_rads_read__4	Don't know															
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1544	icu_rads_read_spec Show the field ONLY if: [icu_rads_read(3)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1545	clinician_icu_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>Incomplete</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Unverified</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Complete</td></tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete																					
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2	Complete																													

Instrument: Clinician ED (clinician_ed)		^ Collapse											
1546	ed_record_id	Section Header: <i>EMERGENCY UNIT (ED)</i> Record ID	text (integer, Min: 0, Max: 1000000), Required										
1547	ed_facility	Name of facility <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	text, Required										
1548	ed_has_ed	Is there an ED in this hospital? <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes						
0	No												
1	Yes												
1549	ed_clin_lead	Is this participant a clinical lead of the ED? <i>To be completed prior to start of interview</i>	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes						
0	No												
1	Yes												
1550	ed_date	Interview date and time (Day-Month-Year; 24 hour clock)	text (datetime_dmy)										
1551	ed_where_work	Section Header: <i>Emergency Unit (ED)A. Background Questions</i> Where in the hospital do you primarily work? <i>if the respondent works in multiple areas, ask them to choose the area they work in the most often</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Outpatient Department (OPD)</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Emergency unit (ED)</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Inpatient ward</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>HDU/ICU</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 1</p>	1	Outpatient Department (OPD)	2	Emergency unit (ED)	3	Inpatient ward	4	HDU/ICU	5	Other
1	Outpatient Department (OPD)												
2	Emergency unit (ED)												
3	Inpatient ward												
4	HDU/ICU												
5	Other												
1552	ed_where_work_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_where_work] = '5' or [ed_where_work] = '3'	Please specify	text										
1553	ed_role	What is your role? <i>read all choices</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Doctor</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Nurse</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Clinical Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Medical Assistant</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 2</p>	1	Doctor	2	Nurse	3	Clinical Officer	4	Medical Assistant	5	Other
1	Doctor												
2	Nurse												
3	Clinical Officer												
4	Medical Assistant												
5	Other												
1554	ed_role_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_role] = '5'	Please specify	text										
1555	ed_days_at_ed	How many days per week do you work in the ED? <i>enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 7) Question number: 3										
1556	ed_hours_prsnt	Section Header: <i>Emergency Unit (ED)B. Hospital Structure/Staffing</i> During which hours is the ED covered by providers who are physically present in the ED?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than 24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>The ED is never covered by providers who are physically present in the ED</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 4</p>	1	24 hours a day	2	Less than 24 hours a day	-1	Don't know	-2	The ED is never covered by providers who are physically present in the ED		
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1557	ed_hours_prsnt_start Show the field ONLY if: [ed_hours_prsnt] = '2'	Coverage starts at	<table border="1"><thead><tr><th colspan="2">dropdown</th></tr></thead><tbody><tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr><tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr><tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr><tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr><tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr><tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr><tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr><tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr><tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr><tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr><tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr><tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr><tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr><tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr><tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr><tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr><tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr><tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr><tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr><tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr><tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr><tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr><tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr><tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr></tbody></table>	dropdown		12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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1558	<p>ed_hours_prsnt_stop</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [ed_hours_prsnt] = '2'</p>	<p>Coverage ends at</p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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1559	<p>ed_hours_in</p>	<p>During which hours is the ED covered by providers who are on call, inside the facility?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than 24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>The ED is never covered by providers who are on call, inside the facility</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 5</p>	1	24 hours a day	2	Less than 24 hours a day	-1	Don't know	-2	The ED is never covered by providers who are on call, inside the facility																																								
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1560	ed_hours_in_start Show the field ONLY if: [ed_hours_in] = '2'	Coverage starts at	dropdown
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1561	<p>ed_hours_in_stop</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [ed_hours_in] = '2'</p>	<p>Coverage ends at</p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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1562	<p>ed_hours_out</p>	<p>During which hours is the ED covered by providers who are on call, outside the facility?</p>	<p>radio</p> <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than 24 hours a day</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>-2</td><td>The ED is never covered by providers who are on call, outside the facility</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 6</p>	1	24 hours a day	2	Less than 24 hours a day	-1	Don't know	-2	The ED is never covered by providers who are on call, outside the facility																																								
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1563	ed_hours_out_start Show the field ONLY if: [ed_hours_out] = '2'	Coverage starts at	<table border="1"><thead><tr><th colspan="2">dropdown</th></tr></thead><tbody><tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr><tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr><tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr><tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr><tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr><tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr><tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr><tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr><tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr><tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr><tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr><tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr><tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr><tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr><tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr><tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr><tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr><tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr><tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr><tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr><tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr><tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr><tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr><tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr></tbody></table>	dropdown		12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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1564	ed_hours_out_stop Show the field ONLY if: [ed_hours_out] = '2'	Coverage ends at	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>12</td><td>12pm</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>1pm</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2pm</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>3pm</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>4pm</td></tr> <tr><td>17</td><td>5pm</td></tr> <tr><td>18</td><td>6pm</td></tr> <tr><td>19</td><td>7pm</td></tr> <tr><td>20</td><td>8pm</td></tr> <tr><td>21</td><td>9pm</td></tr> <tr><td>22</td><td>10pm</td></tr> <tr><td>23</td><td>11pm</td></tr> <tr><td>24</td><td>12am</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1am</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2am</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3am</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4am</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5am</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>6am</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>7am</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>8am</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>9am</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>10am</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>11am</td></tr> </table>	12	12pm	13	1pm	14	2pm	15	3pm	16	4pm	17	5pm	18	6pm	19	7pm	20	8pm	21	9pm	22	10pm	23	11pm	24	12am	1	1am	2	2am	3	3am	4	4am	5	5am	6	6am	7	7am	8	8am	9	9am	10	10am	11	11am
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1565	ed_rn_available	Are nurses available 24 hours a day, every day of the week in the ED for critically ill patients in the ED? <i>read all choices</i>	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes, in the ED</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Yes, on call within the facility</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Yes, on call outside the facility</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 7</p>	0	No	1	Yes, in the ED	2	Yes, on call within the facility	3	Yes, on call outside the facility	-1	Don't know																																						
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1566	ed_corps Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Do you have a core of fixed (non-rotating) providers premanently assigned to the ED?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 11</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																																										
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1567	ed_nonrot_rn Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>What is the number of each of the following non-rotating providers in the Emergency Unit?</i> Nurses	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)																																																
1568	ed_nonrot_rn_cert Show the field ONLY if: [ed_nonrot_rn] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)																																																
1569	ed_nonrot_app Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Mid-level provider or advance practice nurses (e.g. clinical officers)	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)																																																
1570	ed_nonrot_app_cert Show the field ONLY if: [ed_nonrot_app] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)																																																

1571	ed_nonrot_mo Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Doctors without specialist training	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1572	ed_nonrot_mo_cert Show the field ONLY if: [ed_nonrot_mo] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1573	ed_nonrot_ermd Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Emergency medicine specialists	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1574	ed_nonrot_ermd_cert Show the field ONLY if: [ed_nonrot_ermd] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1575	ed_nonrot_othermd Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Other specialist doctor	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1576	ed_nonrot_othermd_cert Show the field ONLY if: [ed_nonrot_othermd] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1577	ed_rot_rn Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>What is the number of each of the following rotating providers in the Emergency Unit?</i> Nurses	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1578	ed_rot_rn_cert Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rot_rn] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1579	ed_rot_app Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Mid-level provider or advance practice nurses (e.g. clinical officers)	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1580	ed_rot_app_cert Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rot_app] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1581	ed_rot_mo Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Doctors without specialist training	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1582	ed_rot_mo_cert Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rot_mo] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1583	ed_rot_ermd Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Emergency medicine specialists	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1584	ed_rot_ermd_cert Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rot_ermd] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1585	ed_rot_othermd Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Other specialist doctor	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1586	ed_rot_othermd_cert Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rot_othermd] > '0'	How many are licensed or certified?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000)
1587	ed_rn_avgday Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	How many nurses work in the ED on an average daytime shift? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to ED, enter -1 if unsure</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 14
1588	ed_rn_today Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	How many nurses are working in the ED today? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to ED, enter -1 if unsure</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 15

1589	ed_rn_avgnight Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	How many nurses work in the ED on an average overnight shift? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to these beds, enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 16						
1590	ed_rn_lastnight Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	How many nurses worked in your ED last night? <i>enter 0 if no nurses specifically assigned to ED, enter -1 if unsure</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000)						
1591	ed_census Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	How many patients are currently in your ED? <i>enter -1 if unsure</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 18						
1592	ed_obs_freq	What is the frequency of nurse observations for patients in the ED? <i>give answer in hours, enter -1 if unknown, enter -2 if no standard frequency</i>	text (number, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 19						
1593	ed_notify_change	If a nurse observes a clinical change, who does the nurse call? <i>enter -1 if don't know, enter 0 if nobody</i>	text Question number: 21						
1594	ed_rn_change	Can nurses initiate treatment without specific provider orders in response to an observed clinical change?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 22	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1595	ed_rn_change_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rn_change] = '1'	Please specify	text						
1596	ed_to_inpt	Section Header: <i>Emergency Unit (ED) C. Transfers and Patient Flow</i> Does the ED transfer patients directly to inpatient wards in this hospital?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 23	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1597	ed_sick_accept	Are patients ever too sick (meaning unstable vital signs or requiring interventions or monitoring that are too frequent or prognosis is too poor) to be accepted into the ED?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 24	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1598	ed_sick_accept_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_sick_accept] = '1'	Please specify	text						
1599	ed_sick_trans Show the field ONLY if: [ed_to_inpt] = '1'	Are patients ever too sick (meaning unstable vital signs or requiring interventions or monitoring that are too frequent or prognosis is too poor) to be transferred from the ED to the inpatient wards of this hospital and need to stay in the ED as a result?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 25	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1600	ed_sick_trans_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_sick_trans] = '1'	Please specify	text						
1601	ed_from_inpt	Can patients be transferred from the inpatient wards of the hospital to the ED?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1602	ed_from_inpt_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_from_inpt] = '1'	Please specify	text Question number: 26						

1603	ed_transfer_out	Does the ED transfer patients from the ED directly to other hospitals or health facilities?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 27</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
1604	ed_transfer_number Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Approximately how many patients were transferred out from the ED to other hospitals or health facilities in the last month? <i>Ask respondent to give best guess, for example, consider how many patients they personally have transferred and what % of the time they work. Enter -1 if unable to give best guess</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 28												
1605	ed_trans_dka Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Section Header: <i>For the following conditions, indicate how often patient with that condition is transferred out to another hospital. Please consider only patients who are actually transferred, not how often you feel a patient with this condition requires transfer.</i> Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Almost never</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Infrequently</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Sometimes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Frequently</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Almost always</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 29</p>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1606	ed_trans_seizures Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Seizures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Almost never</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Infrequently</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Sometimes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Frequently</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Almost always</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1607	ed_trans_poisoning Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Poisoning	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Almost never</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Infrequently</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Sometimes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Frequently</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Almost always</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1608	ed_trans_chf Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Severe heart failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Almost never</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Infrequently</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Sometimes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Frequently</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Almost always</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1609	ed_trans_arf Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Severe renal failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Almost never</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Infrequently</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Sometimes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Frequently</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Almost always</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														

1610	ed_trans_respiratory Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Respiratory distress or respiratory failure	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
1611	ed_trans_shock Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Low blood pressure or shock	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
1612	ed_trans_ams Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Coma (altered mental status or decreased level of consciousness)	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
1613	ed_trans_stroke Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Suspected stroke	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
1614	ed_trans_head_trauma Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Severe head trauma	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know
1615	ed_trans_open_frac Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Open fracture	radio (Matrix) 1 Almost never 2 Infrequently 3 Sometimes 4 Frequently 5 Almost always -1 Don't know

1616	ed_trans_closed_frac Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Closed long bone fracture (e.g. femur)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1617	ed_trans_other_trauma Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Other trauma	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1618	ed_trans_obstructed_labor Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Obstructed labor	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1619	ed_trans_pph Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	Post-partum hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1620	ed_ambulance Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	When patients are transferred from the ED to another hospital/healthcare facility, how often is it by ambulance?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														

1621	ed_trans_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	What, if any, barriers do you commonly encounter when transferring patients to another hospital/healthcare facility? <i>Do not read choices, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1" data-bbox="1044 107 1523 573"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>ed_trans_barrier__1</td> <td>Patient finances</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>ed_trans_barrier__2</td> <td>Availability of transportation</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>ed_trans_barrier__3</td> <td>Patient too sick to transfer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>ed_trans_barrier__4</td> <td>Bed space at accepting hospital</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>ed_trans_barrier__5</td> <td>Approval for transfer from accepting hospital</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>ed_trans_barrier__6</td> <td>Family objection</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>ed_trans_barrier__7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>ed_trans_barrier__0</td> <td>No barriers</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>ed_trans_barrier__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 31</p>	1	ed_trans_barrier__1	Patient finances	2	ed_trans_barrier__2	Availability of transportation	3	ed_trans_barrier__3	Patient too sick to transfer	4	ed_trans_barrier__4	Bed space at accepting hospital	5	ed_trans_barrier__5	Approval for transfer from accepting hospital	6	ed_trans_barrier__6	Family objection	7	ed_trans_barrier__7	Other	0	ed_trans_barrier__0	No barriers	-1	ed_trans_barrier__1	Don't know						
1	ed_trans_barrier__1	Patient finances																																		
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7	ed_trans_barrier__7	Other																																		
0	ed_trans_barrier__0	No barriers																																		
-1	ed_trans_barrier__1	Don't know																																		
1622	ed_trans_barrier_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_trans_barrier(7)] = '1'	Please specify	text																																	
1623	ed_trans_accompany Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1'	When critically ill patients are transferred to other facilities by ambulance, what, if any, staff typically accompany the patient, other than driver? <i>do not read choices, check all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1" data-bbox="1044 774 1528 1398"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>ed_trans_accompany__1</td> <td>Nurse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>ed_trans_accompany__2</td> <td>Clinical officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>ed_trans_accompany__3</td> <td>Medical assistant</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>ed_trans_accompany__4</td> <td>Doctors without specialist training</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>ed_trans_accompany__5</td> <td>Emergency medicine specialists</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>ed_trans_accompany__6</td> <td>Other specialist doctor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>ed_trans_accompany__7</td> <td>Emergency medical technician/paramedic</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>ed_trans_accompany__8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>ed_trans_accompany__0</td> <td>Staff do not typically accompany critically ill patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>ed_trans_accompany__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-2</td> <td>ed_trans_accompany__2</td> <td>Patients do not go by ambulance</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 32</p>	1	ed_trans_accompany__1	Nurse	2	ed_trans_accompany__2	Clinical officer	3	ed_trans_accompany__3	Medical assistant	4	ed_trans_accompany__4	Doctors without specialist training	5	ed_trans_accompany__5	Emergency medicine specialists	6	ed_trans_accompany__6	Other specialist doctor	7	ed_trans_accompany__7	Emergency medical technician/paramedic	8	ed_trans_accompany__8	Other	0	ed_trans_accompany__0	Staff do not typically accompany critically ill patients	-1	ed_trans_accompany__1	Don't know	-2	ed_trans_accompany__2	Patients do not go by ambulance
1	ed_trans_accompany__1	Nurse																																		
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-2	ed_trans_accompany__2	Patients do not go by ambulance																																		
1624	ed_trans_accompany_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_trans_accompany(8)] = '1'	Please specify	text																																	

1625	ed_trans_treatment Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfer_out] = '1' and [ed_trans_accompany(-2)] <> '1'	When patients are transferred to other facilities by ambulance, what if any treatments can be done in the ambulance? <i>read choices, check all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>ed_trans_treatment__1</td> <td>Vital sign monitoring</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>ed_trans_treatment__2</td> <td>Cardiac monitoring</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>ed_trans_treatment__3</td> <td>IV fluid administration</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>ed_trans_treatment__4</td> <td>IV medication administration</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>ed_trans_treatment__5</td> <td>Blood transfusion</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>ed_trans_treatment__6</td> <td>Oxygen delivery</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>ed_trans_treatment__7</td> <td>Manual bag ventilation (through endotracheal tube or bag-valve-mask)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>ed_trans_treatment__8</td> <td>Mechanical non-invasive ventilation (BIPAP or CPAP)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>ed_trans_treatment__9</td> <td>Mechanical invasive ventilation with endotracheal tube</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>ed_trans_treatment__0</td> <td>None</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>ed_trans_treatment__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 33</p>	1	ed_trans_treatment__1	Vital sign monitoring	2	ed_trans_treatment__2	Cardiac monitoring	3	ed_trans_treatment__3	IV fluid administration	4	ed_trans_treatment__4	IV medication administration	5	ed_trans_treatment__5	Blood transfusion	6	ed_trans_treatment__6	Oxygen delivery	7	ed_trans_treatment__7	Manual bag ventilation (through endotracheal tube or bag-valve-mask)	8	ed_trans_treatment__8	Mechanical non-invasive ventilation (BIPAP or CPAP)	9	ed_trans_treatment__9	Mechanical invasive ventilation with endotracheal tube	0	ed_trans_treatment__0	None	-1	ed_trans_treatment__1	Don't know
1	ed_trans_treatment__1	Vital sign monitoring																																		
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-1	ed_trans_treatment__1	Don't know																																		
1626	ed_arrive_ambulance Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Emergency Unit (ED)D. Clinical</i> What proportion (%) of patients with emergency conditions are brought to the facility by ambulance with formally trained prehospital care providers? <i>enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (number, Min: -2, Max: 100) Question number: 34																																	
1627	ed_must_triage Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Are there regulations and/or protocols mandating that acutely ill or injured patients are clinically triaged prior to being required to register?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 35</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																											
0	No																																			
1	Yes																																			
-1	Don't know																																			
1628	ed_must_pay Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Does the facility require payment prior to provision of initial emergency care?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 36</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																											
0	No																																			
1	Yes																																			
-1	Don't know																																			
1629	ed_electronic_register Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Is there an electronic system for registration?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 37</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																											
0	No																																			
1	Yes																																			
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1630	ed_has_triage Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Does this facility use a formal triage system (includes a structured triage tool used by trained personnel 24 hours per day, 7 days per week)?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 38</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																											
0	No																																			
1	Yes																																			
-1	Don't know																																			
1631	ed_triage_system Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_triage] = '1'	Which system? <i>enter -1 if unknown</i>	text Question number: 39																																	

1632	ed_triage_attempted Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_triage] = '0'	Has triage ever been attempted?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 40</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1633	ed_triage_timing Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_triage] = '1'	Are there time targets for each triage category (e.g. YELLOW-seen by provider within 2 hours)?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 41</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1634	ed_triage_tracked Show the field ONLY if: [ed_triage_timing] = '1'	Is compliance (to time targets) tracked regularly?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 42</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1635	ed_triage_peds Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Are there specific triage protocols for children < 5 years of age?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 43</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1636	ed_triage_pregnant Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Are there specific triage protocols for pregnant women?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 44</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1637	ed_protocol_triage Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Are the following protocols available at this facility</i> Protocol for systematic triage that ensure patients are seen in order of acuity	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 45</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1638	ed_protocol_surveillance Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Syndromic surveillance guidelines with links to public health officials for case definition and reporting	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1639	ed_protocol_crowding Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Clear protocol for communication with hospital administration during times of overcrowding	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								
1640	ed_protocol_ext_event Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Emergency unit specific emergency response protocol, including protocol for mass casualty incidents?	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know
0	No								
1	Yes								
-1	Don't know								

1641	ed_protocol_abcd Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Are the following clinical management protocols available at this facility</i> Protocol for initial approach to ABCs (airway, breathing, circulation, etc.) and basic neurologic function	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 46
1642	ed_protocol_trauma Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Trauma care checklist	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1643	ed_protocol_med_resus Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Medical resuscitation checklist	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1644	ed_protocol_neo_resus Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for neonatal resuscitation	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1645	ed_protocol_volume Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for volume resuscitation of children and adults	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1646	ed_protocol_malnourish Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for adjusting interventions for malnourished patients	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1647	ed_protocol_pt_pep Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for post-exposure prevention of STI/HIV, emergency contraception, counseling	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1648	ed_protocol_labor Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for management of labor and delivery in low risk women	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1649	ed_protocol_asthma Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Condition-specific management protocols for:</i> Asthma exacerbation	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 47
1650	ed_protocol_pneumonia Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Pneumonia	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1651	ed_protocol_ob_bleed Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Maternal hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know

1652	ed_protocol_sepsis Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Sepsis	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1653	ed_protocol_dka Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1654	ed_protocol_other Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Other	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1655	ed_protocol_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_protocol_other] = '1'	Please specify	text
1656	ed_protocol_inter_trans Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Are the following disposition protocols available at this facility</i> Acuity-based internal transfer protocols to OR or ICU	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 48
1657	ed_protocol_dispo Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for timely disposition from the emergency unit	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1658	ed_protocol_pt_comm Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for conveying information about discharge or disposition to the patient	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1659	ed_protocol_handoff Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Hand-over protocols when transferring patients from one care provider to another	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1660	ed_protocol_ext_trans Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Are the following outside transfer protocols available at this facility</i> Condition-specific transfer or referral protocols (e.g. criteria for transfer of burn patients to burn center)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 49
1661	ed_protocol_trans_comm Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Communication with receiving facility prior to transfer of patients with emergency conditions	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1662	ed_protocol_infect_contr Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Are the following safety protocols available at this facility</i> Infection prevention and control protocols	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 50

1663	ed_protocol_hcw_pep Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for post exposure prophylaxis for health care workers	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1664	ed_protocol_security Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Security protocols to protect staff, patients, and infrastructure from violence	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1665	ed_protocol_hazards Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Protocol for managing hazardous exposures (including designated decontamination area)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1666	ed_protocol_waste Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Containment and disposal of sharps and biomedical waste	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1667	ed_protocol_inter_event Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Plan to ensure emergency unit staff and patient safety if an incident occurs within the emergency unit (including space, transport, communications)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1668	ed_sw Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Emergency Unit (ED) Ancillary Services Please rate the availability of each item 1 to 3 1 - Generally unavailable 2 - Some availability 3 - Adequate availability Note: If "don't know", enter -1 For rating < 3, mark all relevant barriers: Infrastructure Absent Equipment Broken Equipment Stock Out (Supplies) Training Personnel User Fees Opening Hours Other</i> Social work services	radio (Matrix) 1 Generally Unavailable 2 Some Availability 3 Adequate Availability -1 Don't know
1669	ed_sw_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_sw] = '1' or [ed_sw] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox 1 ed_sw_barrier__1 Infrastr. 2 ed_sw_barrier__2 Absent equip 3 ed_sw_barrier__3 Broken equip 4 ed_sw_barrier__4 Stock out 5 ed_sw_barrier__5 Training 6 ed_sw_barrier__6 Prsnnl. 7 ed_sw_barrier__7 User fees 8 ed_sw_barrier__8 Opening hours 9 ed_sw_barrier__9 Other
1670	ed_sw_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_sw_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text
1671	ed_transport Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Patient transport services (within ED)	radio (Matrix) 1 Generally Unavailable 2 Some Availability 3 Adequate Availability -1 Don't know

1672	ed_transport_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transport] = '1' or [ed_transport] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_transport_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_transport_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_transport_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_transport_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_transport_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_transport_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_transport_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_transport_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_transport_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_transport_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_transport_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_transport_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_transport_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_transport_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_transport_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_transport_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_transport_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_transport_barrier__9	Other
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3	ed_transport_barrier__3	Broken equip																												
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9	ed_transport_barrier__9	Other																												
1673	ed_transport_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transport_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1674	ed_security Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Security	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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3	Adequate Availability																													
-1	Don't know																													
1675	ed_security_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_security] = '1' or [ed_security] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_security_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_security_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_security_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_security_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_security_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_security_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_security_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_security_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_security_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_security_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_security_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_security_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_security_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_security_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_security_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_security_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_security_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_security_barrier__9	Other
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8	ed_security_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	ed_security_barrier__9	Other																												
1676	ed_security_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_security_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1677	ed_spirit Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Spiritual support	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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-1	Don't know																													
1678	ed_spirit_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_spirit] = '1' or [ed_spirit] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_spirit_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_spirit_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_spirit_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_spirit_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_spirit_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_spirit_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_spirit_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_spirit_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_spirit_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_spirit_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_spirit_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_spirit_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_spirit_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_spirit_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_spirit_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_spirit_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_spirit_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_spirit_barrier__9	Other
1	ed_spirit_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
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1679	ed_spirit_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_spirit_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1680	ed_qi Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Emergency Unit (ED) Quality Improvement</i> Are there quality improvement projects in the ED currently or at any time in the past year?^ <i>A quality improvement project is an effort to improve patient care based on an evaluation of the shortcomings of the care the ED provides and the changing knowledge base that informs best care</i>	radio 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 60
1681	ed_registry Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Is there a systematic process for collecting patient data that links condition, management, and outcomes (e.g. trauma registry)?	radio 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 61
1682	ed_m_and_m Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Are there regular meetings convened to use clinical data for quality improvement (e.g. morbidity and mortality conferences, preventable death panels)?	radio 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 62
1683	ed_audits Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Is there tracking (e.g. clinical audit) to ensure that quality improvement actions (e.g. corrective action) are implemented after review meetings?	radio 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 63
1684	ed_clin_template Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Is there a clinical document template (e.g. standardized clinical chart)?	radio 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 64
1685	ed_ext_visitor Show the field ONLY if: [ed_clin_lead] = '1'	Has there been a visit to this emergency facility by a supervisor from outside the facility within the last 6 months?	radio 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 65
1686	ed_ext_visitor_org Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ext_visitor] = '1'	What organization did the supervisor work for?	radio 1 NGO (e.g. PIH, CHAM) 2 Ministry of Health 3 Other -1 Don't know Question number: 66
1687	ed_ext_visitor_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ext_visitor_org] = '3'	Please specify	text
1688	ed_ext_visitor_doc Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ext_visitor] = '1'	Is there any documentation from the most recent external supervisory visit?	radio 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 67

1689	ed_ext_visitor_doc_detail Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ext_visitor_doc] = '1'	Does the document provide any feedback or comments on some aspect of emergency services?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 68</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
1690	ed_triagevital	Section Header: <i>Emergency Unit (ED) Signal Functions Please rate the availability of each item 1 to 3 1 - Generally unavailable 2 - Some availability 3 - Adequate availability Note: If "don't know", enter -1 For rating < 3, mark all relevant barriers: Infrastructure Absent Equipment Broken Equipment Stock Out (Supplies) Training Personnel User Fees Opening Hours Other</i> Are vital signs measured in the triage area?	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1691	ed_triagevital_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_triagevital] = '1' or [ed_triagevital] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_triagevital_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_triagevital_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_triagevital_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_triagevital_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_triagevital_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_triagevital_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_triagevital_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_triagevital_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_triagevital_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_triagevital_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_triagevital_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_triagevital_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_triagevital_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_triagevital_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_triagevital_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_triagevital_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_triagevital_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_triagevital_barrier__9	Other
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1692	ed_triagevital_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_triagevital_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1693	ed_checkvital	Are vital signs measured in the Emergency Unit?	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1694	ed_checkvital_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_checkvital] = '1' or [ed_checkvital] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_checkvital_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_checkvital_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_checkvital_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_checkvital_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_checkvital_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_checkvital_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_checkvital_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_checkvital_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_checkvital_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_checkvital_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_checkvital_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_checkvital_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_checkvital_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_checkvital_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_checkvital_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_checkvital_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_checkvital_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_checkvital_barrier__9	Other
1	ed_checkvital_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
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9	ed_checkvital_barrier__9	Other																												
1695	ed_checkvital_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_checkvital_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1696	ed_manual	Section Header: <i>Airway Interventions</i> Use of manual maneuvers (e.g. jaw thrust, chin lift)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1697	ed_manual_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_manual] = '1' or [ed_manual] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_manual_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_manual_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_manual_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_manual_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_manual_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_manual_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_manual_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_manual_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_manual_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_manual_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_manual_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_manual_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_manual_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_manual_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_manual_barrier__6	Prsnl.	7	ed_manual_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_manual_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_manual_barrier__9	Other
1	ed_manual_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
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9	ed_manual_barrier__9	Other																												
1698	ed_manual_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_manual_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1699	ed_suction	Use of suction	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1700	ed_suction_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_suction] = '1' or [ed_suction] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_suction_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_suction_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_suction_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_suction_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_suction_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_suction_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_suction_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_suction_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_suction_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_suction_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_suction_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_suction_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_suction_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_suction_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_suction_barrier__6	Prsnl.	7	ed_suction_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_suction_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_suction_barrier__9	Other
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9	ed_suction_barrier__9	Other																												
1701	ed_suction_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_suction_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1702	ed_oronas	Placement of oro- or naso-pharyngeal airway device	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1703	ed_oronas_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_oronas] = '1' or [ed_oronas] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_oronas_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_oronas_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_oronas_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_oronas_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_oronas_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_oronas_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_oronas_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_oronas_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_oronas_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_oronas_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_oronas_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_oronas_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_oronas_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_oronas_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_oronas_barrier__6	Prsnl.	7	ed_oronas_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_oronas_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_oronas_barrier__9	Other
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1704	ed_oronas_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_oronas_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1705	ed_glottic	Placement of supraglottic device	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1706	ed_glottic_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_glottic]= '1' or [ed_glottic]= '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_glottic_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_glottic_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_glottic_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_glottic_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_glottic_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_glottic_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_glottic_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_glottic_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_glottic_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_glottic_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_glottic_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_glottic_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_glottic_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_glottic_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_glottic_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_glottic_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_glottic_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_glottic_barrier__9	Other
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1707	ed_glottic_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_glottic_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1708	ed_intubate	Endotracheal intubation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1709	ed_intubate_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_intubate] = '1' or [ed_intubate] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_intubate_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_intubate_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_intubate_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_intubate_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_intubate_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_intubate_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_intubate_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_intubate_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_intubate_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_intubate_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_intubate_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_intubate_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_intubate_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_intubate_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_intubate_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_intubate_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_intubate_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_intubate_barrier__9	Other
1	ed_intubate_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
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1710	ed_intubate_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_intubate_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1711	ed_cric	Creation of surgical airway	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1712	ed_cric_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cric] = '1' or [ed_cric] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_cric_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_cric_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_cric_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_cric_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_cric_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_cric_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_cric_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_cric_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_cric_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_cric_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_cric_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_cric_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_cric_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_cric_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_cric_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_cric_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_cric_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_cric_barrier__9	Other
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1713	ed_cric_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cric_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1714	ed_triagespo2	Section Header: <i>Breathing Interventions</i> Measurement of pulse oximetry at triage	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1715	ed_triagespo2_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_triagespo2] = '1' or [ed_triagespo2] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_triagespo2_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_triagespo2_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_triagespo2_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_triagespo2_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_triagespo2_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_triagespo2_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_triagespo2_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_triagespo2_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_triagespo2_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_triagespo2_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_triagespo2_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_triagespo2_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_triagespo2_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_triagespo2_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_triagespo2_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_triagespo2_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_triagespo2_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_triagespo2_barrier__9	Other
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1716	ed_triagespo2_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_triagespo2_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1717	ed_checkspo2	Measurement of pulse oximetry in the Emergency Unit	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1718	ed_checkspo2_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_checkspo2] = '1' or [ed_checkspo2] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_checkspo2_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_checkspo2_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_checkspo2_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_checkspo2_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_checkspo2_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_checkspo2_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_checkspo2_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_checkspo2_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_checkspo2_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_checkspo2_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_checkspo2_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_checkspo2_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_checkspo2_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_checkspo2_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_checkspo2_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_checkspo2_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_checkspo2_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_checkspo2_barrier__9	Other
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9	ed_checkspo2_barrier__9	Other																												
1719	ed_checkspo2_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_checkspo2_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1720	ed_txasthma	Administration of critical therapies for reactive airway disease	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1721	ed_txasthma_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_txasthma] = '1' or [ed_txasthma] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_txasthma_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_txasthma_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_txasthma_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_txasthma_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_txasthma_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_txasthma_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_txasthma_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_txasthma_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_txasthma_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_txasthma_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_txasthma_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_txasthma_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_txasthma_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_txasthma_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_txasthma_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_txasthma_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_txasthma_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_txasthma_barrier__9	Other
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1722	ed_txasthma_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_txasthma_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1723	ed_giveo2	Administration of oxygen	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1724	ed_giveo2_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_giveo2] = '1' or [ed_giveo2] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_giveo2_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_giveo2_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_giveo2_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_giveo2_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_giveo2_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_giveo2_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_giveo2_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_giveo2_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_giveo2_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_giveo2_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_giveo2_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_giveo2_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_giveo2_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_giveo2_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_giveo2_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_giveo2_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_giveo2_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_giveo2_barrier__9	Other
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1725	ed_giveo2_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_giveo2_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1726	ed_bagmask	Bag-valve-mask ventilation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1727	ed_bagmask_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_bagmask] = '1' or [ed_bagmask] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_bagmask_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_bagmask_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_bagmask_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_bagmask_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_bagmask_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_bagmask_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_bagmask_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_bagmask_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_bagmask_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_bagmask_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_bagmask_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_bagmask_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_bagmask_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_bagmask_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_bagmask_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_bagmask_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_bagmask_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_bagmask_barrier__9	Other
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1728	ed_bagmask_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_bagmask_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1729	ed_ptx	Perform needle decompression of tension pneumothorax	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1730	ed_ptx_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ptx] = '1' or [ed_ptx] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_ptx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_ptx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_ptx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_ptx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_ptx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_ptx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_ptx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_ptx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_ptx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_ptx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_ptx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_ptx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_ptx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_ptx_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_ptx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_ptx_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_ptx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_ptx_barrier__9	Other
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1731	ed_ptx_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ptx_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1732	ed_chesttube	Placement of chest tube	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1733	ed_chesttube_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_chesttube] = '1' or [ed_chesttube] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_chesttube_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_chesttube_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_chesttube_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_chesttube_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_chesttube_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_chesttube_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_chesttube_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_chesttube_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_chesttube_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_chesttube_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_chesttube_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_chesttube_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_chesttube_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_chesttube_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_chesttube_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_chesttube_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_chesttube_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_chesttube_barrier__9	Other
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1734	ed_chesttube_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_chesttube_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1735	ed_nippv	Non-invasive mechanical ventilation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1736	ed_nippv_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_nippv] = '1' or [ed_nippv] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_nippv_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_nippv_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_nippv_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_nippv_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_nippv_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_nippv_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_nippv_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_nippv_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_nippv_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_nippv_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_nippv_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_nippv_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_nippv_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_nippv_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_nippv_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_nippv_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_nippv_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_nippv_barrier__9	Other
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1737	ed_nippv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_nippv_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1738	ed_vent	Invasive mechanical ventilation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1739	ed_vent_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_vent] = '1' or [ed_vent] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_vent_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_vent_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_vent_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_vent_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_vent_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_vent_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_vent_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_vent_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_vent_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_vent_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_vent_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_vent_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_vent_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_vent_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_vent_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_vent_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_vent_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_vent_barrier__9	Other
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1740	ed_vent_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_vent_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1741	ed_number_vented Show the field ONLY if: [ed_vent] = '2' or [ed_vent] = '3'	How many patients can receive mechanical ventilation via a ventilator and endotracheal tube in the ED at any one time? <i>enter 0 if none, -1 if unknown</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000) Question number: 86																											
1742	ed_vent_policy Show the field ONLY if: [ed_vent] = '2' or [ed_vent] = '3'	Is there a written policy for who can or cannot be intubated and/or placed on mechanical ventilation?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> Question number: 87	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
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1743	ed_extubate_policy Show the field ONLY if: [ed_vent] = '2' or [ed_vent] = '3'	Is there a written policy for if and when intubation and/or mechanical ventilation can be withdrawn?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 88</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
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1744	ed_ors	Section Header: <i>Volume Resuscitation Interventions</i> Administer oral rehydration	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1745	ed_ors_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ors] = '1' or [ed_ors] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_ors_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_ors_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_ors_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_ors_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_ors_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_ors_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_ors_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_ors_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_ors_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_ors_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_ors_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_ors_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_ors_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_ors_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_ors_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_ors_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_ors_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_ors_barrier__9	Other
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1746	ed_ors_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ors_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1747	ed_adj_ivf	Adjust fluid resuscitation for malnutrition or severe anemia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1748	ed_adj_ivf_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_adj_ivf] = '1' or [ed_adj_ivf] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_adj_ivf_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_adj_ivf_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_adj_ivf_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_adj_ivf_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_adj_ivf_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_adj_ivf_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_adj_ivf_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_adj_ivf_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_adj_ivf_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_adj_ivf_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_adj_ivf_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_adj_ivf_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_adj_ivf_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_adj_ivf_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_adj_ivf_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_adj_ivf_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_adj_ivf_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_adj_ivf_barrier__9	Other
1	ed_adj_ivf_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
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8	ed_adj_ivf_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	ed_adj_ivf_barrier__9	Other																												
1749	ed_adj_ivf_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_adj_ivf_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1750	ed_piv	Place peripheral IV access	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1751	ed_piv_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_piv] = '1' or [ed_piv] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_piv_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_piv_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_piv_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_piv_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_piv_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_piv_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_piv_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_piv_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_piv_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_piv_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_piv_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_piv_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_piv_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_piv_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_piv_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_piv_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_piv_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_piv_barrier__9	Other
1	ed_piv_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
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9	ed_piv_barrier__9	Other																												
1752	ed_piv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_piv_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1753	ed_io	Establish intraosseous access	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1754	ed_io_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_io] = '1' or [ed_io] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_io_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_io_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_io_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_io_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_io_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_io_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_io_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_io_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_io_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_io_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_io_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_io_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_io_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_io_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_io_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_io_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_io_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_io_barrier__9	Other
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9	ed_io_barrier__9	Other																												
1755	ed_io_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_io_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1756	ed_cutdown	Perform venous cutdown	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1757	ed_cutdown_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cutdown] = '1' or [ed_cutdown] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_cutdown_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_cutdown_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_cutdown_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_cutdown_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_cutdown_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_cutdown_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_cutdown_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_cutdown_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_cutdown_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_cutdown_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_cutdown_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_cutdown_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_cutdown_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_cutdown_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_cutdown_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_cutdown_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_cutdown_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_cutdown_barrier__9	Other
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1758	ed_cutdown_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cutdown_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1759	ed_cvc	Establish central venous access	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1760	ed_cvc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cvc]='1' or [ed_cvc]='2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_cvc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_cvc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_cvc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_cvc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_cvc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_cvc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_cvc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_cvc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_cvc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_cvc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_cvc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_cvc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_cvc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_cvc_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_cvc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_cvc_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_cvc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_cvc_barrier__9	Other
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1761	ed_cvc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cvc_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1762	ed_give_ivf	Administration of IV fluids	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1763	ed_give_ivf_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_give_ivf]='1' or [ed_give_ivf]='2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_give_ivf_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_give_ivf_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_give_ivf_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_give_ivf_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_give_ivf_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_give_ivf_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_give_ivf_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_give_ivf_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_give_ivf_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_give_ivf_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_give_ivf_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_give_ivf_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_give_ivf_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_give_ivf_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_give_ivf_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_give_ivf_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_give_ivf_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_give_ivf_barrier__9	Other
1	ed_give_ivf_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
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1764	ed_give_ivf_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_give_ivf_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1765	ed_foley	Place urinary catheter	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1766	ed_foley_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_foley] = '1' or [ed_foley] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_foley_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_foley_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_foley_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_foley_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_foley_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_foley_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_foley_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_foley_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_foley_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_foley_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_foley_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_foley_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_foley_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_foley_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_foley_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_foley_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_foley_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_foley_barrier__9	Other
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1767	ed_foley_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_foley_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1768	ed_exctrl_bleed	External control of haemorrhage	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1769	ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_exctrl_bleed] = '1' or [ed_exctrl_bleed] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier__9	Other
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1770	ed_exctrl_bleed_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_exctrl_bleed_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1771	ed_pack	Perform packing and/or suture control	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1772	ed_pack_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_pack] = '1' or [ed_pack] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_pack_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_pack_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_pack_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_pack_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_pack_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_pack_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_pack_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_pack_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_pack_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_pack_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_pack_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_pack_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_pack_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_pack_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_pack_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_pack_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_pack_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_pack_barrier__9	Other
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9	ed_pack_barrier__9	Other																												
1773	ed_pack_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_pack_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1774	ed_tourniquet	Apply arterial tourniquet	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1775	ed_tourniquet_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_tourniquet] = '1' or [ed_tourniquet] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_tourniquet_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_tourniquet_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_tourniquet_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_tourniquet_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_tourniquet_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_tourniquet_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_tourniquet_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_tourniquet_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_tourniquet_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_tourniquet_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_tourniquet_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_tourniquet_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_tourniquet_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_tourniquet_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_tourniquet_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_tourniquet_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_tourniquet_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_tourniquet_barrier__9	Other
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1776	ed_tourniquet_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_tourniquet_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1777	ed_pelvicbind	Apply pelvic binding or sheeting	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1778	ed_pelvicbind_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_pelvicbind] = '1' or [ed_pelvicbind] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_pelvicbind_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_pelvicbind_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_pelvicbind_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_pelvicbind_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_pelvicbind_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_pelvicbind_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_pelvicbind_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_pelvicbind_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_pelvicbind_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_pelvicbind_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_pelvicbind_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_pelvicbind_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_pelvicbind_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_pelvicbind_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_pelvicbind_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_pelvicbind_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_pelvicbind_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_pelvicbind_barrier__9	Other
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1779	ed_pelvicbind_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_pelvicbind_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1780	ed_transfuse	Ability to perform safe transfusion (including protocols for appropriate ratios for massive transfusion)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1781	ed_transfuse_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfuse] = '1' or [ed_transfuse] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_transfuse_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_transfuse_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_transfuse_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_transfuse_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_transfuse_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_transfuse_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_transfuse_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_transfuse_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_transfuse_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_transfuse_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_transfuse_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_transfuse_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_transfuse_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_transfuse_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_transfuse_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_transfuse_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_transfuse_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_transfuse_barrier__9	Other
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1782	ed_transfuse_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_transfuse_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1783	ed_pocus	Perform and interpret point of care ultrasound	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1784	ed_pocus_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_pocus] = '1' or [ed_pocus] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_pocus_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_pocus_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_pocus_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_pocus_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_pocus_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_pocus_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_pocus_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_pocus_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_pocus_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_pocus_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_pocus_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_pocus_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_pocus_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_pocus_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_pocus_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_pocus_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_pocus_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_pocus_barrier__9	Other
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1785	ed_pocus_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_pocus_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1786	ed_ecg	Section Header: <i>Cardiac Interventions</i> Perform and interpret ECG	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1787	ed_ecg_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ecg] = '1' or [ed_ecg] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_ecg_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_ecg_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_ecg_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_ecg_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_ecg_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_ecg_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_ecg_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_ecg_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_ecg_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_ecg_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_ecg_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_ecg_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_ecg_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_ecg_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_ecg_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_ecg_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_ecg_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_ecg_barrier__9	Other
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1788	ed_ecg_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ecg_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1789	ed_asa	Administer aspirin for ischemia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1790	ed_asa_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_asa] = '1' or [ed_asa] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_asa_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_asa_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_asa_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_asa_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_asa_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_asa_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_asa_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_asa_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_asa_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_asa_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_asa_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_asa_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_asa_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_asa_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_asa_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_asa_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_asa_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_asa_barrier__9	Other
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1791	ed_asa_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_asa_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1792	ed_defib	Perform external defibrillation and/or cardioversion	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1793	ed_defib_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_defib] = '1' or [ed_defib] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_defib_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_defib_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_defib_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_defib_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_defib_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_defib_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_defib_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_defib_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_defib_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_defib_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_defib_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_defib_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_defib_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_defib_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_defib_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_defib_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_defib_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_defib_barrier__9	Other
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1794	ed_defib_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_defib_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1795	ed_epi	Administration of adrenaline	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1796	ed_epi_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_epi] = '1' or [ed_epi] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_epi_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_epi_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_epi_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_epi_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_epi_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_epi_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_epi_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_epi_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_epi_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_epi_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_epi_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_epi_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_epi_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_epi_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_epi_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_epi_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_epi_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_epi_barrier__9	Other
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1797	ed_epi_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_epi_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1798	ed_inotrope	Administer inotropes <i>Examples of inotropes: digoxin, milrinone, dobutamine</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1799	ed_inotrope_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_inotrope] = '1' or [ed_inotrope] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_inotrope_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_inotrope_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_inotrope_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_inotrope_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_inotrope_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_inotrope_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_inotrope_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_inotrope_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_inotrope_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_inotrope_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_inotrope_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_inotrope_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_inotrope_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_inotrope_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_inotrope_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_inotrope_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_inotrope_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_inotrope_barrier__9	Other
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4	ed_inotrope_barrier__4	Stock out																												
5	ed_inotrope_barrier__5	Training																												
6	ed_inotrope_barrier__6	Prsnnl.																												
7	ed_inotrope_barrier__7	User fees																												
8	ed_inotrope_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	ed_inotrope_barrier__9	Other																												
1800	ed_inotrope_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_inotrope_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1801	ed_rhythm	Administer anti-arrythmics <i>Anti-arrythmics include amiodarone, lidocaine, flecainide, procainamide</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1802	ed_rhythm_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rhythm] = '1' or [ed_rhythm] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_rhythm_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_rhythm_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_rhythm_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_rhythm_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_rhythm_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_rhythm_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_rhythm_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_rhythm_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_rhythm_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_rhythm_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_rhythm_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_rhythm_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_rhythm_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_rhythm_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_rhythm_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_rhythm_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_rhythm_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_rhythm_barrier__9	Other
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9	ed_rhythm_barrier__9	Other																												
1803	ed_rhythm_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rhythm_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1804	ed_lytics	Administration of thrombolytics <i>Thrombolytics include alteplase, urokinase, streptokinase, tenecteplase. They DO NOT include enoxaparin, heparin, warfarin</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1805	ed_lytics_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_lytics] = '1' or [ed_lytics] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_lytics_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_lytics_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_lytics_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_lytics_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_lytics_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_lytics_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_lytics_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_lytics_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_lytics_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_lytics_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_lytics_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_lytics_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_lytics_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_lytics_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_lytics_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_lytics_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_lytics_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_lytics_barrier__9	Other
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1806	ed_lytics_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_lytics_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1807	ed_tamponade	Perform pericardiocentesis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1808	ed_tamponade_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_tamponade] = '1' or [ed_tamponade] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_tamponade_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_tamponade_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_tamponade_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_tamponade_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_tamponade_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_tamponade_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_tamponade_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_tamponade_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_tamponade_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_tamponade_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_tamponade_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_tamponade_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_tamponade_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_tamponade_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_tamponade_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_tamponade_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_tamponade_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_tamponade_barrier__9	Other
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1809	ed_tamponade_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_tamponade_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1810	ed_prctctams	Section Header: <i>Unconscious Patient</i> Protect unconscious patient from secondary injury	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1811	ed_prctctams_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_prctctams] = '1' or [ed_prctctams] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_prctctams_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_prctctams_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_prctctams_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_prctctams_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_prctctams_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_prctctams_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_prctctams_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_prctctams_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_prctctams_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_prctctams_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_prctctams_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_prctctams_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_prctctams_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_prctctams_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_prctctams_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_prctctams_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_prctctams_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_prctctams_barrier__9	Other
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1812	ed_prctctams_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_prctctams_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1813	ed_hypoglyc	Check and/or administer glucose	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1814	ed_hypoglyc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_hypoglyc] = '1' or [ed_hypoglyc] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_hypoglyc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_hypoglyc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_hypoglyc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_hypoglyc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_hypoglyc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_hypoglyc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_hypoglyc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_hypoglyc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_hypoglyc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_hypoglyc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_hypoglyc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_hypoglyc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_hypoglyc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_hypoglyc_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_hypoglyc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_hypoglyc_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_hypoglyc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_hypoglyc_barrier__9	Other
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1815	ed_hypoglyc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_hypoglyc_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1816	ed_insulin	Administer insulin for hyperglycemia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1817	ed_insulin_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_insulin]= '1' or [ed_insulin] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_insulin_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_insulin_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_insulin_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_insulin_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_insulin_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_insulin_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_insulin_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_insulin_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_insulin_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_insulin_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_insulin_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_insulin_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_insulin_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_insulin_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_insulin_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_insulin_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_insulin_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_insulin_barrier__9	Other
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1818	ed_insulin_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_insulin_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1819	ed_lp	Perform lumbar puncture	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1820	ed_lp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_lp] = '1' or [ed_lp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_lp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_lp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_lp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_lp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_lp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_lp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_lp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_lp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_lp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_lp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_lp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_lp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_lp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_lp_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_lp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_lp_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_lp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_lp_barrier__9	Other
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1821	ed_lp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_lp_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1822	ed_benzo	Section Header: <i>Seizure</i> Administer benzodiazepine	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1823	ed_benzo_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_benzo] = '1' or [ed_benzo] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_benzo_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_benzo_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_benzo_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_benzo_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_benzo_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_benzo_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_benzo_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_benzo_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_benzo_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_benzo_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_benzo_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_benzo_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_benzo_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_benzo_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_benzo_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_benzo_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_benzo_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_benzo_barrier__9	Other
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1824	ed_benzo_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_benzo_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1825	ed_ecclamp	Administer IV magnesium for pregnant patient	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1826	ed_ecclamp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ecclamp] = '1' or [ed_eccl amp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_ecclamp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_ecclamp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_ecclamp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_ecclamp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_ecclamp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_ecclamp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_ecclamp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_ecclamp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_ecclamp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_ecclamp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_ecclamp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_ecclamp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_ecclamp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_ecclamp_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_ecclamp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_ecclamp_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_ecclamp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_ecclamp_barrier__9	Other
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1827	ed_ecclamp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ecclamp_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1828	ed_antidote	Administer locally appropriate antidote	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1829	ed_antidote_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_antidote] = '1' or [ed_anti dote] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_antidote_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_antidote_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_antidote_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_antidote_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_antidote_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_antidote_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_antidote_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_antidote_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_antidote_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_antidote_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_antidote_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_antidote_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_antidote_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_antidote_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_antidote_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_antidote_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_antidote_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_antidote_barrier__9	Other
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1830	ed_antidote_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_antidote_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1831	ed_mse	Section Header: <i>Other Neurologic Interventions</i> Perform mental status exam	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1832	ed_mse_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_mse] = '1' or [ed_mse] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_mse_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_mse_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_mse_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_mse_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_mse_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_mse_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_mse_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_mse_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_mse_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_mse_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_mse_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_mse_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_mse_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_mse_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_mse_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_mse_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_mse_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_mse_barrier__9	Other
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1833	ed_mse_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_mse_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1834	ed_thermia	Management of extreme temperatures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1835	ed_thermia_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_thermia] = '1' or [ed_thermia] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_thermia_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_thermia_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_thermia_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_thermia_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_thermia_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_thermia_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_thermia_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_thermia_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_thermia_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_thermia_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_thermia_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_thermia_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_thermia_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_thermia_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_thermia_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_thermia_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_thermia_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_thermia_barrier__9	Other
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1836	ed_thermia_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_thermia_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1837	ed_agitation	Administer appropriate therapeutics for agitation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1838	ed_agitation_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_agitation] = '1' or [ed_agitation] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_agitation_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_agitation_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_agitation_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_agitation_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_agitation_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_agitation_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_agitation_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_agitation_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_agitation_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_agitation_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_agitation_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_agitation_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_agitation_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_agitation_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_agitation_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_agitation_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_agitation_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_agitation_barrier__9	Other
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1839	ed_agitation_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_agitation_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1840	ed_restraint	Ability to provide physical restraints	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1841	ed_restraint_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_restraint] = '1' or [ed_restraint] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_restraint_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_restraint_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_restraint_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_restraint_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_restraint_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_restraint_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_restraint_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_restraint_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_restraint_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_restraint_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_restraint_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_restraint_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_restraint_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_restraint_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_restraint_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_restraint_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_restraint_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_restraint_barrier__9	Other
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1842	ed_restraint_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_restraint_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1843	ed_ivcs	Perform procedural sedation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1844	ed_ivcs_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ivcs] = '1' or [ed_ivcs] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_ivcs_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_ivcs_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_ivcs_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_ivcs_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_ivcs_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_ivcs_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_ivcs_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_ivcs_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_ivcs_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_ivcs_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_ivcs_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_ivcs_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_ivcs_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_ivcs_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_ivcs_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_ivcs_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_ivcs_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_ivcs_barrier__9	Other
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1845	ed_ivcs_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ivcs_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1846	ed_giveabx	Section Header: <i>Sepsis Interventions</i> Administration of IV or IM antibiotics	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1847	ed_giveabx_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_giveabx] = '1' or [ed_giveabx] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_giveabx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_giveabx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_giveabx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_giveabx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_giveabx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_giveabx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_giveabx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_giveabx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_giveabx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_giveabx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_giveabx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_giveabx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_giveabx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_giveabx_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_giveabx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_giveabx_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_giveabx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_giveabx_barrier__9	Other
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1848	ed_giveabx_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_giveabx_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1849	ed_pressor	Administration of IV vasopressors <i>Vasopressors include: dopamine, epinephrine, norepinephrine, vasopressin, phenylephrine</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1850	ed_pressor_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_pressor] = '1' or [ed_pressor] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_pressor_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_pressor_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_pressor_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_pressor_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_pressor_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_pressor_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_pressor_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_pressor_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_pressor_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_pressor_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_pressor_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_pressor_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_pressor_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_pressor_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_pressor_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_pressor_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_pressor_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_pressor_barrier__9	Other
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9	ed_pressor_barrier__9	Other																												
1851	ed_pressor_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_pressor_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1852	ed_para	Perform diagnostic paracentesis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1853	ed_para_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_para] = '1' or [ed_para] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_para_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_para_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_para_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_para_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_para_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_para_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_para_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_para_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_para_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_para_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_para_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_para_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_para_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_para_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_para_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_para_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_para_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_para_barrier__9	Other
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1854	ed_para_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_para_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1855	ed_sourcectrl	Bedside minor surgical techniques for source control (e.g. abscess, empyema)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1856	ed_sourcectrl_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_sourcectrl] = '1' or [ed_sourcectrl] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_sourcectrl_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_sourcectrl_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_sourcectrl_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_sourcectrl_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_sourcectrl_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_sourcectrl_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_sourcectrl_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_sourcectrl_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_sourcectrl_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_sourcectrl_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_sourcectrl_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_sourcectrl_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_sourcectrl_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_sourcectrl_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_sourcectrl_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_sourcectrl_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_sourcectrl_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_sourcectrl_barrier__9	Other
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1857	ed_sourcectrl_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_sourcectrl_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1858	ed_woundcare	Section Header: <i>Trauma Interventions</i> Perform initial appropriate wound care	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1859	ed_woundcare_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_woundcare] = '1' or [ed_woundcare] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_woundcare_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_woundcare_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_woundcare_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_woundcare_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_woundcare_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_woundcare_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_woundcare_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_woundcare_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_woundcare_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_woundcare_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_woundcare_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_woundcare_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_woundcare_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_woundcare_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_woundcare_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_woundcare_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_woundcare_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_woundcare_barrier__9	Other
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1860	ed_woundcare_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_woundcare_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1861	ed_tetanus	Administer tetanus vaccination or IVIG as appropriate	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1862	ed_tetanus_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_tetanus] = '1' or [ed_tetanus] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_tetanus_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_tetanus_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_tetanus_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_tetanus_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_tetanus_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_tetanus_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_tetanus_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_tetanus_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_tetanus_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_tetanus_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_tetanus_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_tetanus_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_tetanus_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_tetanus_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_tetanus_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_tetanus_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_tetanus_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_tetanus_barrier__9	Other
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1863	ed_tetanus_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_tetanus_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1864	ed_rabies	Administer rabies vaccine or IVIG as appropriate	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1865	ed_rabies_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rabies] = '1' or [ed_rabies] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_rabies_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_rabies_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_rabies_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_rabies_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_rabies_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_rabies_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_rabies_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_rabies_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_rabies_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_rabies_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_rabies_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_rabies_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_rabies_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_rabies_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_rabies_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_rabies_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_rabies_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_rabies_barrier__9	Other
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1866	ed_rabies_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rabies_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1867	ed_cspine	Immobilize the cervical spine	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1868	ed_cspine_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cspine] = '1' or [ed_cspine] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_cspine_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_cspine_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_cspine_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_cspine_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_cspine_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_cspine_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_cspine_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_cspine_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_cspine_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_cspine_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_cspine_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_cspine_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_cspine_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_cspine_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_cspine_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_cspine_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_cspine_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_cspine_barrier__9	Other
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1869	ed_cspine_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cspine_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1870	ed_immob_frac	Immobilize fractures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1871	ed_immob_frac_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_immob_frac] = '1' or [ed_immob_frac] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_immob_frac_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_immob_frac_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_immob_frac_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_immob_frac_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_immob_frac_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_immob_frac_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_immob_frac_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_immob_frac_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_immob_frac_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_immob_frac_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_immob_frac_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_immob_frac_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_immob_frac_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_immob_frac_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_immob_frac_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_immob_frac_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_immob_frac_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_immob_frac_barrier__9	Other
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1872	ed_immob_frac_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_immob_frac_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1873	ed_reduce_frac	Perform closed reduction of fracture or dislocation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1874	ed_reduce_frac_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_reduce_frac] = '1' or [ed_reduce_frac] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_reduce_frac_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_reduce_frac_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_reduce_frac_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_reduce_frac_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_reduce_frac_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_reduce_frac_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_reduce_frac_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_reduce_frac_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_reduce_frac_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_reduce_frac_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_reduce_frac_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_reduce_frac_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_reduce_frac_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_reduce_frac_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_reduce_frac_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_reduce_frac_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_reduce_frac_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_reduce_frac_barrier__9	Other
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1875	ed_reduce_frac_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_reduce_frac_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1876	ed_abx4frac	Administer antibiotics for open fracture	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1877	ed_abx4frac_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_abx4frac] = '1' or [ed_abx4frac] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_abx4frac_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_abx4frac_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_abx4frac_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_abx4frac_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_abx4frac_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_abx4frac_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_abx4frac_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_abx4frac_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_abx4frac_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_abx4frac_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_abx4frac_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_abx4frac_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_abx4frac_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_abx4frac_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_abx4frac_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_abx4frac_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_abx4frac_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_abx4frac_barrier__9	Other
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1878	ed_abx4frac_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_abx4frac_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1879	ed_compartsynd	Perform fasciotomy or escharotomy for compartment syndrome	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1880	ed_compartsynd_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_compartsynd]= '1' or [ed_compartsynd] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_compartsynd_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_compartsynd_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_compartsynd_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_compartsynd_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_compartsynd_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_compartsynd_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_compartsynd_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_compartsynd_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_compartsynd_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_compartsynd_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_compartsynd_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_compartsynd_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_compartsynd_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_compartsynd_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_compartsynd_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_compartsynd_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_compartsynd_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_compartsynd_barrier__9	Other
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1881	ed_compartsynd_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_compartsynd_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1882	ed_threeway	Apply three-way dressing for sucking chest wound	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1883	ed_threeway_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_threeway] = '1' or [ed_threeway] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_threeway_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_threeway_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_threeway_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_threeway_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_threeway_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_threeway_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_threeway_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_threeway_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_threeway_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_threeway_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_threeway_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_threeway_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_threeway_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_threeway_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_threeway_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_threeway_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_threeway_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_threeway_barrier__9	Other
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1884	ed_threeway_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_threeway_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1885	ed_opioids	Administer opiate analgesia	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1886	ed_opioids_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_opioids] = '1' or [ed_opioids] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_opioids_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_opioids_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_opioids_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_opioids_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_opioids_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_opioids_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_opioids_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_opioids_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_opioids_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_opioids_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_opioids_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_opioids_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_opioids_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_opioids_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_opioids_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_opioids_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_opioids_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_opioids_barrier__9	Other
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1887	ed_opioids_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_opioids_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1888	ed_avd	Perform assisted vaginal delivery <i>Assisted vaginal delivery is a vaginal delivery performed with the help of a forceps or vacuum device</i>	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1889	ed_avd_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_avd] = '1' or [ed_avd] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_avd_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_avd_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_avd_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_avd_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_avd_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_avd_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_avd_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_avd_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_avd_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_avd_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_avd_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_avd_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_avd_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_avd_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_avd_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_avd_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_avd_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_avd_barrier__9	Other
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1890	ed_avd_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_avd_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1891	ed_oxytocin	Administer uterotonic drug (e.g. oxytocin)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1892	ed_oxytocin_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_oxytocin] = '1' or [ed_oxytocin] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_oxytocin_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_oxytocin_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_oxytocin_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_oxytocin_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_oxytocin_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_oxytocin_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_oxytocin_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_oxytocin_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_oxytocin_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_oxytocin_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_oxytocin_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_oxytocin_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_oxytocin_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_oxytocin_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_oxytocin_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_oxytocin_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_oxytocin_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_oxytocin_barrier__9	Other
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1893	ed_oxytocin_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_oxytocin_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

1894	ed_neonate	Perform neonatal resuscitation	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1895	ed_neonate_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_neonate] = '1' or [ed_neo nate] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_neonate_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_neonate_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_neonate_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_neonate_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_neonate_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_neonate_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_neonate_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_neonate_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_neonate_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_neonate_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_neonate_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_neonate_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_neonate_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_neonate_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_neonate_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_neonate_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_neonate_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_neonate_barrier__9	Other
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1896	ed_neonate_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_neonate_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1897	ed_goc	Section Header: <i>End of Life Care</i> Communicate with patient and/or families, including sharing poor prognoses	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1898	ed_goc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_goc] = '1' or [ed_goc] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_goc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_goc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_goc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_goc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_goc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_goc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_goc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_goc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_goc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_goc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_goc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_goc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_goc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_goc_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_goc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_goc_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_goc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_goc_barrier__9	Other
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1899	ed_goc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_goc_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
1900	ed_cmo	De-escalate care (e.g. stop treatments or remove life support) for patients with poor prognoses based on the expressed goals and wishes of the patient or their families	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1901	ed_cmo_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cmo] = '1' or [ed_cmo] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_cmo_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_cmo_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_cmo_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_cmo_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_cmo_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_cmo_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_cmo_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_cmo_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_cmo_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_cmo_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_cmo_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_cmo_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_cmo_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_cmo_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_cmo_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_cmo_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_cmo_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_cmo_barrier__9	Other
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1902	ed_cmo_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cmo_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1903	ed_ivsedate	Section Header: <i>Critical Care Interventions</i> Administer IV sedatives (e.g. benzodiazepine, propofol)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
1	Generally Unavailable																													
2	Some Availability																													
3	Adequate Availability																													
-1	Don't know																													
1904	ed_ivsedate_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ivsedate] = '1' or [ed_ivsedate] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_ivsedate_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_ivsedate_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_ivsedate_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_ivsedate_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_ivsedate_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_ivsedate_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_ivsedate_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_ivsedate_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_ivsedate_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_ivsedate_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_ivsedate_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_ivsedate_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_ivsedate_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_ivsedate_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_ivsedate_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_ivsedate_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_ivsedate_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_ivsedate_barrier__9	Other
1	ed_ivsedate_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
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8	ed_ivsedate_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	ed_ivsedate_barrier__9	Other																												
1905	ed_ivsedate_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ivsedate_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1906	ed_ivopioid	Administer IV opioids	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1907	ed_ivopioid_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ivopioid] = '1' or [ed_ivopioid] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_ivopioid_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_ivopioid_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_ivopioid_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_ivopioid_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_ivopioid_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_ivopioid_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_ivopioid_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_ivopioid_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_ivopioid_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_ivopioid_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_ivopioid_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_ivopioid_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_ivopioid_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_ivopioid_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_ivopioid_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_ivopioid_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_ivopioid_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_ivopioid_barrier__9	Other
1	ed_ivopioid_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
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7	ed_ivopioid_barrier__7	User fees																												
8	ed_ivopioid_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	ed_ivopioid_barrier__9	Other																												
1908	ed_ivopioid_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ivopioid_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											

1909	ed_q4bmp	Frequently (at least every 4 hours) check electrolytes and adjust management based on results	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Generally Unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Some Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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1910	ed_q4bmp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_q4bmp] = '1' or [ed_q4bmp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>ed_q4bmp_barrier__1</td> <td>Infrastr.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>ed_q4bmp_barrier__2</td> <td>Absent equip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>ed_q4bmp_barrier__3</td> <td>Broken equip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>ed_q4bmp_barrier__4</td> <td>Stock out</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>ed_q4bmp_barrier__5</td> <td>Training</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>ed_q4bmp_barrier__6</td> <td>Prsnnl.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>ed_q4bmp_barrier__7</td> <td>User fees</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>ed_q4bmp_barrier__8</td> <td>Opening hours</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>ed_q4bmp_barrier__9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	ed_q4bmp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_q4bmp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_q4bmp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_q4bmp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_q4bmp_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_q4bmp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_q4bmp_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_q4bmp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_q4bmp_barrier__9	Other
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8	ed_q4bmp_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	ed_q4bmp_barrier__9	Other																												
1911	ed_q4bmp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_q4bmp_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1912	ed_cc_idsick	Section Header: "Emergency Unit (ed) F. Critical Care" Is there a standardized method (e.g. protocol/checklist) for identifying patients who do not arrive critically ill, but become critically ill during their stay in the ED?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 159</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																					
0	No																													
1	Yes																													
-1	Don't know																													
1913	ed_cc_idsick_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cc_idsick] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
1914	ed_cc_diff	Compared to other patients in the ED, what is different about the way you take care of critically ill patients? <i>Read options, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>ed_cc_diff__1</td> <td>Nurse to patient ratios</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>ed_cc_diff__2</td> <td>Type of nursing care</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>ed_cc_diff__3</td> <td>Training level of provders</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>ed_cc_diff__4</td> <td>Monitoring equipment</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>ed_cc_diff__5</td> <td>Frequency of vital signs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>ed_cc_diff__6</td> <td>Capabilities for advanced interventions</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>ed_cc_diff__7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>ed_cc_diff__0</td> <td>No difference</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>ed_cc_diff__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 160</p>	1	ed_cc_diff__1	Nurse to patient ratios	2	ed_cc_diff__2	Type of nursing care	3	ed_cc_diff__3	Training level of provders	4	ed_cc_diff__4	Monitoring equipment	5	ed_cc_diff__5	Frequency of vital signs	6	ed_cc_diff__6	Capabilities for advanced interventions	7	ed_cc_diff__7	Other	0	ed_cc_diff__0	No difference	-1	ed_cc_diff__1	Don't know
1	ed_cc_diff__1	Nurse to patient ratios																												
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7	ed_cc_diff__7	Other																												
0	ed_cc_diff__0	No difference																												
-1	ed_cc_diff__1	Don't know																												
1915	ed_cc_diff_rn_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cc_diff(2)] = '1'	Please specify how type of nursing care is different for critically ill patients	text																											
1916	ed_cc_diff_train_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cc_diff(3)] = '1'	Please specify how training level of providers is different for critically ill patients	text																											
1917	ed_cc_diff equip_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cc_diff(4)] = '1'	Please specify how monitoring equipment is different for critically ill patients	text																											
1918	ed_cc_diff_adv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cc_diff(6)] = '1'	Please specify how capabilities for advanced interventions is different for critically ill patients	text																											

1919	ed_cc_diff_other_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cc_diff(7)] = '1'	Please specify what other things are different about the way you take care of critically ill patients	text																								
1920	ed_cc_space	Is there a dedicated area in the ED preferentially used for critically ill patients	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 161</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																		
0	No																										
1	Yes																										
-1	Don't know																										
1921	ed_cc_beds	How many dedicated beds are there in the ED for critically ill patients?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 100000)																								
1922	ed_cc_census	How many critically ill patients are in the ED today?	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 100000) Question number: 162																								
1923	ed_cc_admit_policy Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cc_space] = '1'	Is there a formal written policy outlining the criteria for placing a patient in the bed(s) reserved for critically ill patients in the ED?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 163</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know																		
0	No																										
1	Yes																										
-1	Don't know																										
1924	ed_cc_admit_role Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cc_space] = '1'	Who makes the decision to place a patient there? <i>do not read, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>ed_cc_admit_role__1</td> <td>Doctor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>ed_cc_admit_role__2</td> <td>Nurse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>ed_cc_admit_role__3</td> <td>Clinical officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>ed_cc_admit_role__4</td> <td>Medical assistant</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>ed_cc_admit_role__5</td> <td>Administrator</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>ed_cc_admit_role__6</td> <td>Patient or patient family</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>ed_cc_admit_role__7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>ed_cc_admit_role__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 164</p>	1	ed_cc_admit_role__1	Doctor	2	ed_cc_admit_role__2	Nurse	3	ed_cc_admit_role__3	Clinical officer	4	ed_cc_admit_role__4	Medical assistant	5	ed_cc_admit_role__5	Administrator	6	ed_cc_admit_role__6	Patient or patient family	7	ed_cc_admit_role__7	Other	-1	ed_cc_admit_role__1	Don't know
1	ed_cc_admit_role__1	Doctor																									
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7	ed_cc_admit_role__7	Other																									
-1	ed_cc_admit_role__1	Don't know																									
1925	ed_cc_admit_role_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cc_admit_role(7)] = '1'	Please specify	text																								
1926	ed_vitals_how	How are vital signs checked on patients in the ED? <i>read choices, select all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>ed_vitals_how__1</td> <td>Manual BP cuff</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>ed_vitals_how__2</td> <td>Automatic BP cuff</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>ed_vitals_how__3</td> <td>Intermittent pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>ed_vitals_how__4</td> <td>Continuous pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>ed_vitals_how__5</td> <td>Continuous cardiac monitor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>ed_vitals_how__6</td> <td>Invasive monitoring (e.g. arterial line)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>ed_vitals_how__7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>ed_vitals_how__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 165</p>	1	ed_vitals_how__1	Manual BP cuff	2	ed_vitals_how__2	Automatic BP cuff	3	ed_vitals_how__3	Intermittent pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)	4	ed_vitals_how__4	Continuous pulse oximeter (SpO2 probe)	5	ed_vitals_how__5	Continuous cardiac monitor	6	ed_vitals_how__6	Invasive monitoring (e.g. arterial line)	7	ed_vitals_how__7	Other	-1	ed_vitals_how__1	Don't know
1	ed_vitals_how__1	Manual BP cuff																									
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1927	ed_vitals_how_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_vitals_how(7)] = '1'	Please specify	text																								

1928	ed_vitals_recheck	Are vital signs rechecked on stable patients in the ED?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 166</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
1929	ed_vitals_recheck_freq Show the field ONLY if: [ed_vitals_recheck] = '1'	How often (in hours)? <i>enter -1 if unknown, -2 if not checked at regular intervals</i>	text (integer, Min: -2, Max: 1000000)												
1930	ed_ccvitals_recheck Show the field ONLY if: [ed_cc_diff(5)] = '1'	Are vital signs rechecked on critically ill patients in the ED?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 167</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
1931	ed_ccvitals_recheck_freq Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ccvitals_recheck] = '1'	How often (in hours)? <i>enter -1 if unknown, -2 if not checked at regular intervals</i>	text (number, Min: -2, Max: 1000000)												
1932	ed_cc_reassessed	Are critically ill patients in the ED reassessed at least twice a day by a clinician who can change the treatment plan if needed?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Almost never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Infrequently</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Sometimes</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Almost always</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH</p>	1	Almost never	2	Infrequently	3	Sometimes	4	Frequently	5	Almost always	-1	Don't know
1	Almost never														
2	Infrequently														
3	Sometimes														
4	Frequently														
5	Almost always														
-1	Don't know														
1933	ed_seen_dka	Section Header: <i>Have you seen > 5 patients over the past 3 months in the ED with each of the following?</i> Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Question number: 169</p>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
1934	ed_seen_seizures	Seizures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
1935	ed_seen_poisoning	Poisoning	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
1936	ed_seen_chf	Severe heart failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														
1937	ed_seen_arf	Severe renal failure	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know						
0	No														
1	Yes														
-1	Don't know														

1938	ed_seen_respiratory	Respiratory distress or respiratory failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1939	ed_seen_shock	Low blood pressure or shock	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1940	ed_seen_ams	Coma (altered mental status or decreased level of consciousness)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1941	ed_seen_stroke	Suspected stroke	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1942	ed_seen_head_trauma	Severe head trauma	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1943	ed_seen_open_frac	Open fracture	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1944	ed_seen_closed_frac	Closed long bone fracture (e.g. femur)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1945	ed_seen_other_trauma	Other trauma	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1946	ed_seen_obstructed_labor	Obstructed labor	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1947	ed_seen_pph	Post-partum hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1948	ed_learn_dka	Section Header: <i>Have you received training in the past year on the following conditions:</i> Diabetic ketoacidosis	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 170

1949	ed_learn_seizures	Seizures	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1950	ed_learn_poisoning	Poisoning	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1951	ed_learn_chf	Severe heart failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1952	ed_learn_arf	Severe renal failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1953	ed_learn_respiratory	Respiratory distress or respiratory failure	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1954	ed_learn_shock	Low blood pressure or shock	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1955	ed_learn_ams	Coma (altered mental status or decreased level of consciousness)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1956	ed_learn_stroke	Suspected stroke	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1957	ed_learn_head_trauma	Severe head trauma	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1958	ed_learn_open_frac	Open fracture	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1959	ed_learn_closed_frac	Closed long bone fracture (e.g. femur)	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
1960	ed_learn_other_trauma	Other trauma	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know

1961	ed_learn_obstructed_labor	Obstructed labor	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1962	ed_learn_pph	Post-partum hemorrhage	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1963	ed_trauma_train	Have staff in your ED received training on Primary Trauma Care?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1964	ed_trauma_train_percent Show the field ONLY if: [ed_trauma_train] = '1'	Approximately what percent of staff have received Primary Trauma Care Training? <i>enter -1 if unknown</i>	text (number, Min: -2, Max: 100)								
1965	ed_trauma_train_follow Show the field ONLY if: [ed_trauma_train] = '1'	Has there been any follow up or ongoing training for Primary Trauma Care Training?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
1966	ed_has_water	Section Header: <i>Emergency Unit (ed) G. Infrastructure and Essential Equipment</i> <i>Rate availability of each item 1 to 3) 1) Generally unavailable 2) Some availability 3) Adequate availability</i> If "don't know", enter -1 Provide comment if rating < 3 Clean, running water	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 174	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1967	ed_has_water_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_water] = '1' or [ed_has_water] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1968	ed_has_electric	Electricity source (e.g. wired, generator)	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 175	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1969	ed_has_electric_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_electric] = '1' or [ed_has_electric] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1970	ed_has_comms	Designated telephone or radio for communicating with other facilities and/or prehospital providers	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 176	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										

1971	ed_has_comms_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_comms] = '1' or [ed_has_comms] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1972	ed_paper_chart	Paper-based ED chart	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1973	ed_paper_chart_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_paper_chart] = '1' or [ed_paper_chart] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1974	ed_elec_chart	Electronic emergency unit chart	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 178	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1975	ed_elec_chart_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_elec_chart] = '1' or [ed_elec_chart] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1976	ed_iso_room	Isolation room for infectious diseases (e.g. TB, haemorrhagic fever)	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 179	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1977	ed_iso_room_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_iso_room] = '1' or [ed_iso_room] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1978	ed_accessible	Easy physical access to emergency unit for those requiring a wheelchair or stretcher	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 180	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1979	ed_accessible_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_accessible] = '1' or [ed_accessible] = '2'	Please comment	text								

1980	ed_waiting	Designated waiting area	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 181	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1981	ed_waiting_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_waiting] = '1' or [ed_waiting] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1982	ed_has_resus	Designated resuscitation area	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 182	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1983	ed_has_resus_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_resus] = '1' or [ed_has_resus] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1984	ed_ecg_monitor	Electronic cardiac monitoring in ED	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1985	ed_ecg_monitor_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ecg_monitor] = '1' or [ed_ecg_monitor] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1986	ed_codecart	Crash trolley or code cart with high-acuity equipment and supplies of various sizes in emergency unit	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 184	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1987	ed_codecart_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_codecart] = '1' or [ed_codecart] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1988	ed_rapid_ambu	Rapid access to a transport ambulance and provider to administer care during transport for patients who need to be transferred to another facility	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 185	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										

1989	ed_rapid_ambu_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rapid_ambu] = '1' or [ed_rapid_ambu] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1990	ed_comm_mech	Is there a dedicated mechanism (radio, telephone) for communication with other facilities for transfer of patients?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 186	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1991	ed_comm_mech_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_comm_mech] = '1' or [ed_comm_mech] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1992	ed_storage	Is there access to storage space within (or with immediate proximity to) the emergency unit, including secure storage for controlled substances?	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 187	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1993	ed_storage_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_storage] = '1' or [ed_storage] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1994	ed_workspace	Access to dedicated staff work area	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 188	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1995	ed_workspace_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_workspace] = '1' or [ed_workspace] = '2'	Please comment	text								
1996	ed_toilet	Access to toilet facilities for patients and staff	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> Custom alignment: LH Question number: 189	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1997	ed_toilet_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_toilet] = '1' or [ed_toilet] = '2'	Please comment	text								

1998	ed_handwash	Access to handwashing facilities in each patient care area	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 190</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
1999	ed_handwash_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_handwash] = '1' or [ed_handwash] = '2'	Please comment	text								
2000	ed_inventory	System for stocking, managing, and dispensing medications in the emergency unit	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 191</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
2001	ed_inventory_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_inventory] = '1' or [ed_inventory] = '2'	Please comment	text								
2002	ed_has_o2	Oxygen in the emergency unit	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1) Generally unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>2) Some availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3) Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>-1) Don't know</td></tr> </table> <p>Custom alignment: LH Question number: 192</p>	1	1) Generally unavailable	2	2) Some availability	3	3) Adequate Availability	-1	-1) Don't know
1	1) Generally unavailable										
2	2) Some availability										
3	3) Adequate Availability										
-1	-1) Don't know										
2003	ed_has_o2_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_o2] = '1' or [ed_has_o2] = '2'	Please comment	text Question number: 193								
2004	ed_o2_piped Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_o2] = '2' or [ed_has_o2] = '3'	Section Header: <i>Which of the following methods supply oxygen in the emergency unit?</i> Central piped system	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
2005	ed_o2_cnctrt Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_o2] = '2' or [ed_has_o2] = '3'	Oxygen concentrator stored in the emergency unit	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
2006	ed_o2_tanks Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_o2] = '2' or [ed_has_o2] = '3'	Tanks that are stored in the emergency unit	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										
2007	ed_o2_central_tank Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_o2] = '2' or [ed_has_o2] = '3'	Call for tank from central location if needed	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	0	No	1	Yes	-1	Don't know		
0	No										
1	Yes										
-1	Don't know										

2008	ed_o2_central_cnctr Show the field ONLY if: [ed_has_o2] = '2' or [ed_has_o2] = '3'	Call for oxygen from concentrator from central location if needed	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
2009	ed_protec_eye	Section Header: Which of the following personal protective equipment is available in the ed? Eye protection	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know Question number: 194
2010	ed_protec_n95	N-95 mask	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
2011	ed_protec_gown	Gowns	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
2012	ed_protec_glove	Gloves	radio (Matrix) 0 No 1 Yes -1 Don't know
2013	ed_drwblood	Section Header: Emergency Unit (ED) Diagnostic Services Please rate the availability of each item 1 to 3 1 - Generally unavailable 2 - Some availability 3 - Adequate availability Note: If "don't know", enter -1 For rating < 3, mark all relevant barriers: Infrastructure Absent Equipment Broken Equipment Stock Out (Supplies) Training Personnel User Fees Opening Hours Other Blood draw for laboratory testing in ED (as opposed to central lab)	radio (Matrix) 1 Generally Unavailable 2 Some Availability 3 Adequate Availability -1 Don't know
2014	ed_drwblood_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_drwblood] = '1' or [ed_drwblood] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox 1 ed_drwblood_barrier__1 Infrastr. 2 ed_drwblood_barrier__2 Absent equip 3 ed_drwblood_barrier__3 Broken equip 4 ed_drwblood_barrier__4 Stock out 5 ed_drwblood_barrier__5 Training 6 ed_drwblood_barrier__6 Prsnl. 7 ed_drwblood_barrier__7 User fees 8 ed_drwblood_barrier__8 Opening hours 9 ed_drwblood_barrier__9 Other
2015	ed_drwblood_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_drwblood_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text
2016	ed_hgb	Hemoglobin	radio (Matrix) 1 Generally Unavailable 2 Some Availability 3 Adequate Availability -1 Don't know

2017	ed_hgb_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_hgb] = '1' or [ed_hgb] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_hgb_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_hgb_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_hgb_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_hgb_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_hgb_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_hgb_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_hgb_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_hgb_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_hgb_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_hgb_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_hgb_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_hgb_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_hgb_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_hgb_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_hgb_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_hgb_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_hgb_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_hgb_barrier__9	Other
1	ed_hgb_barrier__1	Infrastr.																												
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9	ed_hgb_barrier__9	Other																												
2018	ed_hgb_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_hgb_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2019	ed_fbc	Full blood count	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2020	ed_fbc_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_fbc] = '1' or [ed_fbc] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_fbc_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_fbc_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_fbc_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_fbc_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_fbc_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_fbc_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_fbc_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_fbc_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_fbc_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_fbc_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_fbc_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_fbc_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_fbc_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_fbc_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_fbc_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_fbc_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_fbc_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_fbc_barrier__9	Other
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3	ed_fbc_barrier__3	Broken equip																												
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7	ed_fbc_barrier__7	User fees																												
8	ed_fbc_barrier__8	Opening hours																												
9	ed_fbc_barrier__9	Other																												
2021	ed_fbc_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_fbc_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2022	ed_ptinr	Coagulation profile (PT/PTT, INR)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2023	ed_ptinr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ptinr] = '1' or [ed_ptinr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_ptinr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_ptinr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_ptinr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_ptinr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_ptinr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_ptinr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_ptinr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_ptinr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_ptinr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_ptinr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_ptinr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_ptinr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_ptinr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_ptinr_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_ptinr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_ptinr_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_ptinr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_ptinr_barrier__9	Other
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2024	ed_ptinr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ptinr_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

2025	ed_electrolyte	Electrolytes	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2026	ed_electrolyte_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_electrolyte] = '1' or [ed_electrolyte] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_electrolyte_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_electrolyte_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_electrolyte_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_electrolyte_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_electrolyte_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_electrolyte_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_electrolyte_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_electrolyte_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_electrolyte_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_electrolyte_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_electrolyte_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_electrolyte_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_electrolyte_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_electrolyte_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_electrolyte_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_electrolyte_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_electrolyte_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_electrolyte_barrier__9	Other
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2027	ed_electrolyte_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_electrolyte_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2028	ed_buncr	BUN and creatinine	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2029	ed_buncr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_buncr]= '1' or [ed_buncr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_buncr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_buncr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_buncr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_buncr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_buncr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_buncr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_buncr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_buncr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_buncr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_buncr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_buncr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_buncr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_buncr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_buncr_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_buncr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_buncr_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_buncr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_buncr_barrier__9	Other
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2030	ed_buncr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_buncr_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2031	ed_lipase	Lipase	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2032	ed_lipase_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_lipase] = '1' or [ed_lipase] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_lipase_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_lipase_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_lipase_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_lipase_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_lipase_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_lipase_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_lipase_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_lipase_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_lipase_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_lipase_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_lipase_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_lipase_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_lipase_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_lipase_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_lipase_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_lipase_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_lipase_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_lipase_barrier__9	Other
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2033	ed_lipase_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_lipase_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2034	ed_trop	Cardiac marker (e.g. troponin)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2035	ed_trop_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_trop] = '1' or [ed_trop] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_trop_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_trop_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_trop_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_trop_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_trop_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_trop_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_trop_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_trop_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_trop_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_trop_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_trop_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_trop_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_trop_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_trop_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_trop_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_trop_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_trop_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_trop_barrier__9	Other
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2036	ed_trop_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_trop_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2037	ed_abg	Arterial blood gas	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2038	ed_abg_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_abg] = '1' or [ed_abg] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_abg_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_abg_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_abg_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_abg_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_abg_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_abg_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_abg_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_abg_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_abg_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_abg_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_abg_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_abg_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_abg_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_abg_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_abg_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_abg_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_abg_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_abg_barrier__9	Other
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2039	ed_abg_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_abg_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

2040	ed_typescrn	Cross matching for blood and blood products	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2041	ed_typescrn_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_typescrn] = '1' or [ed_type scrn] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_typescrn_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_typescrn_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_typescrn_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_typescrn_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_typescrn_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_typescrn_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_typescrn_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_typescrn_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_typescrn_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_typescrn_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_typescrn_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_typescrn_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_typescrn_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_typescrn_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_typescrn_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_typescrn_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_typescrn_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_typescrn_barrier__9	Other
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2042	ed_typescrn_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_typescrn_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2043	ed_bcx	Blood cultures	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2044	ed_bcx_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_bcx] = '1' or [ed_bcx] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_bcx_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_bcx_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_bcx_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_bcx_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_bcx_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_bcx_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_bcx_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_bcx_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_bcx_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_bcx_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_bcx_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_bcx_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_bcx_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_bcx_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_bcx_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_bcx_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_bcx_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_bcx_barrier__9	Other
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2045	ed_bcx_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_bcx_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2046	ed_sterilesamp	Capacity to obtain sterile blood samples for lab testing	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2047	ed_sterilesamp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_sterilesamp] = '1' or [ed_sterilesamp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_sterilesamp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_sterilesamp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_sterilesamp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_sterilesamp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_sterilesamp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_sterilesamp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_sterilesamp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_sterilesamp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_sterilesamp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_sterilesamp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_sterilesamp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_sterilesamp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_sterilesamp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_sterilesamp_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_sterilesamp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_sterilesamp_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_sterilesamp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_sterilesamp_barrier__9	Other
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2048	ed_sterilesamp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_sterilesamp_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
2049	ed_reportlab	System for reporting lab results in a timely fashion	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2050	ed_reportlab_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_reportlab] = '1' or [ed_reportlab] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_reportlab_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_reportlab_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_reportlab_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_reportlab_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_reportlab_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_reportlab_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_reportlab_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_reportlab_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_reportlab_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_reportlab_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_reportlab_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_reportlab_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_reportlab_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_reportlab_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_reportlab_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_reportlab_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_reportlab_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_reportlab_barrier__9	Other
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2051	ed_reportlab_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_reportlab_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											
2052	ed_udip	Urine dipstick	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2053	ed_udip_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_udip] = '1' or [ed_udip] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_udip_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_udip_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_udip_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_udip_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_udip_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_udip_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_udip_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_udip_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_udip_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_udip_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_udip_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_udip_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_udip_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_udip_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_udip_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_udip_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_udip_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_udip_barrier__9	Other
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2054	ed_udip_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_udip_barrier(9)]='1'	Please specify	text																											

2055	ed_uhcg	Urine pregnancy	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2056	ed_uhcg_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_uhcg] = '1' or [ed_uhcg] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_uhcg_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_uhcg_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_uhcg_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_uhcg_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_uhcg_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_uhcg_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_uhcg_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_uhcg_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_uhcg_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_uhcg_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_uhcg_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_uhcg_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_uhcg_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_uhcg_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_uhcg_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_uhcg_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_uhcg_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_uhcg_barrier__9	Other
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2057	ed_uhcg_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_uhcg_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2058	ed_glucose	Glucose	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2059	ed_glucose_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_glucose] = '1' or [ed_glucose] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_glucose_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_glucose_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_glucose_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_glucose_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_glucose_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_glucose_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_glucose_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_glucose_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_glucose_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_glucose_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_glucose_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_glucose_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_glucose_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_glucose_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_glucose_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_glucose_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_glucose_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_glucose_barrier__9	Other
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2060	ed_glucose_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_glucose_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2061	ed_rdt	Malaria Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT)	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2062	ed_rdt_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rdt] = '1' or [ed_rdt] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_rdt_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_rdt_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_rdt_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_rdt_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_rdt_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_rdt_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_rdt_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_rdt_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_rdt_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_rdt_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_rdt_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_rdt_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_rdt_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_rdt_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_rdt_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_rdt_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_rdt_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_rdt_barrier__9	Other
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2063	ed_rdt_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rdt_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2064	ed_malariasmr	Malaria smear/microscopy	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2065	ed_malariasmr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_malariasmr] = '1' or [ed_malariasmr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_malariasmr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_malariasmr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_malariasmr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_malariasmr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_malariasmr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_malariasmr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_malariasmr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_malariasmr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_malariasmr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_malariasmr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_malariasmr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_malariasmr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_malariasmr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_malariasmr_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_malariasmr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_malariasmr_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_malariasmr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_malariasmr_barrier__9	Other
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2066	ed_malariasmr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_malariasmr_barrier(9)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
2067	ed_rapidhiv	Rapid HIV testing	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2068	ed_rapidhiv_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rapidhiv] = '1' or [ed_rapidhiv] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_rapidhiv_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_rapidhiv_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_rapidhiv_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_rapidhiv_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_rapidhiv_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_rapidhiv_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_rapidhiv_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_rapidhiv_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_rapidhiv_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_rapidhiv_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_rapidhiv_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_rapidhiv_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_rapidhiv_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_rapidhiv_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_rapidhiv_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_rapidhiv_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_rapidhiv_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_rapidhiv_barrier__9	Other
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2069	ed_rapidhiv_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rapidhiv_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

2070	ed_nonportxr	Stationary X-ray	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2071	ed_nonportxr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_nonportxr] = '1' or [ed_nonportxr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_nonportxr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_nonportxr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_nonportxr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_nonportxr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_nonportxr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_nonportxr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_nonportxr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_nonportxr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_nonportxr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_nonportxr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_nonportxr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_nonportxr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_nonportxr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_nonportxr_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_nonportxr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_nonportxr_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_nonportxr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_nonportxr_barrier__9	Other
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2072	ed_nonportxr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_nonportxr_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2073	ed_portxr	Portable X-ray for use in ED	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2074	ed_portxr_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_portxr] = '1' or [ed_portxr] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_portxr_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_portxr_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_portxr_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_portxr_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_portxr_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_portxr_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_portxr_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_portxr_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_portxr_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_portxr_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_portxr_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_portxr_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_portxr_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_portxr_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_portxr_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_portxr_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_portxr_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_portxr_barrier__9	Other
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2075	ed_portxr_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_portxr_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2076	ed_us_hosp	Ultrasound in the hospital	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2077	ed_us_hosp_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_us_hosp] = '1' or [ed_us_hosp] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_us_hosp_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_us_hosp_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_us_hosp_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_us_hosp_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_us_hosp_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_us_hosp_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_us_hosp_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_us_hosp_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_us_hosp_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_us_hosp_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_us_hosp_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_us_hosp_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_us_hosp_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_us_hosp_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_us_hosp_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_us_hosp_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_us_hosp_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_us_hosp_barrier__9	Other
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2078	ed_us_hosp_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_us_hosp_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2079	ed_us_ed	Ultrasound for use in ED	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2080	ed_us_ed_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_us_ed] = '1' or [ed_us_ed] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_us_ed_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_us_ed_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_us_ed_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_us_ed_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_us_ed_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_us_ed_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_us_ed_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_us_ed_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_us_ed_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_us_ed_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_us_ed_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_us_ed_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_us_ed_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_us_ed_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_us_ed_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_us_ed_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_us_ed_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_us_ed_barrier__9	Other
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2081	ed_us_ed_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_us_ed_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2082	ed_ct	CT scan	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Generally Unavailable</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Some Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Adequate Availability</td></tr> <tr><td>-1</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2083	ed_ct_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ct] = '1' or [ed_ct] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>ed_ct_barrier__1</td><td>Infrastr.</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>ed_ct_barrier__2</td><td>Absent equip</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>ed_ct_barrier__3</td><td>Broken equip</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>ed_ct_barrier__4</td><td>Stock out</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>ed_ct_barrier__5</td><td>Training</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>ed_ct_barrier__6</td><td>Prsnnl.</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>ed_ct_barrier__7</td><td>User fees</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>ed_ct_barrier__8</td><td>Opening hours</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>ed_ct_barrier__9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	ed_ct_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_ct_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_ct_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_ct_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_ct_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_ct_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_ct_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_ct_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_ct_barrier__9	Other
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2084	ed_ct_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_ct_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											

2085	ed_systemrad	System for reporting radiology results in a timely fashion	radio (Matrix) <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Generally Unavailable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Some Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Adequate Availability</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Generally Unavailable	2	Some Availability	3	Adequate Availability	-1	Don't know																			
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2086	ed_systemrad_barrier Show the field ONLY if: [ed_systemrad] = '1' or [ed_systemrad] = '2'	Relevant barriers	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>ed_systemrad_barrier__1</td> <td>Infrastr.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>ed_systemrad_barrier__2</td> <td>Absent equip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>ed_systemrad_barrier__3</td> <td>Broken equip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>ed_systemrad_barrier__4</td> <td>Stock out</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>ed_systemrad_barrier__5</td> <td>Training</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>ed_systemrad_barrier__6</td> <td>Prsnnl.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>ed_systemrad_barrier__7</td> <td>User fees</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>ed_systemrad_barrier__8</td> <td>Opening hours</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>ed_systemrad_barrier__9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	ed_systemrad_barrier__1	Infrastr.	2	ed_systemrad_barrier__2	Absent equip	3	ed_systemrad_barrier__3	Broken equip	4	ed_systemrad_barrier__4	Stock out	5	ed_systemrad_barrier__5	Training	6	ed_systemrad_barrier__6	Prsnnl.	7	ed_systemrad_barrier__7	User fees	8	ed_systemrad_barrier__8	Opening hours	9	ed_systemrad_barrier__9	Other
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2087	ed_systemrad_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_systemrad_barrier(9)]= '1'	Please specify	text																											
2088	ed_rads_read	Who interprets radiology results? <i>read choices, choose all that apply</i>	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>ed_rads_read__1</td> <td>Provider</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>ed_rads_read__2</td> <td>Radiologist</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>ed_rads_read__3</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1</td> <td>ed_rads_read__1</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question number: 221</p>	1	ed_rads_read__1	Provider	2	ed_rads_read__2	Radiologist	3	ed_rads_read__3	Other	-1	ed_rads_read__1	Don't know															
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2089	ed_rads_read_spec Show the field ONLY if: [ed_rads_read(3)] = '1'	Please specify	text																											
2090	clinician_ed_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete																					
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